

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Additional Deliverable AD6.6

Inventory of existing EBD, HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritized in PARC

WP 6 – T6.2

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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

Environmental burden of disease (EBD) analyses are quantitative assessments of the burden of disease (including morbidity and mortality) in a specific population that is attributable to environmental factors such as chemicals. Health impact assessment (HIA) is a tool to estimate the health impact of a policy or program on population health. Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including geographic variation and variation between sociodemographic groups), health outcomes (disease frequency (incidence or prevalence), life expectancy), exposure-response functions (ERF; based on mode of action and data from epidemiological as well as toxicological studies), and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform EBD or HIA for chemical exposure. This Additional Deliverable (AD) describes the first round of results of the inventory of such data for the PARC priority substances. The data availability for EBD estimates or HIA calculations, stratification by socioeconomic status (SES), and application of a Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach to assess the causality of exposure-effect associations is evaluated. Finally, we describe how the results were and will be used to select case studies, steer the development of exposure, risk, and health impact indicators, and define activities that will enable data gap filling.

Key Words

Health Impact Assessment (HIA), Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), exposure-response function (ERF), data availability, chemical

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1. Authors and Acknowledgements

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2. Background

Environmental burden of disease (EBD) analyses are quantitative assessments of the burden of disease (including morbidity and mortality) in a specific population that is attributable to environmental factors such as chemicals. Health impact assessment (HIA) is a tool to estimate the health impact of a policy or program on population health. EBD and HIA analyses for current chemical exposure of EU populations can be used to compare the burden of disease attributable to different environmental exposures and to prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken. Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including geographic variation and variation between sociodemographic groups), health outcomes (disease frequency (incidence or prevalence), life expectancy), exposure-response functions (ERF; based on mode of action and data from epidemiological as well as toxicological studies), and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform EBDs or analytical HIAs for chemical exposures prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform an EBD assessment or HIA are often incomplete. In the first year of PARC, the availability of data for EBD calculations or HIA was evaluated for PARC priority substances in PARC project P6.2.4.a. Links to other projects in T6.2.4 were made with respect to availability of data for implementation of a Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach (P6.2.4.b), prioritization of case studies (P6.2.4.c), and selection of exposure, risk or health impact indicators to be developed within PARC (P6.2.4.d).

Scientific, societal and regulatory questions

T6.2.4 consists of four subprojects related to health impact assessment (HIA) or environmental burden of disease (EBD). These are: collection and generation of data of PARC priority chemicals, case studies, improvement of methodologies, and development of a set of risk and health impact indicators. The way in which these EBD or HIA subprojects are linked to and how these will affect policy needs is explained in the following sections.

- Collection and generation of data for PARC priority chemicals: Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including variation per geographical location and socioeconomic status), health outcomes (based on mode of action and dose-response data from toxicological as well as epidemiological studies), relative risk, disease incidence

or prevalence, and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform HIA, EBD for chemical exposures prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform HIA, EBD are often incomplete. This project will evaluate and increase the availability of data for PARC priority substances for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc. Increased availability of suitable data for specific exposure scenarios will facilitate their uptake by regulators for evaluation and prioritization exercises.

- Case studies: EBD, HIA and external costs or social cost benefit analysis (SCBA) of chemical exposures allow to objectify the impacts of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease (BoD) and costs avoided as a result of policies and regulations. Case studies will be performed for PARC priority substances.
- Methodological improvements: Data on exposure, exposure-effect relations, health outcomes, relative risk, and demographics can be used for BoD-calculations, HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis for chemical exposures. Several aspects of EBD or HIA-methodologies can be improved to reduce uncertainties in the calculations. The methodological improvements to be realized via this project will reduce the uncertainties and allow the use of a broader range of data as input for EBD or HIA-calculations. This will improve the usability by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises.
- Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators: indicators related to risk and health impact will be developed in order to quantify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU-populations. The main purpose of developing these indicators is to complement and support monitoring frameworks (e.g., Zero Pollution Strategy, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, and the 8th Environment Action Programme) and to thereby support national and European policy makers (e.g., by evaluating the efficacy of policies through burden of disease or costs estimations).

Indicators related to health impact of chemical exposure support national and European policy makers and can complement and support monitoring frameworks for e.g., the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Strategy, and the 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP).

The project contributes to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals. By doing so, the project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Risk assessment, Burden of Disease calculations, health impact assessment, and (social) cost benefit analyses inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually

improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Thus, this project contributes to PARC's specific objective 2 (SO2), namely, European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment.

Prioritized chemical families

The methodological developments of the activity A6.2.4 will be applied to case studies (section 3). The PARC strategy prioritised chemical families in considering pre-existing knowledge on exposure, hazardous properties including epidemiological data for some of the compounds and concerns on cumulative risks. The identification of the first set of priorities for PARC started before the launch of the Partnership with the legacy from HBM4EU and with a survey sent to the interim governing board members. In order to have a clearer view on the prioritisation strategy within the different WPs, a survey dedicated to the prioritisation of substances and meetings with WPLs and task leaders to discuss the prioritisation of methods took place after the beginning of PARC. The approach and results are overviewed in PARC deliverable D2.1 Prioritisation criteria report WP2. This process led to a prioritised list of 10 chemical families by PARC stakeholders (academia, HBM4EU workshop, European Commission, Ministries of several Member States). The PARC T6.2 task leaders on integrative risk assessment refined these prioritised chemicals groups with the EFSA and the European Commission to ensure synergies with results reported in EFSA opinions or ongoing discussions within working groups of DG SANTE. From these discussions, PFAS, heavy metals, pesticides, and mycotoxins were prioritised in T6.2. These PARC 6.2 priority chemicals are taken into account in selection of case studies in activity A6.2.4 as well as other chemical families in considering other priority criteria (see 'case study selection and implementation' in section 3).

3. Results

Glossary

A glossary was compiled based on terms defined by international organisations (e.g., WHO, OECD), former EU projects (HERA, HBM4EU), and publications in the international scientific literature to establish a common understanding of the definitions used in the context of EBD and HIA in PARC (see **Annex I**).

Inventory of available data

Prioritized chemical groups

For the first year of PARC, chemical groups of interest for EBD or HIA activities were based on the stakeholder input collected during the PARC proposal preparation and the substance groups selected for exposure, hazard and risk assessment in T4.1, T4.2, T5.1, T5.2, T6.2.1 and T6.2.3. This resulted in nomination of the following substance groups for collection of existing EBD estimates and HIAs, exposure data and exposure-effect relationships:

PFAS, Bisphenols, Flame retardants, Phthalates, Pesticides, Metals, Mycotoxins, Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals, and Mixtures.

These inventories, as well as an inventory of available health outcome data, are further explained below and results can be found in **Annex II**.

Inventory of health impact assessments, environmental burden of disease

An initial inventory was made of EBD estimates, HIAs and cost estimates already performed for the prioritized chemical groups based on expert knowledge among the project partners and international scientific and grey literature. The following information was collected (see **Annex II**):

- Substance
- Reference EBD or HIA calculation
- Reference cost calculation
- Methodology for EBD/HIA
- Linked to EBD/HIA indicator
- Targeted population
- Targeted region
- Temporal resolution of exposure and health data
- Spatial resolution of exposure and health data
- Exposure level (background, elevated, high, hotspot, occupational)
- Health effect/ Endpoint
- Reference health data (prevalence/incidence)
- Health effect severity
- Reference exposure-response relationship
- Exposure-response relationship specifications (human, in vivo, in vitro)
- Exposure-response relationship certainty (low, medium, high)
- Quantitative estimate of the exposure-response relationship
- Availability EU external exposure data (region, source/route, temporal and spatial resolution, reference)
- Availability EU internal exposure data (population, region, year, reference)
- Uncertainties

This clearly shows a data gap of EBD calculations which are primarily performed for metals, dioxins, indoor air pollutants (e.g., benzene, formaldehyde, radon) but to a lesser extent or

not at all for PFAS, phthalates, bisphenols, pesticides, etc. There are no DALY estimates made for endocrine disruptors in general.

Inventory of exposure data

An initial inventory of existing European external and internal measured exposure data (in addition to data used in the identified available EBD estimates and HIAs) was made for the prioritized chemicals based on expert knowledge and data collections available among the project partners, information from related projects, and international scientific and grey literature. The following information was collected (see **Annex II**):

- Substance
- Availability EU external exposure data (source/route, reference)
- Source/route external exposure
- Availability EU internal exposure data (reference)
- Region
- Year
- Study population
- Number of participants
- Information on socioeconomic status
- Exposure level (background, elevated, high, hotspot, occupational)
- Remarks

Many priority substance groups in PARC were also studied in HBM4EU which resulted in human biomonitoring (HBM) data for these chemicals for a range of countries and regions across the EU. More information is available via the European HBM Dashboard: [European Human Biomonitoring Dashboard | VITO HBM](#).

Within the EHEN network, several projects, including ATHLETE and EXPANSE, are inventorying which exposure data are available in the cohorts participating in these projects. These inventories are made public via the online meta-data system MOLGENIS (see: <https://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org/catalogue/catalogue/#/networks-catalogue/EHEN>).

These data sources as well as WP3, WP4 and other T6.2 projects will be consulted to screen for additional exposure information beyond what has been collected in Annex II. For instance, in P4.2.1.a, monitoring data on PFAS and EDC (endocrine disrupting chemicals) across Europe will be collected. In P6.2.1.b, and inventory of exposure data collections is compiled to be used for exposure modelling, which can be of use for the T6.2.4 projects as well.

In the exposure data inventory also links are mentioned to IPCHEM (<https://ipchem.irc.ec.europa.eu/>), the European Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring, to scientific papers published by the PARC partners and to the WHO GEMS/Food database covering chemicals in food (<https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/>).

Inventory of exposure-response relationships

An initial inventory of existing studies that describe the exposure-effect relationships (in addition to those used in the identified available EBD estimates and HIAs) was made for the prioritized chemicals based on expert knowledge and information from related projects (e.g.,

information collected by the EHEN network which can be accessed via MOLGENIS). The following information was collected (see **Annex II**):

- Substance
- Health effect/ Endpoint
- Reference
- Study specifications (human, in vivo, in vitro)
- Study/relationship certainty (low, medium, high)
- Exposure range
- Quantitative estimate presented in study
- Year
- Country (in case of human)
- Study population in case of human (age)
- Information on socio-economic status (yes/no)
- Dynamic quantitative estimate (dependent on extra variables)
- Comments (type of study)
- Link

The availability of quantitative estimates that form the basis for exposure-response relationships can be complemented with those that were already derived or are currently being derived based on HBM4EU data (see Table 1) and those that will be derived in the first years of PARC based on HBM4EU data (see Table 2).

Table 1. Finished/Ongoing derivation of exposure-effect associations based on HBM4EU data (see also PARC WP 4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO)

Substance group	Health outcome/ Effect marker/ Pathway	Age group	Partner	Progress
Flame retardants	Health outcome: BMI/Metabolism	C	NIPH	Ongoing
Phthalates/DINCH	Health outcome: BMI/Metabolism	C+T	NIPH	Drafting publication
PFAS	Health outcome: BMI/Metabolism	T	KI	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36334774/
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Health outcome: Sexual maturation	T	VITO	Drafting publication
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH/FRs	Health outcome: Asthma & allergy	C+T	VITO	Drafting publication
Phthalates/DINCH	Health outcome: Neurodevelopment	C	EPIUD	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36136503/
FRs	Health outcome: Neurodevelopment	C	EPIUD	Draft publication distributed to co-authors
PFAS	Effect marker: Reproductive hormones & kisspeptin	T	UGR	Draft publication distributed to co-authors
Phthalates/DINCH	Effect marker: Reproductive hormones & kisspeptin	T	UGR	Drafting publication
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Effect marker: Thyroid hormones	T	UGR	Drafting publication
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Effect marker: Metabolic hormones & kisspeptin	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Effect marker: 8OHdG	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
Phthalates/DINCH/FRs	Effect marker: Available hormones data (chol, ldl, hdl, ...)	C	NIPH	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Effect marker: Epigenetic data	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
Phthalates/DINCH	Pathway: Neurodevelopment & bdnf	C	UGR	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Pathway: Sexual maturation & reproductive hormones	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
Phthalates/DINCH	Pathway: BMI/Metabolism & metabolic hormones	T	NIPH	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
Phthalates/DINCH/FRs	Pathway: BMI/Metabolism & available hormones	C	NIPH	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
PFAS	Pathway: BMI/Metabolism & metabolic hormones	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project
PFAS/Phthalates/DINCH	Pathway: Asthma & allergy & 8OHdG	T	VITO	Initiated in HBM4EU, further analyses in PARC project

C=Children; T=teenagers

Table 2. New research questions for derivation of exposure-effect associations based on HBM4EU data for the general population within the PARC project (see also PARC WP 4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO)

Chemical/chemical group	ERF derivation in PARC
Acrylamide	Is exposure to acrylamide associated with neurologic effects, specifically lower BDNF, in the general population Is exposure to acrylamide associated with metabolic effects (BMI, blood pressure)?
Arsenic	Is arsenic exposure associated with altered metabolism (NBMI, blood pressure)? Does arsenic exposure cause oxidative stress and is this a mechanism for any effect of arsenic on asthma/allergy (8-OHdG)? Is arsenic exposure associated with sexual maturation? Is arsenic exposure associated with changes to epigenetic markers?
Pesticides (glyphosate, pyrethroids, organophosphates)	Are pesticide metabolites associated with asthma/allergy? Are pesticide metabolites associated with metabolism (BMI)?
UV filters	Is exposure to UV-filters associated with metabolic effects (BMI)? Is exposure to UV-filters (2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone, BP3) associated with asthma/allergy?
Bisphenols (BPA, BPF, BPS)	Is exposure to bisphenols associated with metabolic effects (BMI)?
PAHs	Is exposure to PAHs associated with metabolic effects (BMI)?
Mycotoxins	Is exposure to mycotoxins associated with metabolic effects (BMI)?
Cadmium	Is exposure to cadmium associated with metabolic effects (BMI)?

Inventory of health outcome data

Availability and accessibility of European and national health data registries was assessed. Their suitability to derive background health data of different EU countries for EBD or HIA assessments (comparable with the use of GBD estimates), and possibilities for alignment will be assessed in future deliverables. An inventory of the availability of health data for specific countries has been created and will be completed further in the next months. The coverage of the databases ranges from global to European to sub-European and national. The inventory is not complete, yet, but what is currently available suggests that data will be available for most or a larger selection of European countries. Data sources include (environmental) burden of disease studies, cause of death registries, cancer registries, hospital data, general practitioner data, health insurance data, health surveys, birth registries, poisoning registries, etc. Synergies with the other projects, tasks and WPs and beyond will be explored.

The following information was collected (see **Annex II**):

- Name of data source
- Health outcome(s)
- Measure (YLL, YLD, DALY, deaths, prevalence, incidence)
- Type of data (modelled, registry)
- Input data (if modelled)
- Year(s)
- Area (country, region, subnational)
- Link
- Comments

Assessment of data availability

Evaluation of data inventory

The first reflections are presented below on data rich/data poor chemicals; data gaps; data availability for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc., cross-sectional versus longitudinal studies.

We want to emphasize that this is not a complete inventory, but that this inventory merely reflects the databases and publications that the partners involved in this task were aware of and entered into that database.

The completion of the data inventories is an ongoing process during the PARC project. A strategy for making the inventory more complete is currently under discussion. New relevant information on data, exposure-response relationships and performed HIAs/EBDs can be added as the task progresses, particularly in relation to the case studies (T6.2.4.C). Another option would be to contact partners individually and directly to add relevant country-specific health and exposure data.

With the inventory, we identified the HBM4EU database as an important source of human biomonitoring data for PFAS, bisphenol and flame retardants, phthalates, and pesticides, while data for mycotoxins are more limited. Other sources of exposure data, mainly biomonitoring data, but also some data on concentrations of especially metals in food or drinking water, have been identified. For most chemicals, data are available for pregnant women, children, and adults. For bisphenol, data are largely limited to adults however in the EU DEMOCOPHES human biomonitoring project (2010-2012) some countries provided measurements of bisphenols and alternatives in children and pregnant women. Geographical coverage of databases varies between chemicals? from single or a few (regions of) countries to > 10 EU countries (HBM4EU). Some HBM studies are representative of the exposure of the general population in the whole country whereas others are not.

Health databases identified through the inventory include information on morbidity (prevalence and incidence), mortality and DALYs. The geographical coverage of the databases

ranges from global to European to national, and further data collection is required for the completion of the inventory.

In the EBD assessments and HIAs identified through the PARC data inventory, exposure-response functions are commonly based on single cross-sectional studies. Similarly, the inventory of exposure-response associations mainly consists of single epidemiological studies (cross-sectional or longitudinal) and some systematic reviews and meta-analyses. In previous EBD assessments and HIAs, few exposure-response relationships were derived from systematic reviews and meta-analyses and some from (pooled) analyses of longitudinal studies. All exposure-response functions have been derived from studies in humans. In these studies, health impacts are usually expressed as attributable cases or attributable fractions, loss in IQ points, DALYs and costs.

Data required for SES stratification

It has already been shown in large EU HBM projects (DEMOCOPHES & HBM4EU) that chemical exposure differs by socio-economic status (SES) (WHO, 2019) (Govarts et al., 2023). The EU strives to reduce health inequalities (and related exposure inequalities) through zero pollution. This is the first flagship of the Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP) under the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). To reduce these health and exposure inequalities, it is necessary to indicate and monitor which chemicals lead to differences in environmental burden of disease by SES.

The American Psychological Association (APA) defines socioeconomic status (SES) as “the position of an individual or group on the socioeconomic scale, which is determined by a combination of social and economic factors such as income, amount and kind of education, type and prestige of occupation, place of residence, and – in some societies or parts of society – ethnic origin or religious background.” (APA, 2023). In practice, this information is often captured via one or more SES-indicators that act as a proxy for overall SES. These SES-indicators often include but are not limited to education, income, socio-professional status, deprivation, self-perceived poverty and/or social class, and ethnic origin. A problem in epidemiological research is that socioeconomic factors are often not considered or at best regarded as confounders for which the model (e.g., ERF) should be corrected, which could possibly lead to systematic underestimation of socio-economic differences in the health effects of exposure to chemicals (Morrens et al., 2014). Whenever SES is considered, different SES-indicators are used, based on different methods of analysis and cutoff-values which represent the social hierarchy of the population under study at a certain moment in time. This makes it difficult to point out which indicator is best suited to capture SES-information, since some studies might indicate education to be closely associated to a certain health-outcome, while others might find an association between income and the health-outcome. Nevertheless, the SES-indicators that are most prevalently used are education and income, and to a lesser extent, also occupation, deprivation, and sociocultural background (Buekers et

al., 2018; Colles et al., 2015; den Hond et al., 2015; Geens et al., 2014; Govarts & Gilles, 2022; Morrens et al., 2012, 2014; Pathirana & Jackson, 2018; Samoli et al., 2019).

The use of objective measures such as income and education has the advantage of limiting subjective biases in participants' self-reports but fails to assess a participant's subjective SES, social class identity, and thus also an individual's perceived rank within the social hierarchy. Subjective SES-measures have been shown to predict self-rated global health even after controlling for objective SES-measures. Therefore, the APA has recommended that researchers employ both subjective and objective measures in their research on SES (Rubin et al., 2014).

In an effort to reconcile subjective and objective SES-measures, time-dependency and country-comparability of SES-output, the European Deprivation Index (EDI) was put forward (Launoy et al., 2018). The EDI is a framework used to build a country-specific indicator, capable of capturing time-dependent fundamental needs, poverty (both objective and subjective), and deprivation, and furthermore allows for comparison between EU-countries. The basis for this framework is the EU-SILC survey, which is a recurring EU questionnaire coordinated by Eurostat, and contains a list of variables which can be considered fundamental needs. From the EU-SILC survey, information is received on which material items (or lack thereof) are associated with deprivation (income, social exclusion, housing conditions, labour, education and health) on a European scale. Following this information, a national survey is conducted, or national census data is used to identify if there is a match between variables on a national level and the ones on the EU-level. Only the fundamental needs variables that match on both levels and are significantly associated with both subjective and objective poverty (determined via multivariable logistic regression) are used in the construction of the EDI. Finally, the regression coefficients from the model are used as weights assigned to their respective variables and the population group is discretized (e.g., into quintiles, with Q1 being the least deprived and Q5 being the most deprived) (Launoy et al., 2021; Ribeiro et al., 2018). The EDI has already been constructed for several European countries and has primarily been used to investigate and compare socioeconomic inequalities in health-outcomes, both on a national and international level. These health-outcomes include life expectancy, survival rate, hospital deaths, cancer incidence and prevalence, infections, and hip fractures (Ribeiro et al., 2018). Deprivation indices can furthermore also be used to establish dose-response relations. More specifically, the Portuguese version of the EDI was used to demonstrate a positive association between mortality and deprivation (Ribeiro et al., 2018), while an ad hoc developed deprivation index model was used to demonstrate a significant positive association between elevated blood lead level risk and deprivation in Maryland, US (Wheeler et al., 2019).

Individual indicators for SES as education and income are often determined in HBM studies as well as multiple deprivation indexes in which several SES related variables are weighted and combined, to display possible inequalities in chemical exposure by SES. Both have advantages and disadvantages. Next to differences in chemical exposure by SES, the chemical exposure-effect relationship may also vary by SES. For air pollution (Forastiere et al., 2007) and lead

exposure (Marshall et al., 2020) it has already been suggested that people of lower SES may be more susceptible to pollution and that the health effects may be more pronounced. Information on differential chemical exposure by SES is getting more and more available e.g., through HBM data. One goal of PARC T6.2.4 is to obtain a first estimate of the impact of chemical exposure in terms of DALYs or costs and possibly this for different SES categories. The approach could be shown in a case study. In an initial stage, exposure-effect relationships could be estimated and DALY- or social cost calculations could be performed for only one univariate socioeconomic measure (e.g., education or income). The ultimate choice of the SES-measure will primarily depend on the availability and quality of data and how robust that measure is on its own. In a later stage, dose-response functions can be constructed for multivariate or composite SES-measures. In this way, a greater dimension of social and economic well-being (or deprivation) can be captured, and the influence thereof on human health can be calculated. This will help policymakers take action to ultimately reduce health inequalities.

Data required for WoE assessment

Analytical HIA or EBD calculations include an initial hazard assessment and a subsequent selection of exposure-outcome pairs for inclusion in the calculations. Since these pairs should reflect causal associations, application of a Weight of Evidence (WoE) assessment including evaluation of different types of data may be useful to establish causality. **Annex III** already describes some frameworks for addressing causality that can be used in EBD and HIA when multiple sources of data are gathered and evaluated.

Randomised clinical trials are the gold standard for establishing causal relationships. For observational studies, causality of exposure-response relationships is more challenging. The hierarchy of evidence for different study designs is as follows: intervention studies > longitudinal cohort studies > cross-sectional studies. Different Weight of Evidence (WoE) frameworks defined by international agencies or organizations or defined in projects (EFSA¹, ECHA², ANSES³, Athlete project⁴) exist to assess the plausibility of causality following different steps starting with defining the problem and assembling evidence from different types of sources in lines of evidence: epidemiological studies, in vivo studies, in vitro, in silico studies. This evidence needs to be weighted and integrated and often expert judgement is included. New methodologies in which different types of data are integrated are being developed like the development of Bayesian networks (Krewski et al., 2022), Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) (Ferguson et al., 2020), Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) (Perkins et al., 2019). For these networks, modified or evolved Bradford Hill criteria can be applied (Hoffmann et al., 2022; Meek et al., 2014; Spînu et al., 2022).

¹ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/pub/en-1540>

² https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17169198/wo_eu_uncertainty_background_en.docx/4f2b49ab-ade0-6ee3-e977-8abe00c21c23

³ <https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/avis-et-rapport-de-lanses-relatif-au-rapport-illustrations-et-actualisation-des>

⁴ <https://athleteproject.eu/>

An approach to apply a WoE framework and to address uncertainty on the ERF (exposure-response function) in EBD and HIA activities in PARC is currently under development. The WoE approach developed in the Athlete project offers a pragmatic approach for evaluating the weight of evidence and could be applied in the case studies, but this is still under discussion.

One of the aspects we aimed to target in the first year of the PARC 6.2.4 methodology project concerns the uncertainty of the exposure response functions (ERF) applied in HIA and EBD. The current report on WoE methodology in Annex III focuses on causality evaluation, which should precede the development of the exposure-response functions and forms the basis for the selection of exposure-outcome pairs to be included in the quantitative assessments. Other aspects of the ERF like statistical or sampling variation, shape of the ERF (linear vs non-linear), existence of a threshold, underrepresentation of specific groups when the ERF was obtained will be covered in subsequent reports. In general, the WoE approach is part of the methodological improvements for EBD studies under PARC (6.2.4.b) for which work is in progress ([Working paper Methodological improvement 6 2 4 b draft new.docx](#)).

Activities based on data inventories

Case study selection and implementation

During the first year of PARC, a long list of case study proposals for environmental burden of disease or health impact assessment was compiled and a selection of the case studies to be initiated in year 2 was made. For this selection, a framework was established based on the following steps: 1) problem formulation, 2) list of the proposals to rank, 3) criteria definition, 4) criteria documentation, 5) aggregation and weighing of criteria, 6) selection process (multi-criteria decision analysis, MCDA), and 7) communication of the results including uncertainty analysis (see **Annex IV**).

As part of the selection criteria, the availability of exposure data, exposure-effect relation estimates and health outcome data are scored by reviewers (expert judgement + scoring rules). The previously described inventories could be used by case studies holders to document those criteria.

A total of 13 case study proposals were submitted. Twelve of which have been scored. The last proposal was directly related to methodological improvements (for the construction of ERFs) and was thus not scored as the selection criteria were not adapted to effectively score a proposal on methodological improvements. The objective of the proposal will be reformulated and integrated within other case studies when relevant, thereby connecting the projects of T6.2.4 with each other.

	Case study proposal	Leader	Associated partners
1	Environmental burden of a mixture of heavy metals on cancer and cardiovascular related mortality in adults living close to waste incinerators	FMUL (PT)	
2	HIA of arsenic exposure and cancers (lung, bladder & skin)	Sciensano (BE)	DTU (DK), ENSP (PT)
3	HIA of cadmium exposure and chronic kidney disease	Sciensano (BE)	ANSES (FR), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT)
4	HIA of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs and male infertility	DTU (DK)	Sciensano (BE)
5	HIA of lead exposure and cardiovascular diseases and chronic kidney disease	DTU (DK)	Sciensano (BE)
6	Influence of waste co-incineration in a cement plant on cancer burden	OI (SI)	NIJZ (SI)
7	Lead (Pb) and methylmercury (meHg) and IQ loss in Children in Europe	ANSES (FR)	DTU (DK), Sciensano (BE), ENSP (PT), VITO (BE)
8	PFAS exposure and immunotoxicity	VITO (BE)	NIPH (NO), DTU (DK), Sciensano (BE), IISPV (ES)
9	Pyrethroid exposure and association with ADHD	VITO (BE)	RUMC (NL), Sciensano (BE)
10	Alkylaniline-hemoglobin adducts and risk of non-smoking-related bladder	USI (CH)	
11	Comparison of biological effects with albumin adducts of 4,4'-methylenediphenyl diisocyanate (MDI) in workers	USI (CH)	
12	Hemoglobin (Hb) adducts and health effects in workers exposed to nitrotoluenes	USI (CH)	
13	Estimation of Exposure–Response Relations for some PARC priority chemicals by Combining Epidemiologic, Human Biomarker, and Animal Data	UU-IRAS (NL)	

For this first iteration of the selection process, the results of the MCDA were not used to select the case studies given the limited number of proposals. Instead, the core team selected cases studies deemed to perform sufficiently well according to the selection criteria. A two-phase approach with staggered starts will be proposed for the partners leading two case studies to limit their workload.

Concomitant to the launch of the case studies in April 2023, discussions will be held with related activities in other tasks and WPs in order to gather guidance or recommendations on data availability (exposure-effect relationships in WP4 for example), data sharing, modelling tools (from WP7 and WP8), and/or methods (briefly mentioned above) which may lead to some redesigns or adaptations of the case study proposals. Case study leaders and partners will also be brought together to capitalize on their common needs.

Indicator development

In this project, indicators related to risk and health impact will be developed in order to quantify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU-populations. The main purpose of developing these indicators is to complement and support monitoring frameworks (e.g., Zero Pollution Strategy) and to thereby support national and European policy makers (e.g., by evaluating the efficacy of policies through burden of disease or costs estimations). During year 1, two major activities were performed (**Annex V**).

Firstly, an overview was made of existing indicators, which reflect exposure, health risk or health impact, with concrete examples of their usage in the context of chemical exposure and pollution. Special attention was given to indicators capable of capturing total impact, time-trends, spatial differences, socioeconomic status, and also, those indicators that are updated regularly. This was furthermore supplemented with a concise overview of existing policy and regulatory frameworks in which indicators are already used.

Secondly, a set of indicators (long list) was proposed to assess the impact on human health (risk) of selected exposure scenarios, including estimates for intra- and inter-individual variance and population dynamics of exposure and health risk. During the construction of the long list, special attention was given to T6.2.4 partners' interests and expertise regarding indicators, taking into account PARC, policy and scientific relevance, feasibility with respect to data availability, and envisaged timing. The goal of the long list is to provide a list from which indicators can be selected to inform policy makers and to contribute to monitoring frameworks. Which indicators are to be selected will be determined in consultation with the WHO, EEA, ECHA, and with T1.3, WP2 and WP3, while also considering 'timelines of opportunity'. The indicators set forth during the consultation will be used as input, alongside additional input from the case studies (T6.2.4C) to be worked out in year 2 and the HBM-studies to be performed under PARC, for burden of disease calculations and/or assessment of risk and health impact.

Filling data gaps

In case data are lacking for specific case studies or indicators, activities will be defined to fill data gaps:

- Assessment of feasibility to derive population-specific and population-wide (via development of statistical methods to enable appropriate population weighing of available exposure data) exposures, spatio-temporal variations
- Evaluation of possibilities for *in silico* modelling of exposures (e.g., pesticide modelling using MCRA, INTEGRA and HEIMTSA platforms) for prioritized data-poor chemicals, using data-rich chemicals to assess predictive quality
- Evaluation of possibilities to collect data to derive exposure-effect associations by linking exposure, lifestyle, geographical, SES, and health status data, comparing multiple time frames, regions, and populations.

This task has not yet started. We foresee defining case studies focusing on methodological aspects (e.g., for data of chemicals) from year 2 onwards.

- In collaboration with the T6.2.4 projects and with related activities in WP4, 5, 6, 7 and 8, guidance or recommendations in the design of the case studies will be selected for implementation in Y2 (i.e., 2023).

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Annex I

Glossary

Terms indicated with an asterisk (*) will be prominent in the first years of PARC while others may be more relevant towards the end of the project.

Aggregated exposure*

Aggregate exposure is the exposure to one single chemical via all exposure routes (dermal, oral and inhalatory) and from different sources (for example several different consumer products and/ or in combination with food). Human biomonitoring (HBM) is a preferred tool to assess aggregated exposure. (Source: RIVM)

Appraisal (assessment)

Appraisal or assessment follows on from the scoping stage of a HIA, where the potential health impacts which have been identified are assessed and evaluated using the available evidence base. (Source: WHO)

Best available evidence

Conclusive evidence of the links between, for example, socio-environmental factors and health or the effectiveness of interventions is not always available. In such cases, the best available evidence – that which is judged to be the most reliable and compelling – can be used, but with caution. (Source: WHO)

Burden of disease (BoD)*

The burden of disease is a measurement of the gap between a population's current health and the optimal state where all people attain full life expectancy without suffering major ill-health. (Health Promotion Glossary of Terms 2021, WHO 2021)

Causality*

Causality describes the property of being causal, the presence of cause, or ideas about the nature of the relations of cause and effect (Source: Susser, 2001).

Chemical category or chemical group*

A chemical category is a group of chemicals whose physicochemical and human health and/or ecotoxicological properties and/or environmental fate properties are likely to be similar or follow a regular pattern, usually as a result of structural similarity. (Source: OECD)

Cohort study*

Cohort studies are a type of longitudinal study—an approach that follows research participants over a period of time (often many years). Specifically, cohort studies recruit and follow participants who share a common characteristic, such as a particular occupation or demographic similarity. (Source: Barrett and Noble, 2019)

Communicable disease

Any disease that is transmitted between humans or between animals and humans via an agent or medium, such as insects, food, water, direct contact, aerosol spray, or blood and blood-contaminated materials. The disease-causing organisms are referred to as pathogens and cause an infection. Examples are malaria, dengue, cholera, and sexually transmitted infections. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Community participation

Involving the community in an activity such as the planning of projects or carrying out a HIA. There are a number of models of community participation, some of which are outlined in the Gothenburg consensus paper on HIA (WHO, 1999). Levels of participation vary. Manipulation and co-optation can masquerade as participation. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Comparative risk assessment*

Comparative risk assessment evaluates and compares potential health, ecological, and quality-of-life impacts. A comparative risk assessment is a systematic counterfactual approach to estimating health gaps (q.v.) (or changes in health expectancy) causally attributable to a risk factor or a group of risk factors. The underlying approach is the same as the one used in environmental burden of disease assessment (Source: WHO 2016). The Global

burden of disease study follows the general framework established for comparative risk assessment since 2002 (Source: Murray et al. 2020a, 2020b; Murray et al. 2003).

Community health and safety

The health and safety of a community. It includes communicable diseases, noncommunicable diseases, injuries, nutritional disorders, mental health and well-being. These may be changed by a development action. Community health outcomes are mediated by the determinants of health. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Concentration-response function (see also dose-response function)*

Concentration-response functions are generally established based on epidemiological studies and represent the relationship between the concentration of a pollutant to which a population is exposed and the risk of a health outcome. As such, concentration-response functions quantify the health impact per concentration unit of pollutant. (Source: EEA, 2018).

Cost-effectiveness Analysis (CEA)

Systematic comparison of the relative value of different interventions for producing desired effects (i.e., better health and/or longer life, where the denominator reflects the expected gain (e.g., deaths-prevented, quality-adjusted life-years (QALYs), disability adjusted life years (DALYs) or numbers of individuals meeting health recommendations) and the numerator expresses the expected cost of the intervention (Gold et al., 1996). CEA can offer a valuable adjunct to HIA when there is sufficient evidence to generate discrete, credible estimates of the health effects and costs of different policy options. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Cross-sectional study*

A cross-sectional study describes a group of subjects at one particular point in time. (Source: Campbell et al., 2007)

Disability Adjusted Life Year (DALY)*

One DALY represents the loss of the equivalent of one year of full health. DALYs for a disease or health condition are the sum of the years of life lost to due to premature mortality (YLLs) and the years lived with a disability (YLDs) due to prevalent cases of the disease or health condition in a population. DALYs are synthetic indicators of the burden of disease associated with a given exposure. (Source: WHO)

Decision making

The process of reviewing the findings and recommendations of a HIA and making choices about how they should be taken forward. (Source: WHO)

Determinants of health

Determinants of health are factors which influence health status and determine health differentials or health inequalities. They include biological factors (e.g., age, gender and ethnicity), behavior and lifestyles (e.g., smoking, alcohol consumption, diet and physical activity), physical and social environment (e.g., housing quality, workplace stressors, and air pollution), and access to health care (Lalonde, 1974; Labonté 1993). All of these are closely interlinked and differentials in their distribution lead to health inequalities. Analysts conducting an HIA will typically start by asking which of these determinants of health are affected by the proposed policy or project. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Disability weight*

Represents the magnitude of health loss associated with the outcome. Disability weights are measured on a scale from 0 to 1, with 0 implying a state that is equivalent to full health and 1 a state equivalent to death. (Source: Salomon et al., 2015)

Disadvantaged / vulnerable / marginalized groups*

These terms are applied to groups of people who, due to factors usually considered outside their control, do not have the same opportunities as other, more fortunate groups in society. Examples might include unemployed people, refugees and others who are socially excluded. (Source: WHO)

Distribution of effects*

Refers to the differences in health opportunities and risks that are experienced by different communities or population groups. These can be due to, for example, ethnicity, sex and/or gender, age, disability, socioeconomic roles and positions, poverty, education, and social environment. Diversity and health inequality in communities influence the level of vulnerability and, hence, the impact of development. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Dose-response function (see also concentration-response function)*

Dose-response functions measure the relationship between exposure to pollution as a cause and specific outcomes as an effect. They refer to damages/production losses incurred in the current year, regardless of when the pollution occurs. (Source: OECD) Dose-response relationship is also a central concept in toxicology and refers to a biological organism's response to increasing levels of exposure (dose) to a substance.

Doughnut economy or economy of well-being

Economy of well-being. Refers to a policy orientation and a governance approach, which aims to put people and their wellbeing at the center of policy- and decision-making. Taking wellbeing into account in all policies is vitally important to the EU's economic growth, productivity, long-term fiscal sustainability and societal stability. Wellbeing contributes to economic growth (Council of the European Union 2019, 11164/19). (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/> and <https://www.kateraworth.com/doughnut/>)

Economic impact assessment (EIA)

Economic impact assessment involves exploring and identifying the ways in which the economy in general, or local economic circumstances in particular, will be affected by a policy, programme or project. (Source: WHO)

Endocrine disrupting chemical (EDC)*

Substances of very high concern that mimic or inhibit the effects of hormones. (Source: REACH)

Environmental burden of disease (EBD)*

The Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD)-concept was introduced by the World Health Organization to quantify the impacts of environmental risk factors on population health in a comprehensive and comparable way. (Source: Plass et al., 2019)

Environmental impact assessment (EIA)

Environmental impact assessment (EIA) is a well-developed discipline, both in terms of theory and practice, having been in operation for nearly 30 years in the United States (Glasson et al. 1994). Its origins lie in the US National Environmental Policy Acts of 1969. In the same way that HIA explores the effect of policies, programmes and projects on health, EIA does the same in terms of environmental effects. In many countries, including those of the European Union, there is now a statutory requirement for EIA to be undertaken under certain circumstances. The rules vary from country to country but generally EIA should lead to proposals which are likely to have any significant adverse effects on the environment being abandoned or modified. There are numerous definitions of EIA, including the following an assessment of the impact of a planned activity on the environment (UN Economic Commission for Europe, 1991 in Glasson et al, 1994) the process of evaluating the likely environmental consequences of a proposed major action significantly affecting the natural and man-made environment (Walther 1990) a technique and a process by which information about the environmental effects of a project is collected, both by the developed and from other sources, and taken into account by the planning authority in forming their judgements about whether the development should go ahead. (Source: WHO)

Environmental justice*

Environmental justice is the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations and policies. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/> and www.epa.gov)

Equity in health*

Inequity – as opposed to inequality – has a moral and ethical dimension, resulting from avoidable and unjust differentials in health status. Equity in health implies that ideally everyone should have a fair opportunity to attain their full health potential and, more pragmatically, that no one should be disadvantaged from achieving this potential if it can be avoided (WHO EURO, 1985). More succinctly, Equity is concerned with creating equal opportunities for health and with bringing health differentials down to the lowest possible level (Whitehead,

1992). HIA is usually underpinned by an explicit value system and a focus on social justice in which equity plays a major role so that not only both health inequalities and inequities in health are explored and addressed wherever possible (Barnes and Scott-Samuel, 1999). (Source: WHO)

Evaluation

Evaluation involves making a judgement as to how successful (or otherwise) a project has been, with success commonly being measured as the extent to which the project has met its original objectives. Both the “process” (activities) and “outcomes” (what is produced, for example in terms of changes in the health of those targeted by the project) can be monitored and evaluated. (Source: WHO)

Evidence base*

The evidence base refers to a body of information, drawn from routine statistical analyses, published studies and “grey” literature, which tells us something about what is already known about factors affecting health. For example, in the field of housing and health there are a number of studies which demonstrate the links between damp and cold housing and respiratory disease and, increasingly, the links between high quality housing and quality of life. (Source: WHO)

Exposure*

Having come into contact with a cause of, or possessing a characteristic that is a determinant of, a particular health problem. (Source: CDC)

Exposure-response function (see concentration-response function and/or dose-response function)*

Global burden of disease (GBD)*

The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study has been developed by WHO over the past decades. The concept of disease burden refers to a systematic and internally consistent quantification of health problems of a defined population, preferably using a summary measure of population health that integrates mortality and morbidity information. The GBD study estimates the incidence, prevalence, mortality, years of life lost (YLLs), years lived with disability (YLDs), and disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) due to 369 diseases and injuries for 87 risk factors. The Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (<https://www.healthdata.org/>) leads the GBD study and the according methodological developments. (Source: Murray et al. 2020a, 2020b; <https://www.thelancet.com/gbd/about>)

Hazard*

Potential source of harm. Often a subset of health determinants. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Health*

A complete state of physical, social, mental and spiritual well-being, and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity. (Source: WHO)

Health co-benefits

The positive health effects that a policy or measure aimed at one objective might have on other objectives, thereby increasing the total benefits for society or the environment. (Source: <https://www.heraresearch.eu/>)

Health gain

Improvement in health status. (Source: WHO)

Health impact*

A health impact can be positive or negative. A positive health impact is an effect which contributes to good health or to improving health. For example, having a sense of control over one’s life and having choices is known to have a beneficial effect on mental health and wellbeing, making people feel “healthier” (Wilkinson, 1996). A negative health impact has the opposite effect, causing or contributing to ill health. For example, working in unhygienic or unsafe conditions or spending a lot of time in an area with poor air quality is likely to have an adverse effect on physical health status. (Source: WHO)

Health Impact Assessment (HIA)*

HIA is a practical approach used to judge the potential health effects of a policy, programme or project on a population, particularly on vulnerable or disadvantaged groups. Recommendations are produced for decision-makers and stakeholders, with the aim of maximizing the proposal's positive health effects and minimizing its negative health effects. The approach can be applied in diverse economic sectors and uses quantitative, qualitative, and participatory techniques. (Source: Kemm et al., 2004).

WHO distinguishes between "analytical or quantitative" and "comprehensive" HIA with "analytical" having the focus on the information and data collection and the estimation of health impacts; and "comprehensive" HIA being used to engage in decision-making process, involving stakeholders, bringing health arguments to the negotiations by providing evidence (through RAs) and assessing impacts and promoting the most health friendly design and options. (Source: WHO)

Health inequality and inequity*

Health inequalities can be defined as differences in health status or in the distribution of health determinants between different population groups. For example, differences in mobility between elderly people and younger populations or differences in mortality rates between people from different social classes. It is important to distinguish between inequality in health and inequity. Some health inequalities are attributable to biological variations or free choice and others are attributable to the external environment and conditions mainly outside the control of the individuals concerned. In the first case it may be impossible or ethically or ideologically unacceptable to change the health determinants and so the health inequalities are unavoidable. In the second, the uneven distribution may be unnecessary and avoidable as well as unjust and unfair, so that the resulting health inequalities also lead to inequity in health. (Source: WHO)

Health outcome*

Medically defined states of disease or disability, as well as community defined states of well-being. The main categories used in HIA are communicable diseases, noncommunicable diseases, injuries, nutritional disorders, mental health and well-being. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Healthy public policy

Healthy public policy is a key component of the Ottawa Charter for Health Promotion (1986). The concept includes policies designed specifically to promote health (for example banning cigarette advertising) and policies not dealing directly with health but acknowledged to have a health impact (for example transport, education, economics) (Lock, 2000). (Source: WHO)

Health services, health care or health system

Prevention and curative care provided to the population normally under the auspices of a national authority, such as the ministry of health. Services may be offered by private health care providers, government agencies, or both. The capacity of health services is one determinant of community health status; overall community health status is determined by the policies, programs, and projects of all sectors. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

High-throughput methods

High-throughput methods are recent scientific experimentation methods relevant to the field of chemistry and biology, in which hundreds of thousands of experimental samples are subjected to simultaneous testing under given conditions. Using robotics, data processing/control software, liquid handling devices, and sensitive detectors, high-throughput screening methods allow a researcher to quickly conduct millions of chemicals, genetic, or pharmacological tests. Through this process one can rapidly identify for example active compounds, antibodies, genes that modulate a particular biomolecular pathway. As such, the methods are also used to answer complex questions such as assessment of exposure and long-term effects. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/>)

Human biomonitoring (HBM)*

Human biomonitoring is a tool of health-related environmental monitoring with which populations are examined for their exposure to pollutants from the environment. (Source: UBA Germany) Human biomonitoring allows us to measure our exposure to chemicals by measuring either the substances themselves, their metabolites or markers of subsequent health effects in body fluids or tissues (Source: EEA, 2019).

Impact assessment

Impact assessment is about judging the effect that a policy or activity will have on people or places. It has been defined as the “prediction or estimation of the consequences of a current or proposed action” (Vanclay and Bronstein, 1995). (Source: WHO)

Incidence*

Incidence refers to the occurrence of new cases of disease or injury in a population over a specified period of time. (Source CDC)

Incidence based DALY*

Measure the burden of disease in DALYs across an entire lifetime of an individual. (Source: Kim et al., 2022)

Inequalities audit / equity audit

A review of inequalities within an area or of the coverage of inequalities issues in a policy, programme or project, usually with recommendations as to how they can be addressed. (Source: WHO)

Integrated impact assessment

Integrated impact assessment brings together components of environmental, health, social and other forms of impact assessment in an attempt to incorporate an exploration of all the different ways in which policies, programmes or projects may affect the physical, social and economic environment. (Source: WHO)

Longitudinal study*

A longitudinal study is a research method that involves a sample of data being collected repeatedly for the same individuals over time, possibly for many years. (Source: Institute of Epidemiology and Health Care – University College London)

Monitoring

Monitoring is the process of keeping track of events. For example, the monitoring of a project may involve counting the number of people coming into contact with it over a period of time or recording the way in which the project is administered and developed. (Source: WHO)

Multidisciplinary*

A multidisciplinary approach combines or involves several academic disciplines or professional specializations in an approach to a topic or problem. HIA is not the preserve of any one disciplinary group, instead it draws on the experience and expertise of a range of disciplines in its approach. These may include different “stakeholders” such as professionals with knowledge relevant to the issues being addressed, key decision makers, relevant voluntary organizations and – perhaps most importantly – representatives of the communities whose lives will be affected by the policy (Barnes and Scott-Samuel, 1999). (Source: WHO)

Neighborhood

The term neighborhood usually refers to a local area which is defined in some way physically (for example, an estate or an area bounded by major roads) or by people’s perceptions of what constitutes their local area. Neighborhoods are usually fairly small. For example, neighborhoods designated for New Deal for Communities funding are usually made up of around 4,000 households or around 10,000 people. (Source: WHO)

Noncommunicable disease*

Any disease that cannot be transmitted between humans and is not usually an infection; root causes are exposure to pollutants, unhealthy behavior or lifestyle, stress, or genetics. Examples are hypertension, cancer, and diabetes. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Occupational health and safety

Refers to the health, safety, and welfare of people at work. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Odds ratio (OR)*

An OR is a measure of association between an exposure and an outcome. The OR represents the odds that an outcome will occur given a particular exposure, compared to the odds of the outcome occurring in the absence of that exposure. If the OR is greater than 1, then exposure and outcome are associated in the sense that,

compared to the absence of exposure, the presence of exposure raises the odds of the outcome. (Source: Szumilas, 2010)

One Health*

One Health is a collaborative, multisectoral, and transdisciplinary approach—working at the local, regional, national, and global levels—with the goal of achieving optimal health outcomes recognizing the interconnection between people, animals, plants, and their shared environment. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/>)

Outcomes

The effect the process has had on the people targeted by it. These might include, for example, changes in their self-perceived health status or changes in the distribution of health determinants, or factors which are known to affect their health, well-being, and quality of life. (Source: WHO)

Outputs

The products or results of the process. These might include, for example, how many people a project has affected, their ages and ethnic groups or the number of meetings held and the ways in which the findings of the project are disseminated. (Source: WHO)

Partnership

A group of people or organizations brought together with a common purpose such as developing a regeneration programme or undertaking. (Source: WHO)

Planetary Health

Our definition of planetary health is the achievement of the highest attainable standard of health, wellbeing, and equity worldwide through judicious attention to the human systems—political, economic, and social—that shape the future of humanity and the Earth’s natural systems that define the safe environmental limits within which humanity can flourish. Put simply, planetary health is the health of human civilization and the state of the natural systems on which it depends. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/> and Horton et al., 2014)

Policy*

A policy can be defined as an agreement or consensus on a range of issues, goals and objectives which need to be addressed (Wood-Ritsatakis et al., 2000). For example, “Saving Lives: Our Healthier Nation” can be seen as a national health policy aimed at improving the health of the population of England, reducing health inequalities and setting objectives and targets which can be used to monitor progress towards the policy’s overall goal or aims. (Source: WHO)

Population (Affected population)*

Groups of individuals defined by locality, biological criteria (e.g., age, gender, health condition, or common exposure), or social criteria (e.g., socio-economic status or cultural affiliation). How a population is defined in an HIA will depend on the proposed project/policy being considered, health issues of most concern, the extent and classification of existing evidence on those health issues, and what information is of most value to the policy-making process. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Population attributable fraction (PAF)*

The portion of the incidence rate of a given outcome in a given population that is identified as due to a given exposure (Prüss-Üstün et al 2003).

Population exposure

Estimation of the exposure level or exposure distribution of the studied population.

Population Health

The health of groups, families and communities, defined by locality, biological criteria (e.g., age, gender or health condition), or social criteria (e.g., socio-economic status or cultural affiliation). The population health approach, which provides a foundation for HIA, emphasizes health as a resource or capacity, not simply a state. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Prevalence*

Prevalence, sometimes referred to as prevalence rate, is the proportion of persons in a population who have a particular disease or attribute at a specified point in time or over a specified period of time. Prevalence differs from incidence in that prevalence includes all cases, both new and preexisting, in the population at the specified time, whereas incidence is limited to new cases only. (Source: CDC)

Prevalence based DALY*

The pure prevalence-based approach is characterized by measuring the burden of disease in the year of incidence instead of across the entire lifetime of an individual. (Source: Kim et al., 2022)

Process

A course of action or series of activities. (Source: WHO)

Programme

The term programme usually refers to a group of activities which are designed to be implemented in order to reach policy objectives (Wood-Ritsatakis et al., 2000). For example, many Single Regeneration Budget programmes and New Deal for Communities initiatives have a range of themes within their programmes – often including health, community safety (crime), education, employment and housing – and within these themes are a number of specific projects which, together, make up the overall programme. (Source: WHO)

Project

A project is usually a discrete piece of work addressing a single population group or health determinant, usually with a pre-set time limit. For example, “Private Rented Dwellings” was a three-year project in Southport, Merseyside which provided money to private landlords in order to bring their rented properties up to housing fitness standards. (Source: WHO)

QALY

The Quality-Adjusted Life Year (QALY) is a standardized measure of disease burden which combines both survival and health-related quality of life into a single index. The QALY is primarily used in cost-effectiveness analyses to guide decisions regarding the distribution of limited health care resources among competing health programs or interventions for a population of interest but has also been used to aid decisions regarding clinical management and individual patient care. (Source: Encyclopedia of Behavioral Medicine)

Qualitative and quantitative evidence*

HIA tries to balance qualitative and quantitative evidence. It involves an evaluation of the quantitative, “scientific” evidence where it exists but also recognizes the importance of more qualitative information. This may include the opinions, experience and expectations of those people most directly affected by public policies and tries to balance the various types of evidence (Barnes and Scott Samuel, 1999). Generally speaking, quantitative evidence is based on what can be counted or measured objectively whilst qualitative evidence cannot be measured in the usual ways and may more subjective, for example, encompassing people’s perceptions, opinions and views. (Source: WHO)

Relative Risk (RR)*

The ratio of the probability of an event occurring in an exposed group versus an unexposed group. A relative risk of 1 indicates that there is no difference in the two groups’ risk of the event. A relative risk of 2 indicates that the exposed group has double the risk of the unexposed group. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Resource allocation

The process of deciding what is needed to carry out an activity and providing for those needs. This can include making provision for financial resources (money), capital resources (such as buildings and computer hardware) and staff resources (including the number of staff needed and the skill mix required). (Source: WHO)

Risk Assessment (RA)*

The quantitative approach to HIA incorporates many of the elements also found in risk assessment laid out in environmental impact assessment and engineering. The risk assessment paradigm prescribes a sequence for four steps for assessing risks: (1) hazard identification, (2) exposure assessment, (3) dose-response assessment, and (4) risk characterization (i.e., evaluation of impact of changing exposure levels. Usually, but not necessarily this

process is quantitative. Despite apparent objectivity, it is dependent on a series of assumptions and analytic choices. (Source: Nurminen et al. 1999).

Risk, Attributable

The proportion of new events or cases in a given time period attributable to exposure to a risk factor (Kleinbaum, 1982). (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Risk Factor

Social, economic or biological status, behaviours or environments which are associated with or cause increased susceptibility to a specific disease, ill health, or injury. (Health Promotion Glossary of Terms 2021, WHO 2021)

Scoping

Scoping refers to the process of identifying the potential health impacts of a policy, programme or project before they are quantified, as in a rapid HIA. It may include reviewing the relevant literature and evidence base and collecting the views of key stakeholders (those with expert knowledge of the project, those involved and those potentially affected) followed by the tabulation of the potential health impacts (Parry and Stevens, 2001). (Source: WHO)

Screening

In relation to HIA, screening usually refers to an initial step being taken in order to determine whether a policy, programme or project should be subject to a HIA. The criteria used for this process may include, for example, the size and cost of the activity in question, the extent of any obvious or immediate health effects or the perceived extent of longer-term effects. A new road transport policy, for example, might meet these criteria in view of its potentially high financial cost, the possibility of immediate health effects in terms of road traffic accidents and likely longer-term effects in terms of air quality. (Source: WHO)

SES factors*

SES, socio-economic status, is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others. Factors used include income, education, and occupation. SES is often used to describe differences in society as a whole, such as differences among geographic areas, student populations, or social groups. The measure is often used to both explain and predict the development in several areas, such as study results, health status, or income differences. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/>)

Severance

A physical barrier created by a transport or other development project that creates a physical, social and psychological separation for individuals and groups within a community or between communities. (Source: Asian Development Bank)

Social impact assessment

Social impact assessment is “the process of assessing or estimating, in advance, the social consequences that are likely to follow from specific policy actions or project development, particularly in the context of appropriate national, state or provisional policy legislation” (Vanclay and Bronstein, 1995). It is based on the assumption that the way in which the environment is structured can have a profound effect on people’s ability to interact socially with other people and to develop networks of support. For example, a major road cutting across a residential area can have the effect of dividing a community with implications for social cohesion. (Source: WHO)

Steering group

A group of people brought together to oversee a piece of work such as a HIA. Typically, a steering group might be made up of representatives of relevant professional groups, key statutory agencies and the local community and its terms of reference might include overseeing development and progress of the work; agreeing the methodological framework and timescales; providing an input of local knowledge and information; acting as a bridge between partners; facilitating the implementation of the assessment's recommendations; and helping to assimilate and disseminate the emerging lessons (Source: WHO)

Strategy

The term strategy usually refers to a series of broad lines of action intended to achieve a set of goals and targets set out within a policy or programme (Wood-Ritsatakis et al., 2000). For example, within the themes of Single Regeneration Budget or New Deal for Communities initiatives it is usual to set out the strategic direction needed to be taken in order to achieve the goals and objectives of each theme, such as reducing unemployment, improving health or raising educational attainment. (Source: WHO)

Sustainable development

Sustainable development is defined by the United Nations as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It calls for concerted efforts towards building an inclusive, sustainable, and resilient future for people and planet. For sustainable development to be achieved, it is crucial to harmonize three core elements: economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection. These elements are interconnected, and all are crucial for the well-being of individuals and societies. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/> and <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/development-agenda/>)

Stakeholder

Individuals representing one or more disciplines, sectors, or types of organizations in the health-environment-climate nexus that can either impact the success and execution of the agenda or are impacted by it. (Source: <https://www.heraresearcheu.eu/>)

Uncertainty*

HIA is fundamentally about clarifying uncertainty – pointing out and attempting to minimize specific areas of uncertainty about the possible health impacts of a proposed policy. There are many types of uncertainty, including “model uncertainty” (uncertainty about the logical and mathematical representation to explain phenomena) and “parameter uncertainty” (certainty about the value, variation, accuracy, etc. of a specific relations or conditions in a model). High levels of uncertainty (especially model uncertainty) may preclude HIA, but at the same time the value of information from an HIA tends to be highest when there are high levels of uncertainty. (Source: UCLA, adapted & expanded from WHO)

Well-being impact assessment

Well-being impact assessment is difficult to distinguish from HIA although it could be argued that, instead of looking at all aspects of health, including medical factors, it concentrates primarily on aspects of quality of life and physical and mental wellbeing. (Source: WHO)

Working group

In contrast to a steering group, a working group convened for the purpose of carrying out usually consists of those charged with carrying out the work on a day-to-day basis. Typically, it might include people with a range of complementary public health skills such as project management, epidemiology, statistical analysis and presentation, questionnaire design and community development. (Source: WHO)

Workshops

Workshops involve bringing together a group of people for a specific purpose. In HIA this might include, for example, identifying key stakeholders’ health concerns in relation to the policy, programme or project being addressed, identifying sources of current knowledge in relation to the evidence base or training staff in HIA techniques. Workshops are usually structured in some way with a mixture of presentations and “hands on” participative work. (Source: WHO)

YLD*

One YLD represents the equivalent of one full year of healthy life lost due to disability or ill-health. See DALYs. (Source: WHO)

YLL*

YLLs are calculated from the number of deaths multiplied by a global standard life expectancy at the age at which death occurs. See DALYs. (Source: WHO)

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Annex II

Inventory of EBD, HIA, exposure, exposure-effect and health outcome data

Chemical group	Substance	Reference HIA calculation	Reference cost calculation	Methodology	Linked to indicator?	Targeted population	Targeted region	Temporal resolution (year, day...)	Spatial resolution (country, municipality...)	Exposure level (background, elevated, high eg. hotspot, occupational)	Health effect/ endpoint	Reference health data (prevalence/incidence)	Health effect severity	Reference exposure-response function (ERF)	ERF specifications (human, in vivo, in vitro)	ERF certainty (low, medium, high)	Quantitative ERF estimate	Availability EU external exposure data (region, source/route, temporal and spatial resolution, reference)	Availability EU internal exposure data (population, region, year, reference)	Uncertainties	Remarks	Info added by partner(s):		
Metals	Lead	Hänninen et al. 2014		DALys	No	children and adults	Europe			Background	Mild mental retardation and hypertension			MMR: Lanphear et al. 2003; Hypertension: Fawcett et al. 2003								VITO		
Metals	Lead	https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-5-11-human-biomonitoring-in-risk-assessment-4th-set-of-examples-on-the-use-of-hbm-in-risk-assessments-of-hbm4eu-priority-chemicals/		DALys	No	children and adults	Europe			Background & hotspot	Mild mental retardation and premature mortality			MMR: Lanphear et al. 2005; Premature mortality: Lanphear et al. 2018							Study under HBM4EU	VITO		
Metals	Lead	Bierkens, J., Buekers, J., Van Holderbeke, M., & Torfs, R. (2012). Health impact assessment and monetary valuation of IQ loss in pre-school children due to lead exposure through locally produced food. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 414, 90-97. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.10.048	Spadaro, J. V., & Rabi, A. (2004). Pathway Analysis for Population-Total Health Impacts of Toxic Metal Emissions (https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0272-4332.2004.00514.x), <i>Risk Analysis</i> , 24(5), 1121-1141. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0272-4332.2004.00514.x	Test case on community policies affecting human exposure to lead - Full-chain impact pathway approach (consecutive model calculation: MUSE-HM, WATSON, XtraFOOD, IEURK)	Blood lead (B-Pb) levels?	Children 1 to 5 years (pre-school)	EU-27	Year 2000, 2000-2010 and 2000-2020	Results expressed: point estimates for each EU member state	Background	Reduction of average loss in IQ points/child	Meta-analysis performed by Schwartz, J. (1994). Low-Level Lead Exposure and Children's IQ: A Metaanalysis and Search for a Threshold. <i>Environmental Research</i> , 65(1), 42-55. https://doi.org/10.1006/enrs.1994.1020	2.6 IQ point decrease for B-Pb increase from 10 to 20 µg/dL	Meta-analysis performed by Schwartz, J. (1994). Low-Level Lead Exposure and Children's IQ: A Metaanalysis and Search for a Threshold. <i>Environmental Research</i> , 65(1), 42-55. https://doi.org/10.1006/enrs.1994.1020	A meta analysis of 8 individual studies examining the relationship in school age children (the association between B-Pb levels, children's IQ) was performed		External dose modeling (XtraFOOD, MUSE-HM (levels in air) deposition data and the WATSON (soil data))	Internal dose modelling (IEURK)	...The WATSON calculated soil concentrations mainly rely on deposition fluxes which are significantly lower than the actual measured background values in EU countries, what underpredicts the contribution of soil. The latter leads to lower B-Pb levels comparing biomonitoring data (EU project (MFAFSE)) and low loss of IQ. Further needed refinements: differentiation between feeding habits between countries (XtraFOOD model), empirical relationship between B-Pb and loss of IQ.			NIJZ		
Metals	11 Metals	Majanka et al. 2022. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.107662	R.K. Rosenbaum, M.A.J. Huijbregts, A.D. Henderson, M. Margni, T.E. McKone, D. van de Meent, M.Z. Hauschild, S. Shukla, D.S. Li, L.S. GOMEZ O. <i>Intergovernmental human exposure and toxicity factors for comparative assessment of toxic emissions in life cycle analysis: Sensitivity to key chemical properties</i> . <i>Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.</i> , 16 (8) (2011), pp. 710-727. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-011-0316-4	DALys	No	Preschool children	Europe	9th December 2014 to 23rd May 2015	Silesia province of southern Poland	background	Cancer and non-cancer endpoints	Fantke et al., (2018, 2021) https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP3871 https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11367-021-01899-y											Asnes	
Metals	Lead	Holnicki et al. 2017 (reference?)		DALys	No	General population	Europe	Year 2012	Warsaw (Poland)	Background	Mild Mental Retardation (MMR)			https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42715	human								Asnes	
Metals	Lead	Holnicki et al. 2017		Attributable deaths and DALys	No	General population	Europe	Year 2012	Warsaw (Poland)	Background	Cardiovascular disease			https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42715	human								Asnes	
Metals	Lead	Carrington et al. 2015		Attributable incidence, DALys		Children aged 3-7 years	Global	2015	WHO regions	Background (from food only)	Intellectual disability			Lanphear et al. 2005	human	Uncertainty in exposure-response function propagated throughout calculations	-0.48 (95% CI -1.19; -0.0) IQ points/µg/dL Pb in the blood					IQ reductions due to Pb exposure during early childhood assumed to be lifelong; IQ as sole measure of neurodevelopment.	Only dietary exposure to Pb considered.	DTU
Metals	Lead, inorganic arsenic, cadmium and methylmercury	Thomsen et al. 2022		Attributable incidence, YLD, YLL, DALys		Children aged 5 years	Europe	2019	Denmark	Background (from food only)	Intellectual disability			Lanphear et al. 2005	human	Uncertainty in exposure-response function propagated throughout calculations	-0.48 (95% CI -1.19; -0.0) IQ points/µg/dL Pb in the blood					IQ reductions due to Pb exposure during early childhood assumed to be lifelong; IQ as sole measure of neurodevelopment.	Only dietary exposure to Pb considered.	DTU
Metals	Lead, inorganic arsenic, cadmium and methylmercury	Thomsen et al. 2022		Attributable incidence, mortality, YLD, YLL, DALys		Adults > 40 years	Europe	2019	Denmark	Background (from food only)	Late stage chronic kidney disease			Ginsberg et al. 2012	human		7.8% decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) per µg/L Cd in the urine					Only dietary exposure to Cd considered. Cd exposure from other sources (e.g. smoking) not included.	DTU	
Metals	Methylg	Bellanger et al. 2019		Attributable incidence, DALys		Women of childbearing age (and their unborn children)	Global	2015	WHO regions	Background	Intellectual disability (IQ < 70)			Axelrad et al. 2007	human		-0.18 point IQ (95% CI: -0.38, -0.01) per µg/g increase in maternal hair Hg					IQ reductions due to Methylg exposure during fetal development assumed to be lifelong; IQ as sole measure of neurodevelopment.	DTU	
Metals	Lead, inorganic arsenic, cadmium and methylmercury	Thomsen et al. 2022		Attributable incidence, YLD, YLL, DALys		Women of childbearing age (and their unborn children)	Europe	2019	Denmark	Background (from food only)	Intellectual disability (IQ < 85)			Zelmaker et al. 2013	human	Uncertainty in exposure-response function propagated throughout calculations	-8.5 IQ points (95% CI -1.5; -19.5) per µg maternal exposure to Methylg/kg bw/day					IQ reductions due to Methylg exposure during fetal development assumed to be lifelong; IQ as sole measure of neurodevelopment.	DTU	
EDC	PBDE	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		All neonates	USA	Year	Country	Background	IQ points loss and intellectual disability	Points loss and cases			Human?								FMUL	
	Organophosphate pesticides	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		All neonates	USA	Year	Country	Background	IQ points loss and intellectual disability	Points loss and cases											FMUL	
	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Children aged 10 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	childhood obesity	cases											FMUL	
	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Adults aged 50-64 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	adult diabetes	cases											FMUL	
	Di-2-ethylhexylphthalate	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Women aged 50-64 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	adult obesity	cases											FMUL	
	Di-2-ethylhexylphthalate	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Women aged 50-64 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	adult diabetes	cases											FMUL	
	Bisphenol A	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Children aged 4 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	childhood obesity	cases											FMUL	
	PBDE	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		All boys and men	USA	Year	Country	Background	testicular cancer	cases											FMUL	
	PBDE	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		All male neonates	USA	Year	Country	Background	cryptorchidism	cases											FMUL	
	Benzophthalates and butylphthalates	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Men aged 20-39 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	male infertility resulting in increased assisted reproductive technology	cases											FMUL	
	Phthalates	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Men aged 55-64 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	low testosterone resulting in increased early mortality	attributable deaths											FMUL	
	Multiple exposures	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Children aged 12 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	ADHD	cases											FMUL	
	Multiple exposures	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Children aged 8 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	autism	cases											FMUL	
	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Women aged 15-54 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	fibroids	cases											FMUL	
	Di-2-ethylhexylphthalate	Attina et al. 2016		Attributable burden of disease and costs		Women aged 20-44 years	USA	Year	Country	Background	endometriosis	cases											FMUL	
	polybrominated diphenyl ethers	Bellanger et al. 2015 . doi: 10.1210/er.2014-4323	Bellanger et al. 2015 . doi: 10.1210/er.2014-4323	estimates of total IQ points lost, attributable cases and cost		General population	European Union	Year/lifetime	Continent	Background	reduced cognition (IQ loss and intellectual disability)	cases?			Human	moderate-to-high	10-fold increase in prenatal BDE-47 was associated with a 4.5-point decrease (95% CI: -8.8, -0.1) in Full-Scale IQ and a 3.3-point increase (95% CI: 0.3, 6.3) in the hyperactivity score at age 5 years	European Union Food exposure European Food Safety Authority. Scientific opinion on polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) in food. http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/doc/2156.pdf . Published August 4, 2014. Accessed October 3, 2014.			biomarker data were not available for all EU countries, and judgment was used in extrapolating to the EU as a whole. The calculations could not take into account potential differences between exposure levels in the member states.		FMUL	
	organophosphate pesticides	Bellanger et al. 2015 . doi: 10.1210/er.2014-4323	Bellanger et al. 2015 . doi: 10.1210/er.2014-4323	estimates of total IQ points lost, attributable cases and cost		General population	European Union	Year/lifetime	Continent	Background	reduced cognition				Human	moderate-to-high	Bouchard et al (63) reported that a 10-fold increase in total urinary DAP was associated with a loss of 5.6 IQ points (28, 40), whereas Engel et al (41) reported that a 10-fold increase was associated with a loss of 1.39 points.						FMUL	

endocrine disruptor exposures (including phthalates)	Bellanger et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4323	Bellanger et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4323	attributable cases and cost	General population	European Union	Year/lifetime	Continent	Background	autism spectrum disorder			Braun JM, Kalkbrenner AE, Just AC, et al. Gestational exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals and reciprocal social, repetitive, and stereotypic behaviors in 4- and 5-year-old children: the HOME study. <i>Environ Health Perspect.</i> 2014;122:513-520. Miodovnik A, Engel SM, Zhu C, et al. Endocrine disruptors and childhood social impairment. <i>Neurotoxicology.</i> 2011;32:261-267.	Human	low	EBD: 2.50 increase in serum concentrations of polybrominated diphenyl ether-28 (PBDE-28) ($\beta = 2.5$; 95% CI: -0.6, 5.6) or trans-nonachlor ($\beta = 4.1$; 95% CI: 0.8-7.3) was associated with more autistic behaviors. In contrast, fewer autistic behaviors were observed among children born to women with detectable versus nondetectable concentrations of PCB-178 ($\beta = -3.0$; 95% CI: -6.3, 0.3), β -hexachlorocyclohexane ($\beta = -3.3$; 95% CI: -6.1, -0.5), or PBDE-85 ($\beta = -3.2$; 95% CI: -5.9, -0.5). Increasing perfluorooctanoate (PFOA) concentrations were also associated with fewer autistic behaviors ($\beta = -2.0$; 95% CI: -4.4, 0.4). Increasing log-transformed low molecular weight (LMW) phthalate metabolite concentrations were associated with greater social deficits ($\beta = 1.5$; 95% CI: 0.25-2.8). LMWP were also associated with poorer Social Cognition ($\beta = 1.40$; 95% CI 0.1-2.7); Social Communication ($\beta = 1.86$; 95% CI 0.5-3.2); and Social Awareness ($\beta = 1.25$; 95% CI	FMUL
endocrine disruptor exposures (including OP and PBDE)	Bellanger et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4323	Bellanger et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4323	attributable cases and costs	General population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder			Bouchara MF, Billinger DL, Wright RO, Weisskopf MG. Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder and urinary metabolites of organophosphate pesticides. <i>Pediatrics.</i> 2010;125:e1270-e1277. Gascon M, Vrijheid M, Martinez D, et al. Effects of pre and postnatal exposure to low levels of polybromodiphenyl ethers on neurodevelopment and thyroid hormone levels at 4 years of age. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2011;37:605-611. Chen A, Yolton K, Rauch SA, et al. Prenatal polybrominated diphenyl ether exposures and neurodevelopment in U.S. children through 5 years of age: the HOME study. <i>Environ Health Perspect.</i> 2014;122(8):856-862. Marks AR, Harley K, Bradman A, et al. Phthalate metabolite Chen A, Yolton K, Rauch SA, Webster G, M., Horning R, Spdin A, et al. 2014. Prenatal polybrominated diphenyl ether exposures and neurodevelopment in U.S. children through 5 years of age: the HOME study. <i>Environ Health Perspect.</i> 2014;122(8):856-862.	Human	low-to-moderate		FMUL
PBDE	Gaylord et al. 2020. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2019.110166	Gaylord et al. 2020. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2019.110166	attributable cases and costs	General population	USA	Lifetime	Country	Background	Intellectual disability	NHANES	IQ less than 70	4.5 IQ points lost per log unit increase in prenatal PBDE exposure with a threshold value of 6.4 ng/g		FMUL		
PBDE	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	attributable cases and costs	Male population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	Testicular cancer	GI/OBORGAN. Estimated Cancer Incidence, Mortality and Prevalence Worldwide in 2012. International Agency for Research on Cancer. http://globocon.iarc.fr . Accessed August 2014.		Hardell L, Bavel B, Lindström G, Eriksson M, Carlberg M. In utero exposure to persistent organic pollutants in relation to testicular cancer risk. <i>Int J Androl.</i> 2006;29:228-234.	Human	very low	OR = 3.8, 95% CI = 1.4-10	FMUL
PBDE	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	attributable cases and costs	Male population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	Cryptorchidism	Prevalence: 0.9-1.8% Virtanen HE, Toppari J. Epidemiology and pathogenesis of cryptorchidism. <i>Hum Reprod Update.</i> 2008;14:46-58		The concentration of PBDEs in breast milk was significantly higher in boys with cryptorchidism than in controls (sum of BDEs 47, 153, 99, 100, 28, 66, and 154: median, 4.16 vs. 3.16 ng/g fat; $p < 0.007$)	FMUL			
Phthalates	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	attributable cases and costs	Male population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	Infertility	World Bank. Population (total). http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?orderwbapi_data_value_2010wbapi_data_valuewbapi_data_value-firstSort asc . Accessed January 3, 2014.	Time to pregnancy	Men's urinary concentrations of monomethyl-, mono-n-butyl-, and monobutyl phthalates were associated with a longer TTP (FOR 0.80; 95% CI, 0.70, 0.93; FOR 0.82; 95% CI 0.70, 0.97; and FOR 0.77; 95% CI, 0.65-0.92, respectively)	FMUL			
Phthalates	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	Hauser et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4325	attributable cases and costs	Male population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	Reduced serum T	rate	mortality	strong (experimental/toxicological data), low (epidemiological evidence)		FMUL		
diphenyldichloroethene (DDE)	Hunt et al. 2016. doi: 10.1210/jc.2015-2873	Hunt et al. 2016. doi: 10.1210/jc.2015-2873	attributable cases and costs	Female population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	fibroids	Fernandez H, Farrugia M, Jones SE, Maukopf JA, Oppelt P, Subramanian D. Rate, type, and cost of invasive interventions for uterine myomas in Germany, France, and England. <i>J Minim Invasive Gynecol.</i> 2009;16:40-46.		per 1-SD increase in log-transformed p,p'-DDE OR (95% CI): 1.37 (1.05-1.80)	Govarts E, Nieuwenhuijzen M, Schoeters G, et al. Birth weight and prenatal exposure to polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE): a meta-analysis within 12 European Birth Cohorts. <i>Environ Health Perspect.</i> 2012;120:162-170.	FMUL		
phthalate	Hunt et al. 2016. doi: 10.1210/jc.2015-2873	Hunt et al. 2016. doi: 10.1210/jc.2015-2873	attributable cases and costs	Female population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	endometriosis	Abbas S, Ihle P, Köster I, Schubert I. Prevalence and incidence of diagnosed endometriosis and risk of endometriosis in patients with endometriosis-related symptoms: findings from a statutory health insurance-based cohort in Germany. <i>Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.</i> 2012;160:79-83.		six phthalate metabolites-mono-n-butyl phthalate, mono-(2-carboxymethyl)hexyl phthalate, mono (2-ethyl-5-carboxyphenyl) phthalate, mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, mono (2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate, and mono (2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate were significantly associated with an approximately twofold increase in the odds of an endometriosis diagnosis. Two phthalates were associated with endometriosis in the operative cohort when restricting to visualized and histologic endometriosis (monooctyl phthalate: OR 1.38; 95% CI 1.10-1.72) or when restricting comparison women to those with a postoperative diagnosis of a normal pelvis [mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; OR 1.35; 95% CI 1.03-1.78].	Den Hond E, Govarts E, Willems H, et al. First steps toward harmonized human biomonitoring in Europe: demonstration project to perform human biomonitoring on a European scale. <i>Env Health Perspect.</i> 2015;123:255-263.	FMUL		
dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE)	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	attributable cases and costs	Children	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	childhood overweight	OECD. Health at a Glance: Europe 2012. Overweight and obesity among children. Available at http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/9789264183095/en/02/02/index.html#item1/content/chapter/9789264183095_26m8_csp_051b7f1a7a00b4030ba503352088:1ba . Accessed August 25, 2014).		the pooled estimate for prenatal exposure was a change of 0.12 across the interquartile range (p,p'-DDE: 60-448 ng/g lipid)	FMUL			

DDE	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	attributable cases and costs	General population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	diabetes	Langenberg C, Sharp S, Forouhi NG, et al. Design and cohort description of the InterAct Project: an examination of the interaction of genetic and lifestyle factors on the incidence of type 2 diabetes in the EPIC Study. <i>Diabetologia</i> . 2011;54:2272-2282.	Human	low (epidemiological evidence); moderate (experimental/toxicological data)	the pooled ORs of diabetes for high versus low concentrations were 1.25 (95% CI: 0.94, 1.66; I ² = 36.8%, heterogeneity = 0.16) for DDE					FMUL	
phthalate	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	attributable cases and costs	General population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	obesity	Finucane MM, Stevens GA, Cowan M, et al. National, regional, and global trends in body mass index since 1980: systematic analysis of health examination surveys and epidemiological studies with 960 country-years and 9.1 million participants. <i>Lancet</i> . 2011;377:557-567.	Human	low (epidemiological evidence); strong (experimental/toxicological data)	weight change rate: Q2-Q9 (-0.07 to 0.24); Q3-Q1 (0.06 to 0.37); Q4: 0.17 (0.02 to 0.33); p<0.05					FMUL	
phthalate	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	attributable cases and costs	General population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	diabetes	Langenberg C, Sharp S, Forouhi NG, et al. Design and cohort description of the InterAct Project: an examination of the interaction of genetic and lifestyle factors on the incidence of type 2 diabetes in the EPIC Study. <i>Diabetologia</i> . 2011;54:2272-2282.	Human	low (epidemiological evidence); strong (experimental/toxicological data)	OR comparing extreme quartiles = 2.14; 95% CI: 1.19, 3.85; OR = 0.87; 95% CI: 0.49, 1.53; trend = 0.29					FMUL	
BPA	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	Legler et al. 2015. doi: 10.1210/jc.2014-4326	attributable cases and costs	General population	European Union	Year	Continent	Background	obesity	Valko D, Casas M, Mendez MA, et al. Prenatal bisphenol A urine concentrations and early rapid growth and overweight risk in the offspring. <i>Epidemiology</i> . 2013;24:791-799.	Human	low to very low (epidemiologic evidence); strong (toxicological data)	β = 0.28 [-0.06 to 0.63]					FMUL	
PBDE	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	All neonates	Canada	Year	Country	Background	intellectual quotient (IQ) point loss	Chen, Amin, Tolton, K.; Rauch, S.; Webster, G.; Horning, R.; Sjödin, A.; Dietrich, K.; Lanphear, B. Prenatal Polybrominated Diphenyl Ether Exposures and Neurodevelopment in U.S. Children through 5 Years of Age: The HOME Study. <i>Environ. Health Perspect</i> 2014, 122, 856-862. doi: 10.1289/ehp.1307562	Human		4.5 IQ points lost per log unit of PBDE					FMUL	
PBDE	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	All neonates	Canada	Year	Country	Background	intellectual disability										FMUL
organophosphate pesticides	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	All neonates	Canada	Year	Country	Background	IQ point loss				4.25 IQ point loss per 10-fold increase in prenatal OP exposure						FMUL
organophosphate pesticides	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	All neonates	Canada	Year	Country	Background	intellectual disability										FMUL
multiple exposures (OP and PBDE)	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	Children aged 12 years	Canada	Year	Country	Background	ADHD	Vasiladiis, H.-M.; Diallo, F.B.; Rochette L.; Smith M.; Langille, D.; Lin E.; Kieley, S.; Fombonne, E.; Thompson, A.H.; Renaud, J.; et al. Temporal Trends in the Prevalence and Incidence of Diagnosed ADHD in Children and Young Adults between 1999 and 2012 in Canada: A Data Linkage Study. <i>Can. J. Psychiatry Rev. Can. Psychiatr.</i> 2017, 62, 818-826. doi: 10.1177/0706743717144668.	Human		OP-OR (1.35) PBDE-47-OR of 1.80					FMUL	
phthalates	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	Children aged 9 years	Canada	Year	Country	Background	autism	prevalence of ASD among male (23.9 per 1000) and female (6 per 1000) Canadian children Ofner, M.; Coles, A. and Decou, M. L. Autism Spectrum Disorder Among Children and Youth in Canada 2018: a Report of the National Autism Spectrum Disorder Surveillance System. 2018. Accessed: 03 July, 2020. [Online]. Available: http://www.deslibris.ca/ID/1006072	Human								FMUL
DDE	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	Children aged 10 years	Canada	Year	Country	Background	childhood obesity	prevalence of 19.5% for overweight status among 6-17 year-old Canadian children in 2007-2009 Rao, D. P.; Kropac, E.; Do, M. T.; Roberts, K. C. and Jayaraman, G. C. Childhood overweight and obesity trends in Canada. <i>Health Promot. Chronic Dis. Prev. Can. Res. Policy Pract.</i> 2016, 36, 194-198.	Human		0.12 increment in the weight-for-age Z-score across the interquartile range						FMUL
DDE	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	Adults aged 40-59 years	Canada	Year	Country	Background	adult diabetes	5.6 per 1,000 in 2008-2009 Public Health Agency of Canada. Diabetes in Canada: facts and figures from a public health perspective. Ottawa, Ont.: Public Health Agency of Canada, 2012. Accessed: 03 April, 2020. [Online]. Available: http://ra.ohci.ca/ra/login.aspx?req=contentmailurl=https://www.deslibris.ca/ID/232351	Human		OR (1.25; 95% CI: 0.94, 1.66)					FMUL	
DEHP	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Mallits et al. 2022. doi: 10.3390/toxics10030146	Attributable disease burden and cost	Women aged 40-59 years		Year	Country	Background	adult obesity	Morin, S.; Tsang, J. F. and Leslie, W. D. Weight and body mass index predict bone mineral density and fractures in women aged 40 to 59 years. <i>Osteoporos. Int. J. Estab. Result Coop. Eur. Found. Osteoporos. Natl. Osteoporos. Found. USA</i> , 2009, 20, 363-370. doi: 10.1007/s00198-008-0688-x.	Human								FMUL

Here we can add detailed information on exposure
Please adapt columns by your preference

Chemical group	Substance	Availability EU external exposure data (source/route, reference)	Source/route external exposure	Availability EU internal exposure data (reference)	Region	Year	Study population	Number of participants	Information on socioeconomic status	Exposure level (background, elevated, high eg. hotspot, occupational)	Remarks	Info added by partner(s):
PFAS				https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Teenagers		Yes	Background		VITO
PFAS	Blood: plasma: Per-/poly-fluorinated compounds (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFOS, PFHxA, PFHxO, PFBS, PFHpA, PFDA, PFUDA, PFDoDA, PFPeA, PFHpS)			SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ and https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ind-ex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia		2018 General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15		Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/sites/PARC6_2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B87707189-8C15-4817-ACFF-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
PFAS	Blood: Per-/poly-fluorinated compounds (PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFHxS, PFOS)				Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (newborns, teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	284 newborns, 283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
PFAS	Serum: PFOS, PFOA				Norway		Pregnant women	41		Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21334069/	NIPH
PFAS	Serum, plasma, whole blood: PFAS; PFOA and 23 additional PFAS				Norway		Adults	61		Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29056041/	NIPH
PFAS	Plasma: PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS				Norway	1999-2008	Pregnant women	2201		Background	Selection of data is included in HBM4EU. Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34293314/	NIPH
PFAS	Plasma (in children) and plasma/serum/while blood) in pregnant women: PFOS, PFHxS, PFOA, PFUnDA, PFNA.				Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2013-2016	Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children (6-7y earlier for maternal)	1301		Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	NIPH
Bisphenols				https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Adults		Yes	Background		VITO
Bisphenols	Urine: Bisphenols: bisphenol F, bisphenol A, bisphenol S			SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)		Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	Information on part of Slovenian HMB data is available on: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#showmetadata/SLOHBM , and https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/	NIJZ
Bisphenols	Urine: Bisphenols: bisphenol F, bisphenol A, bisphenol S			SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ and https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ind-ex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15		Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/sites/PARC6_2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B87707189-8C15-4817-ACFF-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
Bisphenols	Urine: Bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPP, BPZ, BPF)				Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results published here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Bisphenols	Urine: Bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPP, BPZ, BPF)				Wallonia (Belgium)	2020-2021	General population (children 3-5y, 6-11y)	602 children	Yes	Background	Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Bisphenols	Phenols in urine; MEPA, ETPA, PRPA, BUPA, BPA, OXBE, Triclosan. In children: pool of night and morning urine, and in pregnant women; 1 spot sample in trimester 1, 2 or 3.				Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2013-2016	Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children	1301		Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	NIPH
Flame retardants				https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Children		Yes	Background		VITO
	morning urine, and in pregnant women; 1 spot sample in trimester 1, 2 or 3.											

2. Exposure data: additional information

Flame retardants	Blood: PBDEs, HBCDs, antiDP, synDP, DBDPE, BCFP, DPHP, BDCIPP, BCIPP	SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) NIJZ available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenases.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACEF-57555680330F%7D&file=HMB_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	
Flame retardants	Blood: only in pooled samples (BDE-28, BDE-47, BDE-99, BDE-100, BDE-153, BDE-154, BDE-183, Sum PBDE)	SLO HBM1 https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOHBM	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) NIJZ available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenases.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACEF-57555680330F%7D&file=HMB_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	
Flame retardants	Blood: PBDE-28,-47,-99,-100,-153,-154,-183,-20		Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/
Flame retardants	Serum: 43 emerging and legacy halogenated flame retardants, including BDE-47, -153, -197, -209, -49, -85, -99, -100, -154, -206, -207, -208 as well as HBB, syn- and anti-DDC-CO, OBTPMI, DBDPE, α -HBCDD and TBBPA		Norway	2013-2014	Adults	61	Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31539819/	
Flame retardants	Urine and serum: FR metabolites DNBP, BDCIPP, DPHP, BCIPHIIPP, BBOHEEP, 5-HO-EHDPHP, TBOEP-OH, 3-HO-TPHP, 4-HO-TPHP, BBOEP.		Norway	2013-2014	Adults	61	Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30978481/	
Flame retardants	Urine: FR metabolites DNBP, DPHP, BDCIPP and BBOEP.		Norway	2004-2008	Pregnant women	809	Background	Results published in: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36455478/	
Flame retardants	Plasma in children and plasma/serum in pregnant women; PBDE 47, PBDE 153		Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2013-2016	Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children (6-7y earlier for maternal)	1301	Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	
Phthalates		https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Children & teenagers		Background	VITO	
Phthalates	Urine: Phthalates: Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxo-hexyl) phthalate; 7-Carboxy-(mono-methyl- heptyl) phthalate, Mono-carboxy-isononyl phthalate, Mono-4-methyl-7-carboxyheptyl phthalate, Mono-benzyl phthalate, Mono-cyclo-hexyl phthalate; Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxy-pentyl) phthalate; Mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; Mono-ethyl phthalate; Mono-isobutyl phthalate; Mono-n-butyl phthalate; Mono-n-octyl phthalate; Mono-n-pentyl phthalate / monopentyl phthalate; Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy- hexyl) phthalate; 6-OH-Mono-propyl heptyl phthalate; cyclohexane-1, 2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7- hydroxy-4- methyl)octyl ester; cyclohexane-1, 2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-oxo- 4-methyl)octyl ester; 7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate, Mono-hydroxy-iso-nonyl phthalate	SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	
Phthalates	Urine: Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, Butyl benzyl phthalate, Di-n-butyl phthalate, Di-isobutyl phthalate, Diethyl phthalate, Di-isononyl phthalate, Di-isononyl phthalate, Di-isodecyl phthalate (all C10 phthalates including DPHP), Di-isodecyl phthalate (all C10 phthalates including DPHP), Di-n-octyl phthalate, Di-n-pentyl phthalate / dipentyl phthalate, Dicyclohexyl phthalate aaa	SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ and https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) NIJZ available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenases.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACEF-57555680330F%7D&file=HMB_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	

2. Exposure data: additional information

Phthalates	Urine: DINCH and PE metabolites MMP, MEP, MIBP, MnBP, MBzP, MPHP, MEHP, 5-OH-MEHP, 5-oxo- MEHP, OH-MINCH and cx-MINCH									Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27466754/	NIPH
Phthalates	Urine: PE metabolites MEP, MIBP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOPH, MECCP, MMCHP, oh-MINP, oxo-MiNP and cx-MiNP	Norway	2013-2014	Adults		61		Background			
Phthalates	Phthalate metabolites in urine; MEP, MIBP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOPH, MECCP, oh-MiNP, oxo-MiNP. In children; pool of night and morning urine, and in pregnant women; 1 spot sample in trimester 1, 2 or 3.	Norway, Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2004-2008 2013-2016	Pregnant women Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children (6- 7y earlier for maternal)		850 1301		Background		Results published in: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29790729/ Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	NIPH NIPH
Pesticides		https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Children & adults General non-clinical population, rural, age 7- 10 and 12-15		Yes Yes	Background Background		See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	VITO NIJZ
Pesticides	Urine:Pyrethroid (3-PBA, 4-F-3-PBA), organophosphate (IMPP, DEAMP, PNP, MDA, CMHC, TCP), Glyphosate, AMPA, Chlorpyrifos-methyl	SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/index.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7- 10 and 12-15		Yes Yes	Background Background		See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	VITO NIJZ
Pesticides	Urine:Organochlorides (PP_DDT, OP_DDT, OP_DDE, PP_DDD, HCB, aldrin, endrin, dieldrin, HCHs, heptachlor, chlordane, cis- HCE, trans-HCE)	SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)		Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, professional, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	Information on part of Slovenian HMB data is available on: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/howmetadata/SLOHBM , and https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/	NIJZ	
Pesticides	Blood (all): 16 OC Urine (only teenagers + adults): 5 PYR, 6 OP, Glyphosate (+AMPA)		Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (newborns, teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	284 newborns, 283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background		Results published here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Pesticides	Urine: 5 PYR, 6 OP, Glyphosate (+AMPA)		Wallonia (Belgium)	2020-2021	General population (children 3-5y, 6-11y)	602 children	Yes	Background		Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Pesticides	Urine dialkylphosphate (DAP) metabolites: total diethylphosphate [ΣDEP] and total dimethylphosphate [ΣDMP]		Norway	2004-2008	Pregnant women		806	Background		Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35805806/	NIPH
Pesticides	OP pesticide metabolites in urine; DMP, DMTP, DMDTP, DEP, DETP, DEDTP. In children; pool of night and morning urine, and in pregnant women; 1 spot sample in trimester 1, 2 or 3.		Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2013-2016	Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children (6- 7y earlier for maternal)		1301	Background Background		Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	NIPH
Metals/metalloids	Lead and cadmium	Kirinčič, S., Šömen Joksić, A., Zupan, M., Ivanoš, J., Rep, P., Rotter, E., . . . Grčman, H. (2019). Lead and cadmium in foods/drinking water from Slovenian market/taps: Estimation of overall chronic dietary exposure and health risks. Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A, 36(10), 1522-1537. https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2019.1628355	Slovenia	2019	General population and different age groups		No	Background		NIJZ	

2. Exposure data: additional information

Metals/metalloids	Lead	Kirinčič, S., Ivartnik, M., Grčman, H., Zupan, M., Šömen Joksić, A., Golja, V. Exposure of inhabitants of Zgornja Mežiška dolina to toxic metals (Pb, Cd, Zn) in locally grown vegetables and soil. In: Kaučič, V. (ur.). <i>Zbornik referatov in povzetkov. Slovenski kemijski dnevi 2017, 20.-22. september 2017, Portorož. Ljubljana: Slovensko kemijsko društvo, 2017. Str. [1-7]. ISBN 978-961-93849-3-0.</i>	Locally produced leaf and root vegetables	NIJZ internal electronic base: lead concentrations (μ Pb/L) in blood samples summarized in Environmental indicator in Slovenia (Slovenian Environment Agency): [ZD17] Levels of lead in children's blood in the Upper Meža Valley. http://kazalci.arso.gov.si/en/content/levels-lead-childrens-blood-upper-meza-valley-2	Upper Meža valley (degraded area due to mining and melting of lead ore in the past)	metals concentration 2004 - 2016; Pb in blood: 2004 - 2022	Children from 2 to 4 years	Yes (parents' employment, living conditions, eating and living habits)	Hotspot	NIJZ		
Metals/metalloids	Cadmium			https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Adults	Yes	Background	VITO		
Metals/metalloids	Arsenic			https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/			Teenagers	Yes	Background	VITO		
Metals/metalloids	Blood (Mn, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Pb, Hg); Urine (Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Pb, Hg); Mothers milk (Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Pb, Hg); Hair (Hg)			SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	Information on part of Slovenian HMB data is available on: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/howmetadata/SLOHBM , and https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/	NIJZ	
Metals/metalloids	Blood (Mn, Fe, Co, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Hg, Pb, Rb, Sr, Sb, Cs, Tl); Plasma: Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Hg, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Rb, Sr, Mo, Sn, Sb, Ba, Ti, U); Urine 1 (Al, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Rb, Sr, Mo, Sn, Sb, Cs, Ba, Ti, U); Urine 2 (Al, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Rb, Sr, Mo, Sn, Sb, Cs, Ba, Ti, U) Hair (Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Hg, Pb, Al, V, Cr, info, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, info, Sb, Ba)			SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ , and https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/indext.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	Data collection 2018	Children (7-15)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, house characteristics; parents status, diseases, medicines and other food supplements consumption; chemicals in life; food and water consumption; proximity to industry, use of fire; use of metals; proximity to infrastructure, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, use of computer, TV, hobbies ...)		See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6_2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B8B77D7189-8C15-4817-ACEF-57555680330F%7D&file=HMB_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&1&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ	
Metals/metalloids	Blood & urine: Pb, Cd, As(spec), Zn, Mo, Cu				Wallonia (Belgium)	2018	General population (children + adults)	5 children, 88 adults	Yes	Hotspot	1st samples. Results published here: https://www.issep.be/sanisol/ https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S026974912012428	ISSEP
Metals/metalloids	Blood & urine: Pb, Cd, As(spec), Zn, Mo, Cu				Wallonia (Belgium)	2019	General population (children + adults)	5 children, 55 adults	Yes	Hotspot	2nd samples. Results published here: https://www.issep.be/sanisol/	ISSEP
Metals/metalloids	Blood & urine: Pb, Cd, As(spec), Zn, Mo, Cu				Wallonia (Belgium)	2019	General population (adults)	88 adults	Yes	Background	Control samples. Same zone but outside of hotspot. Results published here: https://www.issep.be/sanisol/	ISSEP
Metals/metalloids	Blood (all): Cd, Hg, Pb; Urine (only teenagers + adults): Cd, Hg, Pb, As(tot), Cr, Cu, Se, Zn; Urine (only teenagers): As(spec), Ni, Ti				Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (newborns, teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	284 newborns, 283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results published here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Metals/metalloids	Urine: Cd, Hg, Pb, As(tot), Cr, Cu, Se, Zn, Ni, Ti				Wallonia (Belgium)	2020-2021	General population (children 3-5y, 6-11y)	602 children	Yes	Background	Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
Metals	Methylmercury	WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/Search.aspx?Region=EURO	Methylmercury concentration in foodstuff	NA	European Union	2018	NA	NA	NA	NA	Concentration of Methylmercury in fish & seafood. Needs to be combined with food consumption data to measure dietary exposure. Only partial data Data available for other regions	Sciensano

2. Exposure data: additional information

Metals	Lead	WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/Search.aspx	Lead concentration in foodstuff	NA	European Union	From 1995 to 2017	NA	NA	NA	NA	Needs to be combined with food consumption data to measure dietary exposure. From 1995 to 1999 only few data mainly for fish, seafood & few vegetables. Data available for other regions 345 results from 1997-2000 124508 results in total Data available for other regions	Sciensano	
Metals	Cadmium	WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/Search.aspx?Region=EURO	Cadmium concentration in foodstuff	NA	European Union	1997-2019	NA	NA	NA	NA	Data available for other regions 345 results from 1997-2000 124508 results in total Data available for other regions	Sciensano	
Metals	Arsenic	WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/Search.aspx?Region=EURO	Arsenic concentration in foodstuff	NA		from 2000-2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	131317 results in total Data available for other regions	Sciensano	
Metals	Arsenic	EFSA, "Chronic dietary exposure to inorganic arsenic," EFSA J., vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 1–50, 2021, doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6380	Arsenic concentration in foodstuff		European Union	2013 - 2018					13,608 results on iAs (7,623 corresponding to drinking water and 5,985 to different types of food)	AUTH	
Metals	Blood: cadmium; cesium; cobalt; copper; lead; magnesium; manganese; selenium; zinc; total arsenic; and total mercury				Norway	1999-2008	Pregnant women			2201	Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33765546/	NIPH
Metals	Whole blood in children, whole blood or cord whole blood in pregnant women: arsenic cadmium; cesium; cobalt; copper; mercury; lead; magnesium; manganese; molybdenum, potassium, sodium, thallium, zinc;				Norway, UK, Spain, France, Lithuania, Greece	2013-2016	Pregnant women and their children (at 6y) from children (6-7y earlier for maternal)			1301	Background	Results published here: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30326459/	NIPH
Mycotoxins							Adults		Yes		Background	VITO	
Mycotoxins	afatoxins (AF), ochratoxin A (OTA), fumonisins B1 and B2 (FB), deoxynivalenol (DON), zearalenone (ZON) and T-2/HT-2 toxins	Kirincic, S., Skrljanc, B., Kos, N., Kozolc, B., Pirnat, N., & Tavcar-Kalcher, G. (2015). Mycotoxins in cereals and cereal products in Slovenia - Official control of Foods in the years 2008-2012. Food Control, 50, 157-165. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.08.034	Cereals and cereal products from Slovenian market		Slovenian market	Data collection 2008-2012					Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	Exposure hasn't been assessed yet but concentration data in food exist consumption data to measure dietary exposure. Around 456000 results in total Data available for other regions	NIJZ
Mycotoxins	Aflatoxine	WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/Search.aspx?Region=EURO	Aflatoxin concentration in foodstuff	NA	European Union	from 2000 to 2020	NA	NA	NA	NA		Sciensano	
Mycotoxins	Aflatoxin	Global Burden of Aflatoxin-Induced Hepatocellular Carcinoma: A Risk Assessment https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0901388	Maize and nuts		WHO region		general population (Children & adults)		~ data per country : for developed & developing countries			Biomarkers (internal exposure): Aflatoxin-N7-guanine in urine or Aflatoxin-albumin adducts in serum	Sciensano
EDC	Urine: PAHs: 1+9-OH-Phenanthrene, 1-OH-Pyrene, 2+3-OH-Fluorene, 2-OH-Naphthalene, 2-OH-Phenanthrene, 3-OH-Phenanthrene, 4-OH-Phenanthrene			SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)		Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	Information on part of Slovenian HMB data is available on: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/howmetadata/SLOHBM and https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/	NIJZ	
EDC	Urine: PAHs: 1+9-OH-Phenanthrene, 1-OH-Pyrene, 2+3-OH-Fluorene, 2-OH-Naphthalene, 2-OH-Phenanthrene, 3-OH-Phenanthrene, 4-OH-Phenanthrene			SLO CRP Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	Data collection 2018	Children (7-15)		Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, house characteristics; parents status, diseases, medicines and other food supplements consumption; chemicals in life; food and water consumption; proximity to industry, use of fire; use of metals; proximity to infrastructure, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, use of computer, TV, hobbies ...)		See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencianses.sharepoint.com/x/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACEF-57555680330F%7D&file=HMB_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ	

2. Exposure data: additional information

EDC	Urine: PAHs (1- et 2- naphthols, 2-, 3 et 9-hydroxyfluorenes, 1-, 2-, 3- et 4-hydroxyphenanthrenes, 1-hydroxypyrene)	Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results published here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
EDC	Urine: PAHs (1- et 2- naphthols, 2-, 3 et 9-hydroxyfluorenes, 1-, 2-, 3- et 4-hydroxyphenanthrenes, 1-hydroxypyrene)	Wallonia (Belgium)	2020-2021	General population (children 3-5y, 6-11y)	602 children	Yes	Background	Results will be published in March 2023 here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
EDC	Urine: DINCH (MINCH)	SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
EDC	Urine: DINCH (MINCH)	SLO HBM 1: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOHBM , and https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
EDC	Urine: Parabens : methylparaben, ethylparaben, iso-propylparaben, propylparaben, iso-butylparaben, butylparaben, benzylparaben	SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	NIJZ	
EDC	Urine: Triclosan	SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) Availability EU internal exposure data: See Remarks	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (age 18-49)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	NIJZ	
EDC	Blood: PCB118, PCB28, PCB52, PCB138, PCB153, PCB180	SLO HBM1 https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOHBM	Slovenia (national)	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
EDC	Blood: PCB118, PCB28, PCB52, PCB138, PCB153, PCB180	SLO CRP (HBM4EU Aligned study) https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ndex.html#showmetadata/SLOCRP	Prekmurje region in Slovenia	2018	General non-clinical population, rural, age 7-10 and 12-15	Yes	Background	See also table (HMB data subsets) available on PARC 6.2.3 Sharepoint filled with JSI partner https://agencenses.sharepoint.com/x:/r/sites/PARC6.2/Projects/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B877D7189-8C15-4817-ACFE-57555680330F%7D&file=HBM_data_subsets_focus.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	NIJZ
EDC	Blood (all): PCB118, PCB138, PCB153, PCB180 Blood (only teenagers): PCB28, PCB52, PCB101	Wallonia (Belgium)	2019-2020	General population (newborns, teenagers 12-19y, adults 20-39y)	284 newborns, 283 teenagers, 261 adults	Yes	Background	Results published here: https://www.issep.be/bmh-wal/	ISSEP
EDC		WHO Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS) https://extranet.who.int/gemsford/Search.aspx?Region=EURO	Dioxin & Dioxin like concentration NA	European Union	From 2000-2 NA	NA	NA	72947 results in total Needs to be combined with food consumption data to measure dietary exposure.	Sciensano
Mixtures	Dioxin & Dioxin like								

2. Exposure data: additional information

Mixtures	Bisphenols, phtalates, metals/mettaloids, PAHs, DINCH, flame retardants, parabens, triclosan, PCBs	SLO HBM 1 Reference: NIJZ (internal source) - see NIJZ HBM individual chemicals above (data for all these chemicals are provided for one person, so they can be considered as mixtures).	Slovenia (national) Prekmurje region in Slovenia	Data collection 2008-2014	General population (men and lactating women, age 18-49)	Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, education, profession, employment, working hours, occupational exposure, work with chemicals, proximity to industry, proximity to infrastructure, food consumption, medication consumption, health, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, pregnancy and child care) Yes (gender, age, weight, height, place of residence, housing unit, house characteristics; parents status, diseases, medicines and other food supplements consumption; chemicals in life; food and water consumption; proximity to industry, use of fire; use of metals; proximity to infrastructure, diseases, smoking, hobbies, working at the computer, new products, use of computer, TV, hobbies ...)	Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	See NIJZ HBM individual chemicals above (data for all these chemicals are provided for one person, so they can be considered as mixtures).	NIJZ
Mixtures	Bisphenols, PFAS, phtalates, pesticides, metals/mettaloids, PAHs, DINCH, flame retardants, PCBs	SLO CRP Reference: NIJZ (internal source) - see NIJZ HBM individual chemicals above (data for all these chemicals are provided for one person, so they can be considered as mixtures).		Data collection 2018	Children (7-15)		Background values could be established, and spatial differences in exposure could be assessed including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites?	See NIJZ HBM individual chemicals above (data for all these chemicals are provided for one person, so they can be considered as mixtures).	NIJZ

2. Exposure data: additional information

Here we can add information on additional ERFs.
 There are also a lot of ERFs for which no health impact calculation was performed yet.
 Please adapt columns by your preference

Chemical group	Substance	Health effect/Endpoint	Reference exposure-response function (ERF)	ERF specifications (Human, in vivo, in vitro)	ERF certainty (low, medium, high)	Exposure range	Quantitative ERF estimate	Year	Country (in case of human)	Study population in case of human (age)	Information on socio-economic status (yes/no)	Dynamic ERF or ERF depending on extra variables	LNK	Comments (type of study)
PFAS	PFOA	Hypertension	Min et al. 2012	human									https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3426376/	Cross sectional study (N= 2934 adults)
PFAS	PFOA	Low birth weight	Johnson et al. 2014	human									https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4181929/	Systematic review
PFAS	PFOA	Small for gestational age	Govarts et al. 2018	human									https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160401201731935?via=ihub	Pooled analysis
PFAS	PFOA	Hospitalisation LRTI	Dakager et al. 2021	human									https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160401202100092?via=ihub	Longitudinal study (prenatal exposure; N = 1503; hospitalization first 4y of life)
Bisphenols	Bisphenol A	Obesity	Valvi et al. (2013)	human				2004-2006	Spain	Children			https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1938543/	From ATHLETE's plausibility database
Bisphenols	Bisphenol A	Obesity	Miyawaki et al. (2007)	in vivo										
Bisphenols	Bisphenol S, F	Obesity	Liu et al. (2019); Jacobson et al. (2019)	human					USA (NHANES)	Adolescents			https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6338787/	Cross sectional study (N= 745 children and adolescents)
Bisphenols	Bisphenol S, F	Obesity	Liu et al. (2019); Jacobson et al. (2019)	human					USA (NHANES)	Adolescents			https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6735733/	Cross sectional study (N= 1831 children and adolescents)
Flame retardants	BDE-47	IQ	Herbstman et al. (2010); Eskenazi et al. (2013); Lam et al. 2017	human						Children			Lam, https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.119.13	Systematic review and meta analysis
Flame retardants	BDE-47	ADHD	Gaouan et al. (2011); Eskenazi et al. (2013)	human						Children			Gaouan-https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2010.12.005	Longitudinal/cross-sectional study (N=470 mother child pairs; cord blood analysis N = 88, serum analysis at 4y N= 244, health outcome measured at 4y)
Flame retardants	BDE-47	Cryptorchidism	Main et al. 2007	human						New-borns				
Flame retardants	BDE-47	Testicular cancer	Handberg et al. 2006	human						Adults				
Flame retardants	Organophosphate flame retardants	Allergies	Azaki et al. 2018	human						Children			https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3041263/	Cross sectional study (N=128)
Phthalates														
?	?	Allergic diseases		human, mice and in vitro						Children and adults	no		https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3237130/	Review of epidemiological (n = 43), animal (n = 49), and cell culture studies (n = 42), published until the end of 2019, on phthalates and allergic diseases, such as asthma, rhinoconjunctivitis, and eczema. For experimental studies only studies using concentrations with relevance for human exposure were included
Pesticides	Chlorpyrifos (CPF)	Working memory, IQ	Rauh et al. (2011)	human		Cord blood CPF (pg/g), mean (sd) (range) : 3.17 ± 4.61 (0.09–32)	log of Working Memory Index = -0.006 (95% CI = -0.01, -0.002) concentration of CPF in cord blood. 1.4% reduction in Full-Scale IQ and 2.3% reduction in Working Memory for each standard deviation increase in exposure (4.61 pg/g).			265 of the CCCCE cohort participants at age 7 years			https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21507777/	From ATHLETE's plausibility database, longitudinal study (N=265; prenatal exposure, neurodevelopment at 7y)
Pesticides	Organophosphates	ADHD	Bouchard et al. (2011)											
Pesticides	Organophosphates	ADHD	Bouchard et al. (2010)											
Pesticides	Pyrethroids	ADHD	Dakager et al. (2019)											
Pesticides	Organophosphates	Respiratory symptoms	Raanan et al. (2015)	Human			Total DAPs and DEAP metabolites in urine from the second half of pregnancy were significantly associated with increased odds of respiratory symptoms in children (adjusted OR (aOR) for a 10 fold increase in concentration is 1.77; 95%CI: 1.06, 2.95, p = 0.03; aOR = 1.61; 95% CI: 1.08, 2.39, p = 0.02, respectively). For a 10 fold increase in total DAPs concentration the OR is 2.53 (1.32, 4.86, p < 0.005) for respiratory symptoms, and the aOR is 5.40 (2.10, 13.91, p < 0.001) for exercise-induced coughing.			Pregnant women and children (CHAMACOS)			Raanan R, Harley KG, Balmes JR, Bradman A, Lipssett M, and Eskenazi B. (2015) Early-life Exposure to Organophosphate Pesticides and Pediatric Respiratory Symptoms in the CHAMACOS Cohort. ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH PERSPECTIVES: 123(2), 179-185	
Pesticides	permethrin and piperonyl butoxide (PBO)	Mental development index (MDI)	Horton et al. (2011)	Human			Significant inverse association between prenatal PBO exposure and 36 month MDI. MDI scores reduced 1.2 points per log unit increase in PBO exposure (95% confidence interval (CI) -0.33 to -2.25; p = 0.008). The strongest adverse effect of PBO was at the highest quartile group when compared to the referent group (Odds ratio: 4.57; 95% CI: -0.3 to -8.34; p = 0.04). Children highly exposed to piperonyl butoxide in personal air samples (>4.34 ng/m ³) scored 3.9 points lower on the MDI than those with lower exposures (95% CI: -0.25 to -7.49; p = 0.04). For each log unit increase in PBO exposure, there was 1.3 fold increased odds of delayed mental development (95% CI: 1.06 - 1.66; p = 0.01).		USA (CCCCE study)				Horton MK, Rundle A, Camano DE, Barr DB, Raah VA, Whittam RM. (2011). Impact of Prenatal Exposure to Piperonyl Butoxide and Permethrin on 36-Month Neurodevelopment. Pediatrics: 127(3), e699-706.	
Metals	Cadmium	Birth weight and low birth weight	Huang et al. (2019) (doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2019.05.039) -meta-analysis	Human			50% increase of maternal urine Cd (UCd) = 6.15 g (95% CI:10.81,1.49) decrease in neonatal birth weight. Statistically significant in girls only (8.92 g, 95%CI:17.51,0.34) and first trimester (11.34 g, 95% CI:19.54,1.14). 50% increase of maternal blood Cd (BCd) = 11.57 g (95% CI:18.85,4.30) decrease in neonatal birth weight. Increased UCd levels were associated with a higher rate of low birth weight (LBW) risk (ORs = 1.12, 95% CI: 1.03,1.22).			Newborn (prenatal exposure)				From ATHLETE's plausibility database
Metals	Cadmium	Osteoporosis	Engström et al. 2011 & 2012	human									https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21507777/	
Metals	Lead	Blood pressure	Gemp et al. (2005) (cited in ATSDR 2019) (doi: 10.1016/j.mt.2005.04.002)	Human		Cord PbB mean: 2.97 µg/dL	SBP: β (SE), mmHg log µg/dL: 12.16 (4.96) p=0.016* DBP: β (SE), mmHg per log µg/dL: 8.45 (4.54) p=0.066			122 children, 9 years old				From ATHLETE's plausibility database
Metals	Lead	Blood pressure	Zhang et al. (2011) (cited in ATSDR 2019) (doi: 10.1289/ehp.1103736)	Human		Mean umbilical cord: 5.55 µg/dL Mean child concurrent: 2.96 µg/dL Median maternal postnatal tibia Pb (µg/g): 9.3 µg/dL	SPB: Maternal tibia Pb, girls, β mmHg increased per maternal tibia Pb (13 µg/g): 2.11 (0.69, 3.52) (p=0.025) DBP: Maternal tibia Pb, girls, β mmHg increased per maternal tibia Pb (13 µg/g): 1.60 (0.28, 2.91) (p=0.007*) Not significant in boys	1994-2013 (recruitment), 2008-2010 (follow-up)	Mexico	n=457 mother-child pairs, 7-15 years old				From ATHLETE's plausibility database

3. Exposure-effect functions

Metals	Lead	IQ, FSIQ	Lanphear et al. (2005) (cited in ATSDR 2019) - pooled analysis	Human	Mean (95% CI): • Lifetime average: 12.4 (4.1, 34.8) µg/dL • Peak: 18.0 (6.2, 47.0) µg/dL • Concurrent with FSIQ: 9.7 (2.5, 33.2) µg/dL	β in IQ for each in PbB (µg/dL) increase in PbB: • 6-24 months: -2.04 (-3.27, -0.81)* • Lifetime average: -3.04 (-4.33, -1.75) • Peak: -2.85 (-4.10, -1.60)* • Concurrent: -2.70 (-3.74, -1.66)* FSIQ change for lifetime average PbB: • 2.4-10 µg/dL: -3.9 points (-2.4, -5.3)* • 10-20 µg/dL: -1.9 points (-1.2, -2.6)* • 20-30 µg/dL: -1.1 (-0.7, -1.5)*			n=1,333 children (4.8-6 years of age) from seven prospective studies	https://ehp.niehs.nih.gov/doi/10.1289/ehp.7988	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. The biological significance of the observed supra linear response has been the subject of several reviews and commentaries (Bowers and Beck 2006; Hornung and Lanphear 2014; Jusko et al. 2006).	
Metals	Lead	IQ	US EPA (2014)	Human	Mean (95% CI): • Lifetime average: 12.4 4.1, 34.8) • Peak: 18.0 (6.2, 47.0) • Concurrent with FSIQ: 9.7 (2.5, 33.2)	IQ decrement over different concurrent blood Pb ranges based on the log-linear model: • 2.4 to 30 µg/dL: 6.7 IQ pts (4.1-9.3) • 2.4 to 10 µg/dL: 3.8 IQ pts (2.3-5.3) • 10 to 20 µg/dL: 1.8 IQ pts (1.1-2.6) • 20 to 30 µg/dL: 1.1 IQ pts (0.7-1.5) β in IQ for each in PbB (µg/dL) increase in PbB (95% CI): • 6-24 months: -2.21 (-3.36, -1.04)* • Lifetime average: -3.14 (-4.39, -1.88)* • Peak: -2.86 (-4.10, -1.61)* • Concurrent: -2.65 (-3.69, -1.61)* FSIQ change for concurrent PbB range: • 2.4-10 µg/dL: -3.8 points (-2.3, -5.3)* • 10-20 µg/dL: -1.8 points (-1.1, -2.6)* • 20-30 µg/dL: -1.1 (-0.7, -1.5)*			n=1,333 children (4.8-6 years of age) from seven prospective studies	https://cfpub.epa.gov/ncra/1/1/recordisplay.cfm?id=255721	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. Re-analysis of pooled cohort from Lanphear et al. 2005 with corrections to the database.	
Metals	Lead	Allergic sensitization (positive SPT) (children)	Jedrychowski et al. (2013) - cited in US EPA (2014)	Human	a. Prenatal (cord) geometric mean: 1.16 (95% CI: 1.12, 1.22) µg/dL b. Concurrent geometric mean: 2.04 (95% CI: 1.95, 2.12) µg/dL	a. OR=2.3 (1.1, 4.6) b. OR=1.1 (0.7, 1.6)	Krakow, Poland	224 children followed prenatally to age 5		https://doi.org/10.1186/14752875-2-25	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. Prospective. Study of multiple exposures and outcomes. Clinical assessment of atopy. No information on follow-up participation but no selective attrition. Excluded subjects with cord blood level > 2.5 µg/dL. Logistic regression adjusted for sex, parity, maternal age, education, and atopy, cord blood cotinine, smoker in home during follow-up. Also considered potential confounding by breastfeeding and allergen levels in house dust.	
Metals	Lead	Incident asthma requiring medical care	Joseph et al. (2005) - cited in US EPA (2014)	Human	Measured up to 12 mo before outcome, mean (SD) Caucasian: 3.2 (2.5) µg/dL African American: 5.5 (4.3) µg/dL	OR: 2.7 (0.9, 8.1) (caucasian ≥5 µg/dL vs. caucasian <5 µg/dL)	Southeastern Michigan, USA	4,634 children, ages 4 mo-3 yr followed for 12 months		Blood Lead Level and Risk of Asthma: I Environmental Health Perspectives Vol. 113, No. 7 (nih.gov)	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. Cross-sectional. Recruitment from state blood Pb database (Levels ascertained from statewide database, specific timing unreported but varied among subjects). Moderate participation rate. Parental report of asthma diagnosis. Logistic regression adjusted for age, sex, family income, #stories in unit, cat in home, dog in home, cockroach problem, # persons in home, smoker in home, smoker in home, Pb level at address, candles or incense, months of residency, housing tenure, cooling stove type, main heating source, air conditioning type, peeling paint, ceiling/wall damage, housing age, water dampness/mildew/musty odor.	
Metals	Lead	Prevalent asthma diagnosed within previous 12 months (children)	Pugh Smith and Ntugu, 2011 - cited in US EPA 2014	Human	OR: 7.5 (1.3, 42.9) (children > 10 µg/dL vs. children <10 µg/dL)		Saginaw, Michigan, USA	356 children, ages 0-12 yr (74% age < 6 yr)	primarily low SES population of children in Michigan but adjusted for family annual income	Lead poisoning and asthma among low-income and African American children in Saginaw, Michigan - ScienceDirect	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. Cross-sectional. Recruitment from state blood Pb database (Levels ascertained from statewide database, specific timing unreported but varied among subjects). Moderate participation rate. Parental report of asthma diagnosis. Logistic regression adjusted for age, sex, family income, #stories in unit, cat in home, dog in home, cockroach problem, # persons in home, smoker in home, smoker in home, Pb level at address, candles or incense, months of residency, housing tenure, cooling stove type, main heating source, air conditioning type, peeling paint, ceiling/wall damage, housing age, water dampness/mildew/musty odor.	
Metals	Lead	Onset of puberty (girls and boys)	ATSDR (2019)	Human	Estimates and trends reported in Table 2-44 (page 217-220)					https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/hotspots/lead/fig.asp?fig=96&cid=2	From ATHLETE's plausibility database. No meta-analysis performed. But estimates and trends reported in Table 2-44 (page 217-220).	
Metals	Lead	Premature mortality	Lanphear et al. (2018)	Human			1988-1994	USA	>20y	https://www.thelancet.com/journal/S0140673616000002		
Metals	Arsenic (inorganic)	Carotid intima-media thickness (children)	Osorio-Yanze et al. (2013)	Human	The estimated strength of the effect was a 58 µm increase per µg As/L urine (95% CI: 19.8, 95) in subjects who had urinary arsenic levels >70 µg/L.		Mexico	199 children			From ATHLETE's plausibility database.	
Metals	Arsenic (inorganic)	Blood pressure (children)	Hawkesworth et al. 2013	Human		Systemic and diastolic blood pressure in the children increased in association with both maternal and child urinary arsenic levels. The estimated effect size was an increase of 3.69 mmHg systolic (95% CI: 0.74, 6.63) and 2.91 mmHg diastolic (95% CI: 0.41, 5.42) per mg/L increase in maternal urinary arsenic. In relation to child urinary arsenic levels, the effect size was 8.25 mmHg systolic (95% CI: 1.37, 15.1) and 2.75 mmHg diastolic (95% CI: -3.09, 8.59) per mg/L increase in urinary arsenic measured at age 18 months		Bangladesh	2,499 child-mother pairs		From ATHLETE's plausibility database. Areas with endemic contamination of well water.	
Mycotoxins	Aflatoxin	Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC)	Global Burden of Aflatoxin-Induced Hepatocellular Carcinoma: A Risk Assessment (doi:10.1289/ehp.0901388)	Human	0 to 227 (mg/kg body weight/4ay) depend on countries		2006	General population	~ stratification by country/rural/area	Hepatitis B virus	https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0901388	quantitative risk assessment & estimation of the BoD of HCC
EDC	Organochlorines, phthalates, etc.	Weight	Agay-Shay 2015	human			2004-2006	Spain	children	yes		
Mixtures	Phthalates, phosphate flame retardants & plasticizers (PFBS)	Wheeze & allergy (rhinoconjunctivitis)	Araki 2020	human			2008	Japan	children	no	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32058144/	
Mixtures	PFAS	Cardiometabolic outcomes	Batzella 2022	human			2018-2020	Italy Veneto region (High exposed)	adults	yes	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013935122005527?via=ihub	
Mixtures	Phthalates, parabens, phenols	Allergic and respiratory outcomes	Berger 2020	human			study start 1999-2000	US California (CHAMACOS study)	children	yes		
Mixtures	Phthalates, parabens, phenols	Obesity	Berger 2021	human			study start 1999-2001	US California (CHAMACOS study)	children	yes		
Mixtures	Organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs), phthalates, phenols separately	Size gestational age (small-SGA or large-LGA)	Bommarito 2021	human			study start 2006	US Boston (LIFECODES cohort)	children	yes		
Mixtures	Phthalates	Birth weight	Chiu 2018	human	not significant		2005-2016	US Boston (EARTH study)	newborn	yes		
Mixtures	POPs (PCB, DDE)	Thyroid	Dufour 2020	human			2015-2018	Belgium	adults	no	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013935119307194?via=ihub	
Mixtures	Metals, PAHs, tricosan	Nasal Colonization by Staphylococcus aureus	Eggers 2020	human			2001-2004	US NHANES	>6y	yes		
Mixtures	PFAS & stress	Fetal growth	Eick 2022	human				US Urbana-Champaign & San Francisco	newborn	yes		
Mixtures	PBT	Cancer	Fernandez-Martinez 2020	human				review paper				
Mixtures	Brominated flame retardants and PFAS	Breast cancer	Frenoy 2022	human			1994-2013	France E3N French cohort	women	yes		

3. Exposure-effect functions

Metals (e.g. Pb, Se)	Neurobehavioural outcomes	Fruh 2021	human				study start 1999-2002	US Massachusetts	children	yes		
Metals, phthalates, PFAS	Birth weight	Govarts 2016	human				2008-2009	Belgium	newborn	yes		
Metals, POPs	Birth weight	Govarts 2020	human				2002-2015	Belgium (FLEHSJ,UII,3XG)	newborn	yes		
Metals, pesticides, phenols (main effect Pb and BPA)	IQ	Guo 2020	human				2009-2010	China SMBCS	children	yes		
PFAS	Thyroid	Guo 2021	human				2009-2010	China SMBCS	children	yes		
Organochlorines, lead	Birth weight	Hu 2021	human				2008-2011	Canada	newborns, mothers	yes		
Phenols, phthalates, metals, organophosphate/pyrethroid/organochlorine pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls, polybrominated diphenyl ethers, perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), and environmental tobacco smoke	Birth outcomes	Kaloo 2020	human				2003-2006	US Cincinnati	newborn	yes		
Metals, phthalates, phenols, polybrominated diphenyl ethers, organophosphate and organochlorine pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls, perfluoroalkyl substances, and environmental tobacco smoke in blood or urine	Cognitive development	Kaloo 2021	human				2003-2006	USA HOME study	children	yes		
Metals, phthalates, phenols	Inflammatory changes, gestational age, birth weight	Kelly 2019	human				study start 2010	US Michigan	newborns, mothers	yes		
Bisphenols	Birth weight	Kim 2021	human				2017-2019	S. Korea	newborns, mothers	yes		
Polybrominated diphenyl ethers, organochlorine pesticides, metals, and perfluorinated alkyl substances	Fetal growth	Lazarevic 2022	human			not significant	2008-2011	Australia	newborns, mothers	yes		
PFAS	Thyroid	Lebaux 2020	human			Small or no effect	2003-2006	US Home study	newborns, mothers	yes		
Metals	Neurobehavioural outcomes	Levin-Schwartz 2019	human				2007-2011	Mexico	children	yes		
Bisphenols	Hemoglobin levels	Liang 2022	human				2018	China GZBC study	Pregnant women			
Metals and POPs	Heart rate variation	Liberda 2021	human					Canada	adults	no		
POPs	Gestational diabetes	Liu 2021	human				2013-2015	China	Pregnant women	no		
Metals	Preterm birth	Liu 2022	human				2011-2014	china	Pregnant women	yes		
PFAS, PCBs, organochlorine pesticides (OCPs)	Early menarche	Marks 2021	human			not significant	1991-1992	UK	girls	yes		
Phthalates	Allergies and oxidative stress	Mesfin Ketema 2022	human				2012-2017	Japan	children	yes		
Metals	Cognitive performance	Nasser 2022	human				2011-2014	US NHANES	elderly	yes	by sex	
Heavy metals, volatile organic compound metabolites, and phthalate metabolite	Dyslipidemia	Nguyen 2022	human					S Korea KoNEHS	adults	yes		
Heavy metals	Obesity	Nguyen Duc 2022	human				2009-2017	S Korea KMHANES	adults	yes		
POPs	Fetal growth	Oudir 2019	human				2009-2013	US	newborn	yes	by infant sex, race/ethnicity	
Hg, PCBs, PFAS	Neurotoxicity	Oulhote 2019	human				birth cohort started 1997-2000	Faroe Islands	children	yes		
PCBs	Breast cancer	Parada 2021	human				1993-1996	USA North Carolina	women	yes		
PFAS	Thyroid	Preston 2020	human				1999-2002	US Boston (Project Viva)	mothers and children	no		
Metals	Allergies and oxidative stress	Ruan 2022	human				2013-2016	China Wuhan	children	yes		
PFAS and metals	Kidney	Su 2022	human				2018-2019	China	adults	yes		
PFAS, Triclosan, phthalates, non-phthalate plasticizers, bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, pesticides and PCBs	Childhood weight trajectory	Svensson 2021	human				study start 2007-2010	Sweden (SELMA)	children	yes	by sex	

3. Exposure-effect functions

	EDCs (phenols, plasticizers, PFAS, persistent chlorinated molecules)	IQ	Tanner 2020	human				study start 2007-2010	Sweden (SELMA)	children	yes			
	Phthalates, bisphenols, organophosphates	IQ	van den Dries 2021a	human				study start 2002-2006	The Netherlands (Generation R study)	children	yes			
	Phthalates, bisphenols, organophosphates	Fetal growth	van den Dries 2021b	human				study start 2002-2007	The Netherlands (Generation R study)	children	yes			
	Metals	Neurotoxicity	von Stackelberg 2015	human					review paper					
	Mixture	Neurotoxicity	Vuong 2021	human					review paper					
	Metals	Obesity	Wang 2018	human			2003-2014		US NHANES	adults	yes			
	PFAS	mortality	Wen 2022	human			1999-2014		US NHANES	adults	yes			
	PFAS	Cognitive function	Weng 2022	human			2011-2014		US NHANES	elderly	yes			
	Phthalates, phenols, parabens, pesticides	Obesity	Wu 2020	human			2005-2010		US NHANES	children & adolescents	yes			
	Metals	Cardiovascular	Yin 2022	human					review paper					
	Phenols, pesticides, and phthalates	Obesity	Zhang 2019	human			2013-2014		US NHANES	adults	yes			
	Phenols and phthalates	Preterm birth	Zhang 2021a	human			2005-2019		US Massachusetts (EARTH study)	adults	yes			
	Metals, phthalates	Endometriosis, uterine leiomyomata	Zhang 2021b	human			2001-2006		US NHANES	women	yes			

Here you can add data on Health Outcomes for European populations (national or subnational)

Please edit column titles and add columns by your preference

Name of data source	Health outcome(s)	Measure (YLL, YLD, DALY, deaths, prevalence, incidence)	Type of data (modelled, registry)	Input data (if modelled)	Year(s)	Area (country, region, subnational)	LINK	Comments
WHO global health observatory, GBD	Multiple	DALY, YLD, YLL			2000-2019	at country level	https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mortality-and-global-health-estimates/global-health-estimates-leading-causes-of-dalys	
Belgian Cancer Registry	Cancer	Incidence	registry		2000/2004 onwards	Belgium	https://kankerregister.org/	Statistics by ICD 10 codes, gender, sex, age, year. Available years depend on regions. More precise data can be requested.
Belgian statistical office	Mortality and causes of death	Incidence	registry		1950/1992 onwards	Belgium	https://statbel.fgov.be/	Statistics by ICD 10 codes, day, age, gender, place of death. Available years depend on requested variables. More precise data can be requested.
Belgian Central Registry of Rare Diseases	Rare diseases	Incidence	registry			Belgium	https://rarediseases.sciensano.be/en/registry	Individual information, diagnosis by ICD-10-codes, ICD-O-codes, HPO-code, etc...
Minimum Clinical Data	Hospital discharge data				1990 onwards	Belgium		Clinical data (e.g. primary and secondary diagnosis) and demographic characteristics of patients
Minimum Hospital Data Set	Hospital data				2009 onwards	Belgium	https://fair.healthdata.be/dataset/12d69eca-4449-47d2-943d-e448a467293	Socioeconomic characteristics of the patient diagnosis and pre-admission problems, treatment data, and diagnosis and residual problems at discharge.
National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance	Health insurance databases				2008 onwards	Belgium	https://www.ima-aim.be/-Nos-banques-de-donnees-	Medical and paramedical services and medicines
Sciensano network of general practitioners	health problems (infectious and non-infectious diseases)	Incidence			1979 onwards	Belgium	https://www.sciensano.be/en/projects/network-general-practitioners	
Belgian Health Interview Survey	health status, life style and medical consumption				every 5 years since 1997	Belgium	https://www.sciensano.be/en/projects/health-interview-survey	Representative sample of the general Belgian population (sample of ~10 000 people). Information is also collected on a wide range of sociodemographic background characteristics. Interviews are carried out through a face-to-face interview and a self-complete questionnaire.
Belgian National Burden of Disease Study	various diseases, injuries	YLL, YLD, DALY, deaths, prevalent cases	modelled	Belgian Cancer Registry, the Intermutualistic Agency, the Belgian Health Interview Survey, the Minimal Clinical Data, the Intego general practice sentinel network, and the European kidney registry	2013-2019	Belgium	https://burden.sciensano.be/shiny/daly/	
Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (CEpiP)	Maternal and perinatal health statistics (births and perinatal deaths)	Incidence, mortality	registry		2008 onwards	Wallonia + Brussels (Belgium)	https://www.cepip.be/mission1.php?LG=fr	Statistical analyses of live births and stillbirths, as well as obstetric practices, in Brussels and in Wallonia, since 2008. More precise data can be requested.
The Danish Register of Causes of Death	Causes of death	mortality	registry		1970-2020 (only data from 2002 and onwards are publicly available on the webpage)	Denmark (incl. subnational data)	https://www.esundhed.dk/Registre/Doedsaarsagsregistret#tabpanel197BF92C33E84D969EA49D0D9D4ABCA	In Danish only. Mortality (absolute and rate) by cause (ICD 10), age, gender, region, year
Hjertefond (the Danish Heart Foundation)	Cardiovascular diseases (ICD 10 codes: I00-I99, E10.5, E11.1, E14.5, L97.9)	Incidence, mortality, survival rates	registry		2004-2018	Denmark (incl. subnational data)	https://hjertereforeningen.shinyapps.io/HjerteTal/?input_select=22national%22&bar=%22cvd%22&years=%222018%22&varCVD=%22v1%22&ocVD=%22d1%22	In Danish only. Statistics by ICD 10 codes, age, gender, region, year, education.
Norcan database (Association of the Nordic Cancer Registries)	Cancer	Incidence, mortality, predicted incidence and mortality, prevalence, survival	registry		1943-2020	Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Iceland, Finland	https://nordcan.iarc.fr/en/dataviz/	Various cancer sites. Statistics by ICD 10 codes, age, gender, country, year
EUROCAT	Congenital anomalies	Incidence, mortality, predicted incidence and mortality, prevalence, survival	registry		2005-2020	Europe (43 registries from 23 countries)	https://eu-rd-platform.irc.ec.europa.eu/eurocat_en	European network of population-based registries for the epidemiological surveillance of congenital anomalies. Data cover 29% of the European births.
European Cancer Information System	Cancer	Incidence, mortality, survival	registry	European population-based cancer registries	depending on country - from 1983 on	Europe	https://ecis.irc.ec.europa.eu/	
European Deprivation Index - EDI		ecological level socio-economic deprivation index	modelled	National censuses + EU-SILC	periodically, depending on national census data availability	France, Italy, Spain, Northern Ireland, Portugal, Slovenia and Lithuania	http://www.wasabysite.it/wp5.html	EDI is available on smallest aggregated level possible for particular country.
GBD (Global burden of disease study)	369 diseases and injuries, 286 causes of death. Outcomes are organized in four levels of causes, where level 2 includes e.g. cardiovascular, chronic respiratory, diabetes, neurological disorders, etc.	YLL, YLD, DALY, deaths, prevalence, incidence	modelled	Selection of input data depends on national availability, applied data include censuses, insurance data, disease registries, birth and death registry data, surveys and population studies, scientific literature	1990-2019 (2020-21 to be published soon)	National data for all European countries, and subnational data for Norway, UK and Sweden (only Stockholm + rest)	Data extraction tool: https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/ Data input source tool: https://ghdx.healthdata.org/gbd-2019/data-input-sources	Data can be downloaded after registration as a user

4. Health-outcome data

NCOD (Norwegian Cause of Death registry)	Selection of disease groups, e.g. pulmonary, circulatory, tumors etc	deaths	registry	1972-2021	Norway (can apply for subnational data)	General information (for data application form): https://www.fhi.no/en/hn/health-registries/cause-of-death-registry/ Database (in Norwegian only): http://statistikkbank.fhi.no/dar/	Can apply for number of deaths per year based on disease definitions in terms of ICD10 codes
Portuguese Food and Physical Activity Survey	Pre-obesity and obesity	Prevalence	Survey	2015-2016	Portugal	https://www.ian-af.up.pt	National based survey with anthropometric measurements
SM-COVID Study	Mental health	Prevalence	Survey	2020-2022	Portugal	https://sm-covid19.pt	Conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic period, already with 4 waves of data collection
EPIReumaPt	rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases	Prevalence	Survey	2011-2013	Portugal	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26848402/	National health survey to estimate the national prevalence of rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases and to determine their impact on health-related quality of life (HRQoL), physical function, anxiety and depression (includes survey and clinical assessment).
Central Portuguese Cancer registry	Cancer	Incidence and mortality	registry	2001 onwards	Portugal	https://ron.min-saude.pt/biblioteca/publicacoes-ron/	Portuguese only. Various cancer sites. Statistics by ICD 9 and 10 codes, age, gender, year, Portuguese regions
Portuguese mandatory reporting of infectious diseases	Infectious diseases (HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, cholera, etc.)	Incidence	registry	1990 onwards	Portugal	https://www.pordata.pt/portugal/doencas+de+declaracao+obrigatoria+casos+notificados-773	Authorization required. Portuguese only. Statistics by disease and year.
Slovenian Cancer Registry database	Cancer	Incidence, mortality, predicted incidence and mortality, prevalence, survival	registry	1950-2020	Slovenia	http://www.slora.si/en/	All cancer sites. Statistics by ICD 10 codes, age, gender, year, geographical location on level of x,y coordinates. Corresponding background population information
National institute of public health (NIJZ) Slovenia	inpatient and outpatient treatment depending on the reason/disease (with MKB-10 code)	pevalence	register of hospital treatments; register of medical treatments (out of hospital)	2010-2021	Slovenia (option for local/regional data as well)	Aggregated data is available here : https://podatki.nijz.si/ (we have the possibility of individual data)	
National institute of public health (NIJZ) Slovenia	deaths depending on the reason/disease (with cause and external cause) from MKB-10 code	deaths	register of death persons	2010-2021	Slovenia (option for local/regional data as well)	Aggregated data is available here : https://podatki.nijz.si/ (we have the possibility of individual data)	
National institute of public health (NIJZ) Slovenia	poisonings (with MKB-10 code)	pevalence	register of poisonings	2010-2021	Slovenia (option for local/regional data as well)	Aggregated data is available here : https://podatki.nijz.si/ (we have the possibility of individual data)	
National institute of public health (NIJZ) Slovenia	births	pevalence	birth register	2010-2021	Slovenia (option for local/regional data as well)	Aggregated data is available here : https://podatki.nijz.si/ (we have the possibility of individual data)	
PMSI (French hospital databases)	Hospitalizations and reimbursement information in hospitals (public or private type)	Prevalence	Register	2007 onward	France (national and regional)	Aggregated data : https://www.scansante.fr/ (in French)	Hospitalizations and any reimbursed medical act. National and regional data available. By diagnostic code (ICD10). PMSI is part of the French SNDS (national health data system). More detailed data (but no individual) can be gathered after agreement.
CépiDC (Epidemiology Center of Medical Causes of Death)	Deaths and causes of death	Deaths	Registry	1979-2020 (Metropolitan France only)	France (national and regional)	Aggregated data (N or rates) here : https://opendata-cepidc.inserm.fr/ (in French)	By causes, sex and age. National and regional data available. Causes of deaths in 86 categories. CépiDC is part of the French SNDS (national health data system).

4. Health-outcome data

Annex III

Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach for health impact assessment / EBD

1. Introduction

The objective of this report is to generate a short overview of weight of evidence (WoE) approaches currently applied for hazard identification by various organizations, institutions and projects. How is “causality” addressed? By analyzing causality, the quality of the evidence is weighed, and this includes an analysis of the uncertainty. In the 21st century there is a shift towards the integration of different types of evidence in risk assessment. There are new technologies, high throughput methods, new approach methodologies (NAMs) etc. that all need to be integrated in a holistic view to assess causality for human health risk assessment. There is a desire to base (analytical) health impact assessment, environmental burden of disease (EBD) estimates and risk assessment on the best available scientific evidence. In quantitative approaches like EBD, the inclusion of exposure-outcome pairs in the calculations should reflect causal associations. Thus, a causality evaluation should precede the selection of the exposure-response functions (ERF), and the current WoE approaches summarized here are useful in developing a framework for addressing causality that can be applied in the case studies of task 6.2.4 where multiple sources of data will be gathered and evaluated.

One of the aspects we aimed to target in the first year of the PARC 6.2.4 methodology project concerns the uncertainty of the exposure response functions (ERF) applied in HIA and EBD. In the next chapters the focus will be on causality evaluation, which should precede the development of the exposure-response functions and form the basis for the selection of exposure-outcome pairs to be included in the quantitative assessments. Other aspects of the ERF like statistical or sampling variation, shape of the ERF (linear vs non-linear), existence of a threshold, underrepresentation of specific groups when the ERF was obtained will be covered in subsequent reports.

2. General weight of evidence approaches in literature

Analytical HIA or EBD calculations include a hazard assessment. The hazard assessment requires the analysis of different types of data and a Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach is often followed to conclude on the potential to cause hazards. In the sections below we focus on the hazard side and the WoE for application of an exposure-response function in analytical HIA or EBD.

2.1 Definition

There is no formal adopted definition of the WoE approach. The WoE is defined by WHO as “a process in which all of the evidence considered relevant for a risk assessment is evaluated and

weighted”. The Scientific Committee (SC) of EFSA follows this definition of WHO. ANSES defines WoE as “the structured synthesis of lines of evidence, possibly of varying quality, to determine the extent of support for hypotheses” (ANSES, 2016b). A line of evidence (LOE) is a set of relevant information of similar type grouped to assess a hypothesis. A weight is assigned to each LOE.

OECD defines WoE as “a positive expert opinion that considers available evidence from different independent sources and scientific viewpoints on a particular issue, coming to a considered view of the available, oftentimes conflicting data. It is preferred when every source does not provide sufficient information individually”. Several WoE approaches are presented in literature.

2.2 EFSA

In its “Guidance on the use of the WoE approach in scientific assessments”, EFSA addresses qualitative and quantitative approaches. Three basic steps are proposed: a) assembling the evidence in lines of evidence, b) weighing the evidence and c) integrating the evidence taking into account data gaps (EFSA, 2017). The question to be addressed by each weight of evidence assessment is defined by problem formulation, which is a preceding step in the scientific assessment as a whole. The WoE approach requires weighing different lines of evidence (in vivo, in vitro, in silico, population studies, modelled and measured exposure data, etc.), which may originate from studies conducted according to official guidelines (e.g., OECD) or from non-standardized methodologies. For the weighting step, reliability (correctness), relevance (answering the question) and consistency (compatibility pieces of evidence) are considered as three basic considerations. Uncertainty and WoE are closely related. The WoE assessment contributes to an uncertainty analysis, addressing limitations in reliability, relevance, and consistency (EFSA, 2017).

For evaluation of causality (weighting step) the Bradford Hill criteria are often used for epidemiological studies (Hill, 1965). For rating the evidence, in 2000 a systematic approach was developed by the GRADE⁵ working group. GRADE criteria (OSHA, 2016), build on approaches of causal criteria (Hill). More dimensions than just the quality of the research are accounted for: risk of bias, imprecisions, and indirectness, how results are going to be applied and any inconsistency and publication bias (Schünemann et al., 2008; Guyatt et al., 2011; Balshem et al., 2011). GRADE classifies the level of evidence in 4 categories: high, moderate, low, very low (Table 1).

⁵ Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation

Table 1. GRADE Quality assessment criteria, Adapted from (Guyatt et al., 2011).

Study Design	Quality of Evidence	Lower if	Higher if
Randomized trial →	High	Risk of bias -1 Serious -2 Very serious	Large effect +1 Large +2 Very large
	Moderate	Inconsistency -1 Serious -2 Very serious	Dose response +1 Evidence of a gradient
Observational study →	Low	Indirectness -1 Serious -2 Very serious	All plausible confounding +1 Would reduce a demonstrated effect or
	Very low	Imprecision -1 Serious -2 Very serious Publication bias -1 Likely -2 Very likely	+1 Would suggest a spurious effect when results show no effect

EFSA proposes quantitative methods (e.g., meta-analysis) over qualitative methods to assess the WoE. However, there are some caveats: a) quantitative methods may not be appropriate for various reasons (not applicable to the evidence; not practical within the time) and b) quantitative methods may not address all the considerations that are relevant for weighing the evidence. Transparent reporting, including where expert judgement was used, is necessary.

EFSA identifies areas of its work where a formalized weight of evidence assessment is especially needed and initiates further work to apply suitable approaches from this guidance in those areas. This might include, for example, the integration of different types of evidence in chemical risk assessment, including in vivo, in vitro, in silico, omics, PBPK modelling as well as the Mode of Action and Adverse Outcome Pathway concepts. This recommendation by EFSA shows where there is room for improvement for the hazard assessment.

2.3 Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks

The WoE described by the Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (SCHEER, 2018) is an iterative process involving:

- Problem formulation
- Identification, collection, and selection of the possible sources of evidence
- Assessment and weighing of individual lines of evidence based on relevance (for a particular hazard), validity (method relative to accepted guidelines) and reliability (way procedure and results are described)

- Integration of lines of evidence (may demand expert judgement)
- Description of uncertainties
- Conclusion and reporting

In the step assessing and weighing individual lines of evidence, relevance, validity, and reliability are each classified in one of the categories of high, medium or low. Based on expert judgement, an overall category for quality is derived. General aspects which can be taken into account are:

- Differentiation between non-adverse and adverse effects
- Ensuring that the adverse effect is related to exposure (e.g., substance or material-related)
- Assessment of biological relevance, not simply statistical significance. A biologically relevant effect can be defined as an effect considered by expert judgement as important and meaningful for human, animal, plant or environmental health. It therefore implies a change that may alter how decisions for a specific problem are taken (EFSA, 2017)
- Presence of dose/time-effect relationship
- Data on the reversibility of effect
- Information on normal variation in the incidence of the disease/effect of interest (e.g., consideration of historical controls).

In the individual lines of evidence, the nature of uncertainty can be mentioned together with an influence on the final conclusion (minor (↑), intermediate (↑↑) and strong (↑↑↑) upward influence on probability (Table 2).

Table 2. Expression of uncertainty for individual lines of evidence. Adapted from (SCHEER, 2018)

Aspect	Nature of the uncertainty	Influence on conclusion	Importance of the uncertainty
Line of evidence 1 Key aspects: * *		↑, ↑↑, ↑↑↑	
Line of evidence 2 Key aspects: * *		↑, ↑↑, ↑↑↑	
Line of evidence x Key aspects: * *		↑, ↑↑, ↑↑↑	
Conclusion after integration of lines of evidence		↑, ↑↑, ↑↑↑	

Key to symbols: ↑, ↑↑, ↑↑↑ represent minor, intermediate and strong upward influence on probability respectively (see EFSA, 2017).

In the context of human studies more emphasis is given to meta-analyses, from randomized human trials and experimental studies, prospective (cohort) studies and retrospective case-control studies. Robust conclusions can rarely be drawn from cross-sectional studies or case reports. Ecological studies generally provide a more limited level of evidence, certainly those focusing on spatial contrasts. The increased use of metabolic systems in in vitro data and the extrapolation from in vitro to in vivo by modeling is being explored. **This might possibly allow the future use of in vitro data for exposure response assessment in humans. This observation by SCHEER shows where there are possibilities for improvement in developing exposure-response functions for humans.**

A meta-analysis is considered the best approach to derive exposure-response relationships in humans.

A system is proposed that classifies results of analysis for human and environmental risks in terms of (final result of the integration):

- Strong weight of evidence: Coherent evidence from a primary line of evidence (human, animal, environment) and one or more other lines of evidence (in particular mode/mechanistic studies) in the absence of conflicting evidence from one of the other lines of evidence (no important data gaps)
- Moderate weight of evidence: good evidence from a primary line of evidence but evidence from several other lines is missing (important data gaps)
- Weak weight of evidence: weak evidence from the primary lines of evidence (severe data gaps)

- Uncertain weight of evidence: due to conflicting information from different lines of evidence that cannot be explained in scientific terms
- Weighing of evidence not possible: No suitable evidence available

Integration implies combining conclusions of different lines of evidence and consistency (e.g., mode of action) and this demands an element of expert judgement.

Currently results from in silico and in vitro tests tend to make a lesser contribution to the overall weighing but this may change with time.

2.4 OECD

The framework of OECD (OECD, 2019) proposes in the WoE approach encompass following steps:

- Problem formulation (hypothesis development)
- Evidence collection (establish lines of evidence and knowledge gaps)
- Evidence evaluation (determine data reliability, uncertainty and relevance)
- Evidence weighing (assign weight to evidence)
- Evidence integration and reporting (examine evidence coherence and impact of uncertainty).

These are consistent with several other approaches (e.g., SCHEER, EFSA).

The acceptance level for uncertainty is related to the decision context and the protection goal and thus needs to be defined upfront at the problem formulation stage.

For evidence evaluation, reliability and relevance are two key terms. Reliability refers to the quality, sufficiency (quantity) and consistency of the data evaluated under a LoE and considers the associated contribution of uncertainty of each of these parameters. Klimisch criteria are often used to assess the quality of toxicological data but “the scoring of information should not exclude all unreliable data from further consideration by expert judgment”. For epidemiological data, Bradford Hill criteria are often applied for determining the confidence in the evidence towards causality. Relevance refers to the appropriateness or degree of correspondence of evidence to the hypothesis question outlined in the problem formulation. It is however emphasized that attributing a relevant versus non-relevant classification should be carefully considered and be context specific. Highly relevant lines of evidence are those corresponding closely to the hypothesis generated in the problem formulation (i.e., have high regulatory and scientific impact and require lower extrapolation).

According to OECD the different lines of evidence can be numerically scored but often a qualitative approach (e.g., low, medium, high) is used to weigh the evidence. Regardless of what methodology is used, the approach should be transparent.

OECD concludes by saying that “The data landscape for chemical prioritisation and risk assessment continues to change and now includes multiple sources of non-traditional data. WoE approaches will necessarily need to continue to evolve and adapt to meet this data context, particularly as it relates to 21st century risk science (including exposure science), IATA and development and support for AOPs. A case study on the integration and application of alternative data for decision-making could provide an ideal example to demonstrate the principles and elements described in this document.” This could be an opportunity for assessment in PARC.

2.5 ECHA

ECHA proposes a 6-step iterative approach (ECHA, 2017):

- Problem formulation
- Collection & Documentation of all information
- Assessment of quality of individual evidence (reliability, relevance, adequacy)
- Integration & Weighing of Evidence
- Application of levels of confidence
- Uncertainty Analysis

The assessment of the quality of individual evidence is performed using the Klimisch criteria in all REACH/BPR processes for the reliability of the evidence of experimental studies. GRADE criteria provide an approach for assessing the quality of clinical data. Systematic review frameworks can be used. The OHAT approach provides an approach for assessing the risk of bias (OHAT NTP, 2015). For OHAT, see further the approach made by ANSES.

Criteria specified for the WoE are: adequacy, relevance, reliability for individual evidence assessment, and consistency/specificity, plausibility/likelihood, temporality for WoE analysis).

Confidence levels are usually expressed as: high, medium, low.

For the overall confidence level, a similar approach as described for SCHEER can be applied going from strong, moderate, weak, uncertain and weighing of the evidence not possible.

An example is worked out in the ECHA guidance for “the mode of Action of DCHP for endocrine mediated irreversible effects to the male reproductive system with the potential to affect male reproductive function and its relevance to Humans”.

2.6 ANSES (based on NTP OHAT)

ANSES published recommendations to perform a WoE and proposed a general approach across multiple hazard domains: planning the assessment (scoping), establishing lines of evidence, integrating lines of evidence and expressing conclusions on the WoE (ANSES, 2016c). The same year, ANSES analysed the consideration of uncertainties in health risk assessment and developed a harmonized uncertainty analysis framework to be applied in its activities (ANSES, 2016a).

The objectives of these reports were to describe the current practices of ANSES and compare them with those of other health organizations or agencies, to critically review these approaches and to develop recommendations for the different steps of the WoE assessment and uncertainty analysis.

Later on, ANSES clarified and illustrated the above-mentioned recommendations through case studies conducted within ANSES during 2016-2017 (ANSES, 2017). One of those case studies related to the health effects of ambient air particulate matter according to its components, sources and particle size (ANSES, 2019). The NTP OHAT approach was adapted and applied (Office of Health Assessment and Translation as part of the National Toxicology Program) (OHAT NTP, 2015). A critical analysis of the approach explaining its limitations and uncertainties was included. A similar approach was later followed for the systematic literature review on the characterization of the hazards associated with asbestos ingestion (ANSES, 2021).

The framework consists of 7 steps. An overview is given in Figure 1.

Main points to keep in mind are:

- The WoE coming from epidemiological data and in vivo data (from animal studies for example) are assessed in parallel, following the same steps. Some differentiations were made in the tools used to assess the quality of the studies, but conclusions are expressed the same (i.e., levels of evidence) and the lines of evidence are assessed the same way.
- The NTP OHAT approach allows the combination of the conclusions (i.e., levels of evidence) from epidemiological data and in vivo data to conclude on the overall WoE (see figure 1 in Rooney et al., 2014). This option was not applied as such in the ANSES' reports; overall conclusions were mainly driven by epidemiological evidence with the support of animal data if available and relevant.
- **The NTP OHAT approach does not integrate mechanistic or in vitro data. There is room for improvement on this topic.** In ANSES (2021) on asbestos ingestion, the quality of mechanistic studies was assessed qualitatively, and their conclusions were simply used to support the WoE from human and animal studies when relevant.
- In its report, ANSES recommends characterizing the uncertainty around the WoE conclusions, either qualitatively or quantitatively. One proposed way of integrating quantitative uncertainty is the use of Bayesian modelling as in Gosling et al. (2013). They

combined expert knowledge (translated in terms of expectations and variances) with data from toxicological studies using a Bayesian method. The NTP OHAT approach does not include a specific “expression of uncertainty” but does recommend being very transparent along the process (e.g., when combining intermediate results into an overall conclusion).

The WoE assessment steps are described as follow:

Step 1: Formulation of scope of the problem

Step 2: Study search and selection

Step 3: Data extraction

Data were described according to the grid format suggested by OHAT and summarized related to subjects (human, animal), methods (follow-up time, study design, health outcomes and categories, exposure measurement or estimation, etc.) and results.

Step 4: Quality assessment individual studies

The risk of bias was assessed using an adapted version of the rating tool proposed by OHAT that applies to both human and animal experimental studies. The tool includes 15 questions related to potential sources of bias. Categories considered include selection, attrition, interpretation, confounding, detection, and others. Response options were low risk, probably low risk, probably high risk and high risk. Risks were independently assessed and then discussed by 2 experts to get a final rating. Discrepancies in ratings were discussed to reach consensus (sometimes among the whole working group).

Regardless of the bias rating, 4 questions (1 if yes, 0 if not) needed to be answered to score an initial confidence level.

- 1) Was the exposure controlled?
- 2) Did the exposure occur prior to the outcome?
- 3) Were the health outcome data individual?
- 4) Was a group comparison used?

If the initial confidence is very low (i.e., confidence level of 1) the study is not considered anymore in the WoE assessment. Experimental studies (animal experimentation, controlled clinical trials, etc.) generally have a maximum initial confidence level of 4. Observational studies generally have an initial confidence level of 2 or 3, which never exceeds 3 due to the lack of controlled exposure.

Step 5: Assessing confidence in the body of evidence

The publications were grouped in lines of evidence. Grouping used: type of study (animal, human), components or sources when relevant, exposure timings (short term or long term), health categories and health outcomes examined.

The final confidence was assessed based on 10 factors proposed by OHAT.

- Downgrading factors: risk of bias, unexplained inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, publication bias.
- Upgrading factors: magnitude of effect, dose response, residual confounding, consistency, others.

The final confidence level corresponds to the initial level (from 1 to 4, see Step 4) minus the factors decreasing confidence (from 0 to 5) and plus the factors increasing confidence (from 0 to 5). Each line of evidence was assessed by one person and then discussed by the whole working group. Final decisions (to increase or decrease the level of confidence) were taken after consensus.

Lastly, for each line of evidence on the basis of the results provided by the body of evidence, a decision was taken by the working group on the direction of the effect on the health effect for a given timing of exposure.

Step 6: Translation into level of evidence

The final confidence level of the body of evidence and direction of the health effect were merged to obtain a level of evidence for an adverse health effect (see step 6 in Figure 1). Level of evidence were: "high", "moderate", "low", "inadequate", and "no health effect". Adaptations are possible (e.g., the working group for the asbestos ingestion report differentiated two sublevels of the "inadequate" level of evidence) but they make the results more complicated to understand, so caution is required.

- "High" level of evidence: there is high confidence in the body of evidence to support the association between exposure and the health outcome.
- "Moderate" level of evidence: there is moderate confidence in the body of evidence to support the association between exposure and the health outcome.
- "Low" level of evidence: there is low confidence in the body of evidence to support the association between exposure and the health outcome.
- "Inadequate" level of evidence: confidence in the body of evidence is inadequate to rule as to whether or not there is an association between exposure and the health outcome.
- "No health effect" level of evidence: there is high confidence in the body of evidence to support the lack of an association between exposure and the health outcome.

The first three levels of evidence (high, moderate and low) directly characterize the degree of plausibility for the association between the exposure and the health outcome. The inadequate

level of evidence is used when confidence in the body of evidence is too low to rule as to the plausibility of the association or to support the lack of an association.

Step 7: Conclusion

Figure 1. Weight of evidence approach by ANSES working group adapted from NTP OHAT. (Source: (ANSES, 2019).

2.7 Athlete project⁶

The objective of this project was to summarize the level of evidence (LoE) linking a large number of environmental (chemical and urban) exposure factors to child health, considering findings from epidemiological, toxicological and mechanistic studies in order to build a

⁶ <https://athleteproject.eu/>

“plausibility database”. For this, a pragmatic approach was developed based on the conclusions of already-performed reviews, both from agency reports and the published scientific literature.

Description of the framework

The WoE approach includes four major steps, detailed in the following paragraphs.

Step 1 – identification of relevant sources of information

For each exposure factor, we first searched for recent agency reports published between 2015 and 2021 (such as WHO, EFSA, ECHA, NTP, US EPA). An agency report was considered relevant source of information when a) the association between one or multiple given factors and one or multiple health outcomes was specifically investigated in the relevant population (infants, children, and animal-equivalent) and b) at least one stream of evidence (epidemiological, toxicological, mechanistic) was considered. If no 2015-2021 report could be identified or if the identified reports did not altogether cover the three streams (epidemiological, toxicological, mechanistic), older reports were looked into. Finally, if one or more line of evidence was still missing, published reviews were searched for. PubMed and SCOPUS databases were accessed to identify reviews published in English through generic search queries including a combination of general keywords and concepts. First, reviews that appeared out of scope were excluded based on title and abstract screening. Second, based on full-text screening, reviews were selected in agreement with our Population, Exposure, Comparator, Outcomes (PECO) criteria for inclusion. For the epidemiological and toxicological streams, only systematic reviews were considered, since non-systematic reviews tend to report only positive results. Regarding mechanistic data, all types of reviews were retained.

Step 2 – quality assessment

The conclusions from agency reports were considered a priori to be reliable, so they were all considered to establish the level of evidence without specific quality assessment. It is acknowledged that they may not be fail-safe, but they use scientifically sound methodologies and supporting tools commonly accepted by assessment bodies worldwide. Moreover, they often rely on a relevant number of multi-disciplinary experts in their respective areas of expertise or on working groups of scientists with relevant expertise.

To assess the quality of the systematic reviews, one assessor used a modified version of the Assessment of Multiple Systematic Reviews-2 (AMSTAR-2) (Shea et al., 2017). Only those scored as being of moderate or high quality according to AMSTAR-2 tool were included and considered for establishing the level of evidence.

The non-systematic reviews dedicated to mechanistic data were assessed using SANRA (Baethge et al., 2019). Only those evaluated as moderate and high quality were used to establish the level of evidence.

Step 3 – data extraction

For each exposure-outcome pair, each stream and each source of information, the dataset text underlying the authors’ conclusions was extracted as well as the overall conclusions encompassing all streams if available. These data are reported in the “plausibility database”.

Step 4 – level of evidence definition and assessment

The level of evidence was classified into 5 levels as adapted from (EFSA, 2019), from “very unlikely” to “very likely”. Each level of evidence was allocated with a quantitative expression of the probability of causation with an uncertainty interval (EFSA, 2019). A level of evidence with a probability of causation of 60 % or more was considered to be high. Two independent assessors assessed the level of evidence according to the process described below; disagreements were adjudicated by a third assessor.

For a given factor-outcome pair and existing source of information:

1. If a general conclusion integrating all streams of evidence was available, the wording used in the source of information was directly translated into a level of evidence with a corresponding synthetic probability of causation. For example:

Keywords used in the general conclusion (i.e. covering all streams of evidence)	LoE, probability of causation and uncertainty interval
Certain, known, demonstrate that, very likely, must, recognized, robust, provide sufficient evidence, consistent evidence, to strongly indicate, causal relationship, CLP category 1A, there is evidence, convincing	Very likely 90% [80%-100%[
Probable, presumed, likely, can, could, to contribute to the evidence, likely to be a causal relationship, indicate + target of concern, CLP category 1B	Likely 70% [60%-80%[
(...)	(...)

2. If a conclusion covering only one stream of evidence was available in the source of information, the wording used was translated into stream-specific descriptors (weak, moderate, strong). For example:

Keywords used in stream-specific conclusion (i.e. covering one stream of evidence only)	Stream-specific descriptors
Certain, known, demonstrate that, very likely, must, recognized, robust, provide sufficient evidence, causal relation, consistent, strongly point/ indicate, highly support, substantial evidence, sufficient plausibility, be responsible, show, clearly, cause, high, strong, numerous, <u>compelling</u> , provide evidence, substantial evidence, consistent, highly support, consistently, severely, alters, disrupt, highly plausible, convincing	Strong
Probable, presumed, likely, can, could, to contribute to the evidence, not entirely consistent, not firmly established, generally/relatively consistent, not fully characterized, putative, possible, possibly, moderate, appears to, verified, rather support, relatively complete, in general + provide evidence, indicate a concern, are thought, significant association	Moderate
(…)	(…)

3. If no stream-specific conclusion was available, the two assessors quoted independently the harmonized descriptors based on the data reported in the source of information. If the report or review did not cover a given stream, the “no data” harmonized descriptor was applied.

4. The harmonized descriptors of the three streams (from steps 2. and 3.) were then combined into a LoE with synthetic probability of causation according to a matrix adapted from IARC (Samet et al., 2020) and EFSA (2019). The reliability of the matrix was tested on a limited number of factors by checking whether the combination of the 3 streams would lead to the same LoE as the one obtained by direct translation of the general conclusion. If no data could be retrieved, no LoE nor synthetic probability of evidence was allocated. The top of combination matrix looks like this:

Stream-specific descriptors			LoE, probability of causation, uncertainty interval
Epidemiological stream	Toxicological stream	Mechanistic stream	
Strong	Anything from no data to strong	Anything from no data to strong	Very likely 90% [80%-100%]
Moderate	Strong	Strong	
Weak-Very weak-No data	Strong	Strong	
Moderate	Strong	Moderate	Likely 70% [60%-80%]
Moderate	Strong	Weak-Very weak-No data	
Moderate	Moderate	Strong	
Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	
Moderate	Moderate	Weak-Very weak-No data	
Moderate	Weak-Very weak-No data	Strong	
Moderate	Weak-Very weak-No data	Moderate	
Weak-Very weak-No data	Strong	Moderate	
Weak-Very weak-No data	Moderate	Strong	
Weak-Very weak-No data	Moderate	Moderate	
Weak-Very weak-No data	Strong	Weak-Very weak-No data	
(...)			

If several eligible reports or publications reported different levels of evidence for a given factor-outcome pair, the LoEs and uncertainty intervals were enlarged to encompass the range. For instance, if “likely (70% [60%-80%])” and “very likely (90% [80%-100%])” were obtained from two different sources, the corresponding LoE and probability of causation for the pair was “from likely to very likely (80% [60-100%])”.

Below the example of the LoE for the effects of Cd on neurodevelopment in children is shown. Four sources of information were identified, covering all streams of evidence altogether; several outcomes were investigated, all grouped under the “neurodevelopment” umbrella. The overall conclusion (i.e., LoE) for the pair Cd-neurodevelopment is “From As likely as not to Likely” with high uncertainty (40-80%) related to the heterogeneity in the sources’ conclusions.

Source	Outcomes investigated	Epidemiological stream		Toxicological stream		Mechanistic stream		LoE
		Keywords	Descriptor	Keywords	Descriptor	Keywords	Descriptor	
ANSES, 2019	Cognitive	Suggest	Weak	(None)	No data	(None)	No data	From As likely as not to Likely - 60% [40%-80%]
HBM4EU, 2021	Cognitive	Limited	Weak	(None)	No data	(None)	No data	
ATSDR, 2012	Neuro developmental effects	No update		Appears to be	Moderate	Paucity	Very weak	
Rodríguez-Barranco et al. 2013	Neuro toxicity	No update		(None)	No data	Suggest	Weak	
Branca et al. 2020	Neuro toxicity	No update		(None)	No data	Can	Moderate	

2.8 National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine

The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine in the US recently published a report on “Advancing the Framework for Assessing Causality of Health and Welfare Effects⁷”. It is directly related to the NAAQS reviews (i.e., ambient air pollution) in the US, in particular the Integrated Science Assessments (ISA) conducted by the US EPA. The final report on particulate matter⁸ was released in 2022.

The EPA Office of Research and Development requested the National Academies to i) consider existing frameworks and new advances and tools for integrating, documenting, and evaluating scientific evidence for assessing causality of health and welfare effects, ii) describe how EPA’s methods for classifying the weight of evidence for causation might be refined, and iii) make recommendations related to the development and use of a future causal determination framework.

In chapter 7, the report summarizes some illustrative frameworks for causal determinations (including TSCA, WHO, IRIS, OHAT, IARC, UNECE and CSSA).

In chapter 8, the report provides a summary of methods used in observational studies that could be incorporated into the causal determination – in relation with improved exposure assessment, handling confounders, multiple exposures and effect modification/variation across subgroups.

A summary of the highlights and recommendations is given below:

⁷ <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/26612/advancing-the-framework-for-assessing-causality-of-health-and-welfare-effects-to-inform-national-ambient-air-quality-standard-reviews>

⁸ <https://cfpub.epa.gov/ncea/isa/recordisplay.cfm?deid=354490>

On the WoE framework used by the US EPA for the ISA (Integrated Science Assessment), the National Academies recommend increasing transparency and clearer articulation between the framework's steps. A single causal determination framework for both health and welfare endpoints allow the integration of several aspects of the exposure impact but needs appropriate problem identification. The causal categories provided are reasonable and express a degree of uncertainty.

The National Academies recommend the framework to provide more guidance regarding addressing uncertainties into the determination of causality (for example, heterogeneity in exposure response). These would increase confidence in the causal determination process and yield greater utility of the results.

Regarding the WoE approach used by the US EPA, the National Academies concluded as follows: *"A weight of evidence approach—combining assessment of study quality with expert judgment—allows EPA to draw conclusions that integrate scientific findings across multiple study designs and disciplines. Increased transparency in how evidence is integrated would improve confidence and understanding of the ISA causal determinations and other conclusions."* Points of attention are the assessment of study quality, of combining study quality and expert judgement, of increased transparency (including in the study selection process).

Regarding the granularity of the causal categories, the National Academies considered it to be scientifically meaningful and useful in the context of the NAAQS reviews. The levels expressed some kind of uncertainty degree: *"causal relationship," "likely to be a causal relationship," "suggestive of, but not sufficient to infer, a causal relationship," "inadequate to infer the presence or absence of a causal relationship,"* and *"not likely a causal relationship"*. They are associated with summaries of key strengths and limitations of the body of evidence. They are broadly consistent with those of other regulatory and health and environmental guidance groups.

Regarding the heterogeneity in exposure responses, the National Academies noted the heterogeneity in the response of individuals and populations complicates causal assessments. The current framework explicitly guides consideration of heterogeneity in response to exposures only after a causal determination is made. The associated recommendation is to include guidelines in the framework regarding how heterogeneity in exposure responses is considered to ensure causal determinations fully account for evidence of effects in sensitive groups of humans, other species, and ecosystems. The framework should provide guidance on how evidence should be examined for key sensitive groups and then integrated across endpoints or subgroups in establishing causal determinations. Methods are needed to systematically assess possible bias due to lack of representation in individual studies and in the overall body of evidence with respect to groups, species, or ecosystems that are expected

to be at heightened risk. Research is also needed to understand how causal determinations are influenced by such biases.

Regarding study quality selection and evaluation, the National Academies noted the current framework describes general guidance for study quality evaluation but minimal detail on the determination of individual studies relevance, inclusion or exclusion, or influence on WoE causal determination. The recommendations are i) to include a set of foundational study design attributes and analysis approaches to be considered when selecting and evaluating studies used for causal determinations ii) to provide explicit guidance for assessing the methods used in individual studies (specifically how they account for important and potentially biasing confounders) and how those methods might influence WoE considerations in causal determinations.

Regarding the transparency and the WoE approach, the National Academies noted that EPA recognizes the importance of replicability of individual studies when determining causality. But the current framework does not provide explicit guidance on how the potential reproducibility and replicability of individual studies affect the influence of those studies on causal assessments. The associated recommendation is to develop guidance for assessing individual study transparency, reproducibility, and replicability (documentation of data, methods and assumptions) and how this assessment influences the study weight in the approach.

Regarding the integration of the evidence, the National Academies recommended to monitor research on evidence integration and monitor the evolution of other frameworks used to assess causality (IRIA and OHAT for example) to determine if any emerging approaches or characteristics might be adapted. The National Academies do not recommend the use of more formal methods of quantitative scoring for individual studies or preassigned rubrics for combining evidence as there is evidence to show that they provide either a more reliable or explainable result than the consensus approach. No single formal tool is available that does not ultimately depend on expert evaluation for its inputs.

2.9 Peer reviewed scientific literature

Different frameworks for assessing causality are described in international scientific literature. Some main observations are shortly described here. No systematic review was done so the highlighted literature is not exhaustive.

Martin et al. (2018) did a critical review of WOE analysis methods as a basis for developing a practical framework for considering and assessing WOE in hazard identification at ANSES. Suter et al. (2017; 2020) proposed a framework to integrate best practices (e.g., systematic reviews) into a methodical assembly and weighing of evidence. Krewski et al. (2022) proposed

a preliminary evidence-based risk assessment framework with different tiers depending on data availability. With the advent of new approach methodologies in toxicological risk assessment, guidance is needed to integrate evidence from multiple evidence streams to ensure that all available data is considered in qualitative and quantitative risk assessments (Figure 2). Systematic reviews are a powerful method to assemble all relevant data in support of the assessment.

Zheng et al. (2022) propose a data driven approach – burden of proof studies – complementing existing systems such as GRADE. The aim was to aggregate evidence across multiple studies and enable a quantitative comparison of risk–outcome pairs.

Figure 2. Preliminary evidence risk assessment framework proposed by Krewski et al. (2022).

Also, Trasande et al. applied GRADE criteria to rate epidemiological evidence in relation to cost calculations for exposure to endocrine disruptors (EDCs) (Trasande et al., 2015). However, there is some debate about the use of GRADE criteria for rating epidemiological studies. At ISEE 2022, Francesco Forastiere tackled this issue. GRADE criteria are developed for clinical

medicine studies and for example they categorize evidence coming from observational studies directly as having a low certainty⁹.

Further reading in the study on costs associated with exposure to endocrine disruptors, toxicological evidence related to the impact of endocrine disruptors was evaluated by criteria recently promulgated by the Danish Environmental Protection Agency for evaluating laboratory and animal evidence of endocrine disruption (Hass et al., 2012; Trasande et al., 2015). To evaluate the strength of the toxicological evidence related to endocrine disruption a Delphi approach, based on expert judgement, was followed. Another option to assess the quality or reliability of toxicological data is the use of Klimisch criteria (Klimisch et al., 1997) applied by ECHA and USEPA. According to Beronius and Vandenberg, much research on endocrine disruptors would be considered of lower quality according to Klimisch criteria and these criteria would miss key information relevant for human health (Beronius and Vandenberg, 2016). In this case more qualitative review of data quality would be necessary (OECD, 2019).

3. Approaches addressing causality starting from integrated multiple data sources

3.1 Adverse outcome pathways

Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) give more insight into biochemical and physiological pathways and help to address causality. Information from observational studies, in vivo studies, in vitro studies, etc. are brought together in AOPs. An AOP starts at the molecular level where a chemical interacts with a biological target which leads to a sequential series of higher-order events to produce an adverse health effect. Quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) were first described by (Villeneuve et al., 2014). The OECD defines qAOPS as “an assembly of key events (KEs) supported by descriptions of how the KEs can be measured and the accuracy and precision with which the measurements are made along with key event relationships (KERs) supported by a quantitative understanding of what magnitude and/or duration of change in the upstream KE is needed to evoke some magnitude of change in the downstream KE”. Spînu et al. (2022) describe how causality can make qAOPS more credible. Modified Bradford Hill criteria have been recently applied for evaluating KERs in qAOP models and can serve as a starting point on the causality ladder (Becker et al., 2015) (Perkins et al., 2019) (Spînu et al., 2022). These modified criteria include a) biological plausibility and b) empirical support (exposure-response, temporality, and incidence) for KERs, and c) essentiality of KEs. Next to this narrative approach, quantitative methods like multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) look promising to increase reproducibility in the weight of evidence and deal with complex datasets (Becker et al., 2015).

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3-kzGwvhoek>

3.2 DAGs

Causal relationships between variables can be described with a causal diagram or a DAG (directed acyclic graph, containing no closed loops & bidirectional arrows). Each node is a variable, and an arrow indicates a causal effect. To logic models as DAGs, GRADE could be applied (Hoffmann et al., 2022). Also modified Bradford Hill criteria may be applied (Ferguson et al., 2020; Hoffmann et al., 2022).

A short introduction to DAGs is described in (Moodie and Stephens, 2010).

Directed acyclic graphs are a valuable approach for:

- Clarifying causality assumptions such as temporality and previously known cause-effect relationships;
- Identifying unmeasured confounding and assess potential impacts;
- Identifying the most relevant variables and assess their consideration in the performed analysis (confounders vs. modifiers vs. mediators);
- Identifying time-dependent confounding;
- Clarifying multiple exposure assumptions that could be useful in the analysis or interpretation of the results.

Directed acyclic graphs have been proposed as a tool to improve weight of evidence causal assessments (Brewer et al., 2017). DAGs could help identify an appropriate set of confounders to be taken into account when assessing the quality of individual studies. They provide a visual way to represent key concepts such as confounding, causation, and experimentation (Shrier and Platt, 2008). Specifically, reviewers might build DAGs and apply expert judgment to state and assess the validity of the assumptions required to interpret the results of a study causally, even if DAGs were not used in the original study design and analysis (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2022).

3.3 Bayesian networks

Bayesian network is a potential method of formally weighing and combining evidence across evidence lines (Moe et al., 2020; Krewski et al., 2022). In here imperfections of each type of evidence are captured in the form of conditional probabilities linking evidence of various types and qualities to hypothesis in a Bayesian network (Krewski et al., 2022). An example of this approach was described for mutagenicity testing (Jaworska et al., 2010). A Bayesian network analysis is a kind of a DAG representing the joint probability of a problem.

3.4 Bayesian models

Bayesian models could be used to incorporate results from multiple exposure-response models (Thomas et al., 2013). When study designs are comparable, combined analysis of the primary raw data may be possible. The advantage is that the statistical power can increase and that the same statistical model is applied to all data. Scholten et al. (2022) applied a Bayesian meta-regression model including epidemiological, human biomarker, and animal data to derive an exposure response curve for acute myeloid leukemia related to benzene exposure. For addressing causality, plausible biological hypotheses will still be necessary with consideration of mechanistic data including NAMs (new approach methodoliges).

3.5 Categorical regression

Categorical regression can be used to combine data from diverse sources (toxicity and epidemiological studies, NAMs) (Farrell et al., 2022) (Krewski et al., 2022). Different health outcomes can be placed on a common severity scale. A division can be made indicating if events (or biomarkers) are reversible or not. Adjustments for inter-species differences can be made (Farrell et al., 2022). CatReg is a software package from USEPA to perform categorical regression. A similar approach is proposed by (Sand et al., 2018). Probabilities of response are integrated over the entire severity domain to produce an overall response in terms of the most severe health effect (Sand, 2022). A system of 9 severity weights was applied by Sand (Figure 3). Sequential severity of toxicity (SST) is a concept implemented in the generalisation of the hazard and risk characterisation process. Instead of using a specific reference point (RP) for developing human exposure guidelines, the sequence of reference points with different severity is attempted to be characterised. This sequence is called the reference point profile (RPP). In terms of exposure response concordance between key events, evolved Bradford Hill criteria could be applied (Meek et al., 2014). A mode of action/human relevance framework (MOA/HR) is proposed by Meek et al. in the systematic consideration of the weight of evidence (WoE) of hypothesized MOA(s) for critical effects and their relevance to humans. The WoE for a hypothesized MOA in animals is based on considerations modified from those proposed by Bradford Hill for assessment of causality in epidemiological studies (Table 3).

Table 3. Definition of evolved Bradford Hill consideration for application in MOA analysis.

Consideration	Explanation
Consistency	Is the pattern of effects across species/ strains/ organs/test systems what would be expected?
Essentiality of key events	Is the sequence of events reversible if dosing is stopped or a key event prevented?
Temporal concordance	Are the key events observed in hypothesized order?
Dose-response concordance	Are the key events observed at doses below or similar to those associated with the end (adverse) effect?
Biological concordance	Does the hypothesized MOA conflict with broader biological knowledge? How well established is the MOA in the wider biological database?
Analogy	Would the MOA be anticipated based on broader chemical specific knowledge?
Incidence concordance	Is the occurrence of the end (adverse) effect less than that for preceding key events?

ADDITIONAL DELIVERABLE AD6.6

S-intervals associated with C1 - C9	0.0160	0.0390	0.0920	0.2020	0.3875	0.6125	0.7980	0.9080	0.9610	0.9840
Severity category (for specific health effects)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	
General health effect descriptions	Block 1 (C1 or C2)		Block 2 (C2, C3, or C4)		Block 3 (C4, C5, or C6)		Block 4 (C6, C7, or C8)		Block 5 (C8 or C9)	
Hepatotoxicity or nephrotoxicity	<p>Early markers of toxicity: Change in biological or biochemical markers that may be precursors of adverse health effects (e.g., hematology, red blood cells, hematocrit, plasma protein). Early clinical signs of toxicity: For example, ruffled hair or changed activity in experimental studies, or irritation (e.g., redness, salivation) of epithelial or mucosal surface in contact with chemical, laxative effects.</p>		Change in liver/kidney enzyme/marker levels. Change in absolute/relative kidney/liver weight		Change in liver/kidney pathology/function		Increase of cell necrosis. Moderate/severe organ dysfunction		<p>Highly severe and fatal systemic toxicity with fulminant organ failure: For example, increase in mortality, lethal neurological, cardiovascular, or autoimmune effects</p>	
Neurotoxicity			Change in (mild) neurochemical or neurophysiological markers		Change in central/peripheral neuropathology. Change in brain weight. Change in mild/moderate behavioral, neurological, or neurophysiological effects		Change in moderate/severe behavioral, neurological, or neurophysiological effects. Moderate/severe organ dysfunction.			
Pulmonary or cardiovascular toxicity			Change in clinical chemistry parameters or markers		Change in function (e.g., blood pressure, ECG rhythm). Hypertrophy, hyperplasia		Moderate/severe organ dysfunction			
Immunotoxicity			Change in immune cell parameters/markers (e.g., antibody, cytokine or chemokine levels, lymphocyte numbers).		Functional effects on the immune system (e.g., reduced antibody production, decreased NK cell activity). Sensitization.		Reduced host resistance in experimental infection and tumor models. Allergic reactions.			
Gastrointestinal toxicity			Irritation, hyperplasia		Inflammation, pathology		Moderate/severe organ dysfunction			
General organ toxicity			Change in organ specific markers of toxicity (e.g., changes in clinical chemistry parameters, hormones). Change in absolute/relative organ weight.		Macroscopic pathology (e.g., fat accumulation, oedema, pale color)		Microscopic pathology (e.g., inflammation, necrosis, severe fatty infiltration)			
Developmental toxicity			Change in offspring organ/body weight or size, and litter data		Functional deficiencies; alterations/delays in the physiological and/or biochemical competence of an organ or organ system. Mild structural variation.		Increase in offspring malformations (moderate/severe structural variation). Moderate/severe functional deficiencies.			
Reproductive toxicity			Change in biochemical markers (e.g., hormones, enzymes). Change in reproductive organ weights		Pathological changes in reproductive organs. Functional effects of changes in estrus cycle. Change in sperm counts, motility, or morphology, and duration of pregnancy		Decreased fertility or number of fetuses			
Cancer			Genetic toxicity in vivo		Increase in pre-neoplastic cellular lesions		Increase in cancer risk (benign or malign cancer forms)			
Other toxicity										
<p>Note: The scheme is a development of that in NFA (2015). The lower and upper end of the scheme is linked to “early markers of toxicity / clinical signs of toxicity”, and “highly severe and fatal systemic toxicity with fulminant organ failure”, respectively. More central parts of the scheme describe organ-specific events. General descriptions of target organ toxicity are organized in five blocks, which are linked to an overlapping nine-graded severity scale (C1 to C9) according to which specific health effects are categorized. Each severity category is associated with a quantitative interval for the severity of toxicity, S, that range between 0 and 1. S-intervals are constructed by assuming a symmetrical reference point profile (RPP) as described in Figure 1. C1-C3, C4-C6, and C7-C9 is the lower, central, and upper part of the RPP, respectively.</p> <p>Developmental toxicity: Health effects on the developing organism that may result from exposure prior to conception, during prenatal development, or postnatally to the time of sexual maturation; effects may be detected at any point in the lifespan of the organism (EPA 1991).</p> <p>Reproductive toxicity: Health effects on the reproductive capacity of the parent generation.</p>										

Figure 3. Severity scale applied by Sand et al. (2018) for categorical regression analysis

4. Conclusion and recommendations

Different frameworks addressing causality in hazard assessment exist (EFSA, ECHA, ANSES, ATHLETE project). Overall, these frameworks consist of different phases starting with problem formulation, assembling evidence in lines of evidence, integrating and weighing the evidence lines. The quality of the evidence is being evaluated taking into account uncertainty. With the integration of NAMs, mechanistic evidence etc., an increasing variety of data needs to be taken into account and a holistic approach is therefore needed.

Recommendation for methodological improvements mentioned by the different frameworks include o.a.:

1) Initiation of work for the integration of different types of evidence in chemical risk assessment, including in vivo, in vitro, in silico, omics, PBPK modelling as well as the Mode of Action and Adverse Outcome Pathway concepts.

2) The increased use of metabolic systems in in vitro data and the extrapolation from in vitro to in vivo by modeling is being explored. This might possibly allow the future use of in vitro data for developing exposure response functions with relevance for risk assessment in humans. Bayesian models (Scholten et al., 2022) or categorical regression models combining different types of data are being explored but for addressing causality, plausible biological hypotheses will still be necessary with consideration of mechanistic data.

3) Currently, results from in silico and in vitro tests tend to make a lesser contribution to the overall WoE of hazard identification but this may change with time.

4) The data landscape for chemical prioritization and risk assessment continues to change and now includes multiple sources of non-traditional data. WoE approaches will necessarily need to continue to evolve and adapt to meet this data context, particularly as it relates to 21st century risk science (including exposure science), IATA and development and support for AOPs. A case study on the integration and application of alternative data for decision-making could provide an ideal example to demonstrate the principles and elements described in this document.

Some data sources are already based on a set of multiple types of data. In adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) different types of data are brought together and modified or evolved Bradford Hill considerations could be applied to assess causality. In directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) or other types of network analysis as Bayesian networks also evolved Bradford Hill criteria or GRADE criteria could be applied to assess causality.

The approach worked out in the Athlete project is very pragmatic and could be used as a basis for the case studies on EBD or HIA in PARC. The Athlete framework allows the inclusion of a quantitative indication of the causality and associated uncertainty for a given exposure-outcome pair.

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Annex IV

Selection strategy for case studies

The proposed framework includes the following steps: 1) problem formulation, 2) list of the case studies to rank, 3) criteria definition, 4) criteria documentation, 5) aggregation and weighting of criteria, 6) selection process, and 7) communication of the results including uncertainty analysis.

Problem formulation

We want to select the case studies on health impact assessment and environmental burden of disease to implement in year 2 (i.e., 2023). The selection process will be a recurring annual activity in T6.2.4.

List of the case studies to rank

The items to rank are the case studies that will be proposed by partners of the 6.2.4, in cooperation with 2.1 on priority settings or other PARC boards if considered relevant and feasible. Any partners of the T6.2.4 can submit a case study.

A case study is defined as an exposure-effect pair, for which an EBD, HIA or SCBA will be performed. The exposure can be a single substance or a mixture of substances. The exposure should explicitly state one or several substances names (e.g., mercury and lead), not only their groups or families (e.g., metals). Similarly, the effect should be explicitly stated (e.g., IQ loss), not only its broad category (e.g., neurodevelopment).

Criteria definition

We propose a set of criteria related to the following categories:

- Context – the rationale behind the case study proposal and the context of its implementation (such as involved partners and contribution).
- Description – Target populations, exposure scenarios and health outcomes should be relevant for PARC objectives, for stakeholders (including policy and regulatory) needs, and for general public concerns.
- Data – The data that will be used in the calculation of the EBD or HIA. Case studies to be implemented first need a high level of “readiness”, with already- or almost-available data for the EBD or HIA calculation. This section is linked with other WP and projects within WP6.
- Design – We want to prioritize case studies providing improvements or innovations or filling the gaps identified within the other projects of 6.2.4 (data availability and methodological improvements).

Criteria documentation

Within each criteria sit multiple sub-criteria that need to be documented and scored. To document the sub-criteria, case study holders have to fill in a “case study proposal template” before the selection process. To score the sub-criteria, we defined scoring rules and levels as showed in the table below. Two reviewers were assigned to each proposal.

Aggregation and weighting of criteria

Once the criteria are documented, a performance matrix will be constructed, which reflects how each case study proposal perform on each criterion. By default, the same weight (=1) is attributed to all criteria, meaning they will have the same importance in the selection process. A different set of weights can be proposed in order to translate the relative difference between criteria or sub-criteria, that can reflect for example the relevance for stakeholders and public of the relevance in conducting the case study. The possibility of different weights can be refined as we go through discussion with PARC boards and WP2 or as part of a sensitivity analysis (to check the robustness of the selection process). As a result of refining the weight structure, the final result i.e. the selection will change.

Selection process

The selection process compares the case studies within each criterion and produces the overall ranking. We propose to use an outranking method over an utility-based method because we have experience with the former. The primary considered approach is PROMETHEE. A nice illustration can be found in Fazil et al. (2008).

Outranking methods are mathematical approaches that build a preference relation between a set of alternatives in a binary way (Bouyssou, 2001). This relation is created by comparing the alternative pairwise using the concordance-discordance principle stating that “x is at least as good as y” and there is no reason to refute this assumption.

Communication of the results

We propose to express the results of the selection process in “tiers for implementation” reflecting how the case studies performed overall across criteria. The results of sensitivity analyses (from different sets of weights for example) can be used to support or discuss the position of case studies.

Score levels and rules						
Category	Criteria	Sub-criteria	High	Moderate	Low	Comments
CONTEXT	Context	Rationale	All questions are answered. Documentation or references are provided. The case study answers a clear data gap or health issue.	Questions are partially answered. Documentation is lacking. The objective or added value of the case study is not clear enough.	Some questions are left not answered. No documentation is provided. The case study does not answer any data gap and does not fit with PARC priorities.	We proposed some indicators we can rely on during the qualitative assessment of this criterion.
		Partners	≥ 4 partners	3 partners	1 or 2 partners	
		Contribution	PMs available for the T6.2.4. in Y1 or Y2 + good or partial expertise in EBD or HIA	Default score when does not fit in the other levels	No PMs available for the T6.2.4 in the next 3 years + partial or no expertise in EBD or HIA	We'll look at the PMs per partners to document this line, using Y2 and Y7 numbers. To complement this point, we'll ask the expertise of the partners in the template.
DESCRIPTION	Population	Target	Sensitive or vulnerable population: children, pregnant women, elderly, disadvantaged	General population or workers	Others	
		Location	≥ 4 countries within Europe	2 to 3 countries within Europe	Sole country or region	
	Exposure	Substance(s)	Fit with PARC priorities for this year (including stakeholder needs (policy, regulatory))		Does not fit with PARC priorities for this year (including stakeholder needs (policy, regulatory))	For Y1, we consider PARC priority list to fit with stakeholder's needs. For next iterations, we will be able to revise this sub criterion depending on WP2 input and PARC list.
		Cross-cutting activity	Existing link with T6.2.3, T6.2.1 or other tasks case studies.		No link identified.	
		Levels	Levels above or close to an established health-based guidance value or	Default score when does not fit in the other two levels.	Levels below an established health-based guidance value	If there is no reference or guidance value, exposure levels are expected to be compared with levels outside of Europe. For mixtures, the

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		regulatory reference value.		or regulatory reference value.	comparison (with reference value or other location) has to be made with at least one substance. If no comparison is given in the template, then a default moderate score is assigned. As we assume most of the case studies will be chronic, this criterion could not be discriminative. It can be discarded if necessary. Links with T4.1 HBM surveys and T6.2.1 case studies.	
		Scenario	Chronic	Subchronic	Acute	
		Type	HBM data at individual level	Individual-level estimation	Population-level estimation	
Health outcome	Prevalence, incidence		High (>10 %)	Moderate (1 % to 10 %)	Low (<1 %)	We proposed 10 % here as a limit for “high” prevalence.
	Severity		Cancer, reproduction, development, neurodevelopment, mortality.	Immunology, neurology, other targeted-organ effect (kidney disease...)	Others (cardiovascular, obesity...)	Neurodevelopment (i.e. children) is considered high level whilst neurology (i.e. adults) is moderate level. Immunology includes asthma and allergy.
	Mechanism of action		Endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity	Others	-	Focus on EDC and immunotoxicity is made for Y1, it can be adapted for the next iterations.
	Health outcome(s)		Fit with PARC priorities for this year and relevant for EBD or HIA	-	Does not fit with PARC priorities for this year or not relevant for EBD or HIA	This sub-criterion will be updated at each recurrence of the selection process.
	Cross-cutting activity		Existing link with T6.2.3, T6.2.1 or other tasks case studies.	-	No link identified.	We must be careful that this sub-criterion is not too redundant with the exposure one. They could be merged if necessary.
DATA	Exposure data	Availability	Available within the first year of the case study (2023)	Available within the first two years (2024)	Not available or expected to be generated or no	

		Quality assessment	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	information on availability Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Qualitative assessment
	Health data	Availability	Available within the first year of the case study (2023)	Available within the first 2 years (2024)	Not available or expected to be generated or no information on availability	
		Quality assessment	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Qualitative assessment
	Exposure-risk function	Availability	Available within the first year of the case study (2023)	Available within the first 2 years (2024) or has to be derived within the case study	Not available or expected to be generated or no information on availability	
		Quality assessment	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Cf. Check list for quality assessment below*.	Qualitative assessment
DESIGN	Method	Type of indicator	Clearly stated indicator of health impact (e.g., DALYs, QALYs, PAF, number of attributable cases)		Risk indicators (e.g., margin of Exposure, Hazard quotient, Hazard index)	Link with the “indicator” project of T6.2.4. For the next iteration, we’ll have to make sure the proposed indicator is relevant for and support policy cycle.
		Methodological improvement	Yes		No	Links with the “method” project of T6.2.4. For Y1, as the project is still ongoing, we could check if SES stratification and WoE assessment can be considered in the case study.
	Uncertainties	Uncertainties	If uncertainties clearly identified and controlled.	If uncertainties partly controlled.	No information.	

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* This check-list is proposed as guidance to assess and score the 3 sub-criteria related to the quality of the data.

Category	Criteria	Indicators	Yes	Partial	No	Conclusion
DATA	Exposure data	Matches the target population in terms of age and exposure levels				
		HBM data (if used) come from HBM4EU or PARC aligned studies				
		Standardized or harmonized method for measurements				
	Health data	Transparent and sound hypotheses, assumptions, or scenarios (if any)				
		Matches the target population in terms of age and exposure levels				
		The data selected is recent or match the time period of the exposure data				
	Exposure-risk function (ERF)	Standardized or harmonized method for measurements				
		Transparent and sound hypotheses, assumptions, or scenarios (if any)				
		Matches the target population in terms of age and exposure levels				
		Method of derivation is based on effect in humans				
		Models (if used) are standardized or validated				
		ERF derived from meta-analysis				
		Heavy weight-of-the-evidence				

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Annex V

Development of indicators

Aim

- Develop indicators related to risk and health impact to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations
- Complement and support monitoring frameworks for e.g., the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Strategy, and the 8th Environment Action Programme
- Thereby supporting national and European policy makers, e.g.:
 - *prioritization of preventive or mitigatory actions*
 - *estimation of burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of policies and regulations*

Activities Y1

1. Inventory of indicators (M1-M12)	Inventory of existing types of indicators based on scientific and grey literature search, communication materials of (inter)national organisations, stakeholder input and cooperation with other initiatives such as ATHLETE. Attention will be given to total impact, time-trends, spatial differences, impact of socio-economic status and regular update of the indicators.	ANSES (FR), ENSP (PT), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), OI (SI), Sciensano (BE), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL)
2. Proposal for indicators (M9-M12) <i>Recurring activity</i>	Propose a set of indicators to assess the impact human health (risk) of selected exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates and dynamics of population exposure and health risk) to inform policy makers and to contribute to the Partnership monitoring framework, in consultation with WHO, EEA and ECHA and with T1.3, WP2 and WP3, and taking 'Timelines of opportunity' into account.	ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), OI (SI), Sciensano (BE), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE)

PARC priorities

- Bisphenols
- EDC
- Flame retardants
- Pesticides
- PFAS
- Phthalates
- Metals
- Mixtures
- Mycotoxins

Exposure

Health outcomes

Target population

Indicator types		
<p>Indicator types</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure • Risk • Health impact 	<p>To do</p> <p>Prepare a concise overview of exposure, risk and health impact indicators that are already in use</p> <p>➔ To be defined which indicators we could develop for specific exposures/exposure-effect relations in PARC</p>	<p>Contributors</p> <p>ENSP NIJZ VITO FMUL UU-IRAS Sciensano WR-BIOM AUTH</p>

Indicator type	Subcategory	Examples
Exposure	Number of people exposed	Lead exposure forms an established risk factor for hypertension, renal failure, cardiovascular diseases, and stroke in adults. While in children, neurodevelopmental toxicity is the most important consequence of lead exposure. It is estimated that around 16.8 million individuals are exposed each year worldwide to dangerous concentrations of lead at used lead-acid battery recycling sites (Landrigan et al., 2018).
	Exposure levels	Cadmium is known to particularly affect the kidneys and cause renal failure. Additionally, it is also a known carcinogen and reprotoxic agent, and contributes to the risk of osteoporosis. The recommended health-based guidance values set in place by EFSA amounts to 1 µg/g _{creatinine} at a later age (> 50). New data on Cd-exposure from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2510 individuals) have reported P50- and P90-values, of urinary Cd-concentrations, to be in the ranges of respectively 0.10 – 0.37 µg/g and 0.26 – 1.71 µg/g across studies in adults. For the subpopulation of non-smokers, P50- and P90-values of urinary Cd-concentrations were in the range of 0.09 – 0.36 mg/g and 0.23 – 1.56 µg/g respectively across studies in adults. HBM4EU Policy-Brief-Cadmium.pdf
	Exposure trends	The primary health concern associated with Cr(+VI) is carcinogenicity. A decreasing trend was observed in urinary concentrations of Cr(+VI) in occupationally exposed Belgian workers (3799 workers from different industries) between 1998 and 2018 (30% reduction in urinary Cr(+VI)-levels) (Verdonck et al., 2021). The same trend was also observed in Finland from biomonitoring measurements collected between 1980 and 2016 (Mahiout et al., 2022).
	Probability of exposure	Glyphosate is a herbicide which is several pathological outcomes such as teratogenic effects and increased odds of developing non-Hodgkin’s lymphoma. According to Kongtip et al. (2017), women with serum glyphosate levels above the LOD at childbirth were 11.9 times more likely to report working as an agriculturist, 3.7 times more likely to live near agricultural areas, and 5.9 times more likely to have a family member working in agriculture (Kongtip et al., 2017).
Risk	Margin of Exposure (MoE)	According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), aflatoxins are IARC group 1 carcinogens, known to cause hepatocellular carcinomas in humans, with

		<p>aflatoxin B1 being considered the most potent aflatoxin. Based on the BMDL₁₀-value proposed by EFSA, MOE-values could be estimated for two regions, one characterized by low exposure (daily intake of 0.4 ng/kg-bw/day) and one by high exposure (daily intake of 2.6 ng.kg-bw/day), this led respectively to an MOE of 600 and 100 (Benford et al., 2010).</p>
	<p>Risk Quotients (RQ)</p>	<p>Cadmium (nephrotoxic, carcinogenic, reprotoxic) and chromium (carcinogenic) are toxic metals of which exposure is known to occur through food. Therefore, chocolate drink powders were analyzed for the presence of these metals in Brazil. It was found that concentrations of Cd and Cr ranged between 12 – 124 µg/kg and 81 – 4790 µg/kg, respectively. Based on this, the contributions of daily consumption of chocolate drink powder for children would represent 4 – 35 % of the provisional tolerable weekly intake of Cd and 0.03 – 0.14% of the tolerable daily intake of Cr, thus corresponding to risk quotients lower than 0.04 and 0.001 for Cd and Cr, respectively (Regina et al., 2018).</p>
	<p>Risk characterization ratio (RCR)</p>	<p>Bisphenols are linked to a variety of health outcomes in humans (e.g., endocrine disruption, metabolic diseases, cancer). Based on human biomonitoring data (HBM4EU) collected in various European countries, RCR-values (based on P95 urinary biomarker dose) were calculated for bisphenol A (BPA) and S (BPS). For BPA, the RCR-values (ranging between 0.01 - 0.14) were well below 1 for all HBM-studies considered, thus indicating that current exposure levels do not constitute a risk. However, RCRs obtained for BPS vastly exceeded 1 in some population groups (ranging from 0.4 - 28.9, with most RCRs > 1). Therefore, health risks associated with exposure to BPS cannot be excluded (Meslin et al., 2022).</p>
	<p>External exposure > health-based guidance values</p>	<p>Air pollution exposure is closely associated with cardiovascular (e.g., ischemic heart disease and stroke, hemorrhagic stroke) and respiratory (e.g., respiratory tract infections and cancers, COPD, asthma) diseases. Despite significant reductions in emissions of air pollutants (30% decrease in PM_{2.5}) having occurred between 2000 and 2017, 74 – 81% of the European population was still exposed to PM_{2.5}-levels far exceeding the (now outdated) WHO limit value of 10 µg/m³ in the years 2015 – 2017 (Sicard et al., 2021).</p>

	Internal exposure > health-based guidance values	<p>Cadmium is known to particularly affect the kidneys and cause renal failure. Additionally, it is also a known carcinogen and reprotoxic agent, and contributes to the risk of osteoporosis. Based on internal exposure data from HBM4EU (adult population, 20 – 39 years of age), the urinary Cd-concentration of some adults in the EU exceeded the recommended health-based guidance values (1 µg/g_{creatinine} at > 50 years of age). Exceedances in the different studies and regions ranged from 1.42% to 41.98%. HBM4EU Policy-Brief-Cadmium.pdf</p>
	Risk-benefit analysis	<p>Seafood is recognized as a healthy food choice since it provides a high source of protein and omega-3 fatty acids as well as a low amount of fats. However, seafood is also known to contain certain contaminants (persistent organic pollutants, methyl mercury and other heavy metals), which can induce harmful effects on human health and development. Risk-benefit analyses have been used to determine the most optimal consumption of seafood. In 2001, an advisory was sent out by the US FDA recommending individuals at risk (pregnant women, children under 6) to limit their seafood consumption. This in turn led to a 21.4% reduction in seafood, which resulted in a decline in MeHg-exposure (associated with a benefit of +0.012 IQ-points/child) and a decline in omega-3 fatty acids intake (associated with -0.008 IQ-points/child and with an increase in coronary heart disease and stroke mortality of +0.63/10⁵ adults). From this, the net health impact following decreasing seafood consumption was estimated to value -30 USD, thus suggesting that seafood consumption outweighs the risks. Moreover, when overall fish consumption was maintained solely with consumption of low-mercury fish (e.g., salmon, shrimps), the net benefits were even greater (at +0.039 IQ-points/child, valuing at 587 USD) (Hellberg et al., 2012).</p>
	Risk of disease	<p>A causal association between human arsenic exposure and lung, skin, and bladder cancer has been recognized. Arsenic is furthermore also linked with cardiovascular diseases, stroke, diabetes, skin lesions, and <i>in utero</i> effects. The daily intake of inorganic arsenic was estimated based on average HBM-levels from HBM studies and kinetic modelling (0.16 µg/kg-bw/day), which corresponded with a lifetime excess lung cancer risk of 2.7×10^{-4} HBM4EU Policy-Brief-Arsenic.pdf</p>
Health impact	Changes in activities (i.e., restricted activity days)	<p>Exposure to PFAS has been associated with a broad range of toxicological outcomes, with immunotoxicity (increased pneumonia incidence, reduced vaccine antibody titers)</p>

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		being one of the most sensitive health effects. It has been estimated that an additional 1.5 million days of fever (proxy for immunotoxicity of PFAS) are caused in the European Economic Area (EEA) due to individuals who are moderately exposed to PFAS (through drinking water, proximity to industrial sites, etc.) (Goldenman et al., 2019).
	Changes in life expectancy	Between 1990 and 2017, the life expectancy at birth increased by 7.4 years globally, from 65.5 years in 1990 to 73.0 years in 2017 (Kyu et al., 2018).
	Attributable numbers of cases/deaths	It has been estimated with a strong probability (70 – 100%) that each year in the European Union, 13.0 million IQ points are lost due to prenatal exposure to organophosphate pesticides, and 59 300 additional cases of intellectual disability. With more modest probabilities, 316 cases of autism and 19 400 to 31 200 new cases of ADHD are attributable to endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) (Trasande et al., 2015).
	Population Attributable Fraction (PAF) for morbidity or mortality	Alcohol use is causally linked to multiple cancers (e.g., esophageal, liver and breast cancer). Globally, an estimated 741 300, or 4.1% of all new cancer cases in 2020 were attributable to alcohol consumption. PAFs were lowest in northern Africa (0.3%) and western Asia (0.7%), and highest in eastern Asia (5.7%) and central and eastern Europe (5.6%) (Rumgay et al., 2021).
	Disability Adjusted Life years (DALYs)	Lead exposure forms an established risk factor for hypertension, renal failure, cardiovascular diseases, and stroke in adults. While in children, neurodevelopmental toxicity is the most important consequence of lead exposure. The Global Burden of Disease study indicated that lead was responsible for 9.3 million DALYs worldwide in adults (age 15 and older) in 2015 (Landrigan et al., 2018).
	Quality adjusted life years (QALYs)	Air pollution exposure is closely associated with cardiovascular (e.g., ischemic heart disease and stroke, hemorrhagic stroke) and respiratory (e.g., respiratory tract infections and cancers, COPD, asthma) diseases. Reducing PM2.5-concentrations by 1 µg/m ³ is estimated to yield more than 540 000 QALYs to adults aged 40 and above over their remaining lifetime in England and Wales (Schmitt, 2016).
	Healthy Life Expectancy (HALE)	Healthy life expectancy (HALE) quantifies the number of life years expected to be lived in good health, it is a complementary measure to the DALY, and is also calculated based on YLLs due to premature mortality and YLDs. Between 1990 and 2017, HALE at birth increased by 6.3 years globally from 57.0 years in 1990 to 63.3 years in 2017. The

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		increase varied from 3.8 years in high socio-demographic index (SDI) countries to 10.5 years in low SDI countries (Kyu et al., 2018).
	Use of health care services	Exposure to PFAS has been associated with a broad range of toxicological outcomes such as immunotoxicity (increased pneumonia incidence, reduced vaccine antibody titers), cardiovascular toxicity, reproductive toxicity (infertility, low birth weight), nephrotoxicity, endocrine disruption (type 2 diabetes, obesity), and various cancers. A doubling in maternal PFOS body burden was associated with a 23% (hazard ratio of 1.23) increased risk of hospitalization due to infections in infants aged 0 – 4 years (Dalsager et al., 2021).
	Costs associated with health impact	Exposure to PFAS has been associated with a broad range of toxicological outcomes such as immunotoxicity (increased pneumonia incidence, reduced vaccine antibody titers), cardiovascular toxicity, reproductive toxicity (infertility, low birth weight), nephrotoxicity, endocrine disruption (type 2 diabetes, obesity), and various cancers. It has been estimated that the total costs associated with PFAS-related health outcomes amounts to 5.52 – 62.6 billion USD in the USA (Obsekov et al., 2022), while the total health-related costs in the EEA amount to 52 – 84 billion EUR (Goldenman et al., 2019).
	(Social) cost benefit analyses (S)CBA	Air pollution exposure is closely associated with cardiovascular (e.g., ischemic heart disease and stroke, hemorrhagic stroke) and respiratory (e.g., respiratory tract infections and cancers, COPD, asthma) diseases. Since the Clean Air Act has been passed in the USA, concentrations of six common air pollutants have been reduced by about 70% while GDP has increased by nearly 250% in the same period. It is estimated that 30 USD (in benefits) has been returned to the economy for every dollar invested in air pollution control and prevention measures since 1970. This has resulted in an aggregate benefit of 1.5 trillion USD against an investment of 65 billion USD (Landrigan et al., 2018).

Purpose		
	<p>To do</p> <p>Prepare a concise overview of policy/regulatory frameworks in which indicators are already used</p> <p>➔ To be defined (i) how to support these frameworks and (ii) how to complement them</p>	<p>Contributors</p> <p>ENSP VITO AUTH</p>

Policy / regulatory context	Type of indicator	Status (published, under development, planned, ..)
WHO Environmental Burden of Disease Global health estimates: Leading causes of DALYs (who.int) / Indicators (who.int)	DALY	Published
UN Sustainable Development Goals Progress Chart — SDG Indicators (un.org)	Mortality rate (per 10 ⁵ population)	Published
	DALY	Published
	Pollutant concentration	Published
8th Environment Action Programme Monitoring framework for the 8th Environment Action Programme (europa.eu)	Number of premature deaths/YLL (premature death due to exposure to fine particulate matter PM2.5)	Published
EEA European Topic Center “Human Health and the Environment” ETC HE products — Eionet Portal (europa.eu)		
EC Zero Pollution Action Plan Actions (europa.eu)		
EC Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability		Indicator framework under development by JRC and EA
EC Farm to Fork strategy		Indicator framework under development by JRC

Timeline		
<p>Timeline</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data availability • Policy cycle 	<p>To do</p> <p>Map policy processes/cycles that could make use of PARC T6.2.4 indicators via stakeholder consultation and WP2/WP3 interaction</p> <p>➔ To be defined which (types of) indicators can feed these processes/cycles at which point in time</p>	<p>Contributors</p> <p>VITO, UU-IRAS, OI, SCIENSANO, ENSP, WR-BIOM, FMUL</p>

Stakeholder consultation to be organized:

- WP2 and WP3
- EEA, EFSA, ECHA, JRC
-

Mapping exercise? Eg. [‘Timelines of opportunity’](#) (HBM4EU)

Partner interests		
	<p>To do</p> <p>List specific indicators that T6.2.4 partners would like to develop, with an eye on PARC/policy/scientific relevance, feasibility with respect to data availability, and envisaged timing</p> <p>➔ To be defined which indicators we will prioritize for year 2 and beyond</p>	<p>Contributors</p> <p>VITO, UU-IRAS, OI, SCIENSANO, ENSP, WR-BIOM, FMUL</p>

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Indicator type	Subcategory	Concrete proposals	PARC relevance	Policy relevance	Scientific relevance	Data availability	Timing	Interested partners
Exposure	Number of people exposed	Tobacco first and secondhand exposure (prevalence)		EC Smoke-free environments				FMUL Sciensano
	Exposure levels	Pesticide exposure via diet		Farm to Fork				WR-BIOM
		Implement in model network						
		HBM4EU data (Pesticides, Bisphenols, PAHs, Mycotoxins, UV-filters, Arsenic, Acrylamide, etc.)		Farm to Fork CSS		Data are already available	Year 1/2	VITO, ENSP
	PARC human biomonitoring data (à T4.1)		CSS				ENSP	
Exposure trends			CSS					
Probability of exposure								
Risk	Margin of Exposure (MoE)	Mixture risks						WR-BIOM
		Implement in model network						
	Risk Quotients (RQ)	Mixture risks		CSS				WR-BIOM
		Implement in model network						
Risk characterization ratio (RCR)								
External exposure > health-based guidance values	Implement in model network						WR-BIOM VITO ENSP	

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	Internal exposure > health-based guidance values	Implement in model network						WR-BIOM VITO ENSP
	Risk-benefit analysis	Dietary exposure (contaminants vs. nutritional value)		EFSA				Sciensano, ENSP
	Risk of disease	Cancer incidence		JRC		Cancer data are already available		OI
Health impact <i>To be linked to T6.2. 4 case studies</i>	Changes in activities (i.e. restricted activity days)							
	Changes in life expectancy							
	Attributable numbers of cases/deaths							
	Population Attributable Fraction (PAF) for morbidity or mortality			CSS, JRC		Cancer data are already available		UU-IRAS Sciensano OI VITO ENSP
	Disability Adjusted Life years (DALYs)	Implement in model network		CSS, JRC		Cancer data are already available		UU-IRAS Sciensano

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								OI WR-BIOM VITO ENSP
	Quality adjusted life years (QALYs)			JRC		Cancer data are already available		Sciensano OI
	Healthy Life Expectancy (HALE)							
	Use of health care services							
	Costs associated with health impact			JRC		Cancer data are already available		Sciensano ENSP
	(Social) cost benefit analyses (S)CBA			JRC		Cancer data are already available		Sciensano ENSP

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